

**Crafting Lyrics, Breaking Barriers: Exploring the Role of Rap Music in
Facilitating Mental Health Expression among Black Men in the UK**

LYNETTE MEREDITH

A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of
East London for the degree of Professional Doctorate in Clinical Psychology

May 2025

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to thank the participants who generously shared their time and experiences. I appreciate you speaking with such openness and for expressing your passion for rap in ways that brought this research to life. Your voices are the heart of this study.

Thank you to the individuals within the community organisations who kindly took the time to speak with me, offer advice, and support the recruitment process. Your insights, passion, and encouragement played a vital role in shaping this research.

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my supervisor, Dr Lorna Farquharson, for her support, guidance, and trust throughout this project. Thank you for allowing me the space to develop my own research interests and your belief in my vision for this thesis topic.

To my family and loved ones, thank you for your love, patience and support over the last three years. Your encouragement has been a constant source of strength, particularly during the final and most demanding stages of this thesis. I could not have done it without you.

ABSTRACT

Background: Black men in the UK face significant mental health inequalities, including higher rates of severe mental difficulties and lower rates of engagement with services. Systemic racism, cultural stigma and restrictive norms around masculinity have been shown to influence these disparities. While rap music has historically been used within Black communities to express personal and social struggles, its role in mental health expression remains underexplored in non-clinical contexts in the UK.

Aims: This study aimed to explore whether rap helps Black men to express mental health experiences and examine what influences disclosure.

Methods: Drawing on a critical realist epistemology, this study used qualitative methods to conduct semi-structured interviews with 11 Black men aged 24-51 who create rap music.

Results: The reflexive thematic analysis identified three overarching themes: 'Rap as Therapy', 'Navigating Vulnerability, Identity, and Stigma Through Rap', and 'Rap as Connection, Validation, and Social Influence'. Participants described the benefits of rap for self-expression and overcoming emotional difficulties, navigating identity, and facilitating social impact. Rap offered a culturally and socially safe space for self-expression, enabling participants to express vulnerability in ways often restricted by stigma and masculine norms. The lyrical and creative nature of rap allowed emotions to be communicated authentically, within the mask of rap, and on their own terms.

Conclusions: This study highlights rap's value as a culturally relevant medium for supporting mental health expression among Black men in the UK. This contributes to the growing evidence base supporting the therapeutic potential of arts-based and culturally situated mental health interventions. It also has implications for research, practice and policy, calling for more inclusive and community-informed approaches to supporting Black men's mental health.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION.....	7
1.1. Chapter Overview	7
1.2. Key Terminology.....	7
1.2.1. Black.....	7
1.2.2. Ethnic Minority	8
1.2.3. Male.....	8
1.2.4. Hip-Hop and Rap Music.....	8
1.3. Understanding Inequalities in Black Men’s Mental Health: UK Context, Challenges and Barriers to Care	9
1.3.1. Historical and Current Context in the UK	9
1.3.2. Mental Health Disparities	11
1.3.3. Black Men’s Mental Health	12
1.3.4. Models of Help-Seeking.....	13
1.3.5. Barriers to Help-Seeking.....	15
1.3.5.1. <i>History and current context of the NHS</i>	15
1.3.5.2. <i>Racism, stereotyping, and stigma</i>	16
1.3.5.3. <i>Cultural factors</i>	17
1.3.5.4. <i>Gender and masculinity</i>	18
1.3.6. Government Responses to Mental Health Inequalities	19
1.3.7. Community Initiatives.....	20
1.4. The Role of Hip-Hop Culture and Rap in Mental Health: Origins, Interventions and Relevance to Black Men	21
1.4.1. Hip-Hop Origins	21
1.4.2. Rap: A Global Voice for Self-Expression	22
1.4.3. Rap and Mental Health	24
1.4.4. Psychological and Physiological Effects of Music.....	25
1.4.5. Rap-Based Mental Health Interventions	25
1.5. Scoping Review	27
1.5.1. Scoping Review Findings.....	29
1.5.1.1. <i>Ierardi and Jenkins (2011)</i>	29
1.5.1.2. <i>Alvarez (2011)</i>	30
1.5.1.3. <i>Jefferson and Ohrt (2024)</i>	31
1.5.1.4. <i>Adeyola and Allen (2025)</i>	32
1.5.1.5. <i>Compton Dickinson and Souflas (2011)</i>	33
1.5.1.6. <i>Short (2017)</i>	34
1.5.2. Synthesis of Findings and Gaps in the Literature	35
1.6. Research Rationale and Clinical Relevance	36
1.7. Research Aims and Questions	37
2. METHODS.....	39

2.1. Chapter Overview	39
2.2. Ontological and Epistemological Position	39
2.3. Design.....	40
2.4. Participants	40
2.4.1. Inclusion Criteria	40
2.4.2. Participant Demographics.....	41
2.5. Materials	41
2.5.1. Interview Schedule	41
2.5.2. Resources.....	42
2.6. Procedure	43
2.6.1. Recruitment	43
2.6.2. Initial Contact and Informed Consent.....	43
2.6.3. Interview Process	43
2.6.4. Interview Transcription.....	44
2.6.5. Compensation.....	44
2.6.6. Data Management	45
2.7. Ethical Considerations	45
2.7.1. Informed Consent	45
2.7.2. Confidentiality and Data Protection.....	45
2.7.3. Managing Distress and Risk Management	46
2.7.4. Researcher Supervision.....	46
2.8. Analytic Approach	46
2.8.1. Rationale.....	46
2.8.2. Steps.....	47
2.8.2.1. <i>Data familiarisation</i>	47
2.8.2.2. <i>Generating initial codes</i>	47
2.8.2.3. <i>Generating themes</i>	48
2.8.2.4. <i>Reviewing themes</i>	48
2.8.2.5. <i>Defining themes</i>	48
2.8.2.6. <i>Write up</i>	48
2.8.3. Quality Assurance.....	48
2.8.3.1. <i>Researcher reflexivity</i>	48
2.8.3.2. <i>Transparency</i>	49
2.8.3.3. <i>Coherence</i>	49
2.8.3.4. <i>Data engagement, analysis, and interpretation</i>	50
3. RESULTS	51
3.2. Participant Approaches to Creating Rap	51
3.3. Thematic Summary and Map	51
3.4. Theme 1: Rap as Therapy.....	54
3.4.1. Overcoming Challenges: Rap Is a “Powerful Medicine”	54

3.4.2.	Self-Expression and Catharsis: “It Feels Like a Cry on Paper”	56
3.4.3.	Self-Awareness and Reflection: “A Record of Where My Mind Was”	59
3.4.4.	Limitations of Rap as Therapy: “You Can’t Always Therapise Yourself”	61
3.5.	Theme 2: Navigating Vulnerability, Identity, and Stigma Through Rap	63
3.5.1.	Masculinity and Stigma: “Forced to Be Tough”	63
3.5.2.	Rap as a Safe Space for Vulnerability: “I’d Rather Not Put This on You”	66
3.5.3.	Barriers to Help-Seeking: “Why Would You Trust That System?”	67
3.5.4.	Openness and Protection in Rap: “A Shield for What You Can’t Say in Person”	70
3.6.	Theme 3: Rap as Connection, Validation, and Social Influence	73
3.6.1.	Connection and Culture: “It’s That Togetherness”	73
3.6.2.	Representation: “When You See It More, It Reaffirms You’re Not Alone”	76
3.6.3.	Mutual Support and Impact: “You Might Plant the Seed”	77
4.	DISCUSSION	81
4.1.	Chapter Overview	81
4.2.	Study Aims and Findings	81
4.2.1.	‘Rap as Therapy’	81
4.2.2.	‘Navigating Vulnerability, Identity, and Stigma Through Rap’	83
4.2.3.	‘Rap as Connection, Validation, and Social Influence’	85
4.2.4.	Theoretical Relevance	88
4.3.	Critical Review	89
4.3.1.	Sensitivity to Context	89
4.3.2.	Commitment and Rigour	90
4.3.3.	Coherence and Transparency	90
4.3.4.	Impact and Importance	91
4.3.5.	Limitations.....	91
4.4.	Implications and Recommendations.....	93
4.4.1.	Research	93
4.4.2.	Practice.....	94
4.4.3.	Policy	96
4.5.	Researcher Reflections	97
4.6.	Conclusion	99
5.	REFERENCES	100
6.	APPENDICES	124
	Appendix A: The Integrated Behavioural Model of Mental Health Help Seeking Diagram (Hammer et al., 2024)	124

Appendix B: Examples of the Integrated Behavioural Model of Mental Health Help Seeking (Hammer et al., 2024)	125
Appendix C: PRISMA-ScR Diagram Demonstrating Scoping Review Literature Search	128
Appendix D: Interview Schedule	129
Appendix E: Information Sheet	131
Appendix F: Consent Form.....	135
Appendix G: Debrief Sheet	137
Appendix H: Advertisement Poster and Recruitment Strategy	140
Appendix I: Voucher Reimbursement Form	143
Appendix J: Ethics Submission, Approval with Minor Amendment and Ethics Submission with Minor Amendment.....	144
Appendix K: Excerpt of Coded Transcript	177
Appendix L: Excerpt from Reflexive Journal	178

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Chapter Overview

Mental health services in the UK face the critical challenge of effectively engaging and supporting Black men, a population with lower rates of voluntary mental health service utilisation, despite experiencing disproportionate mental health challenges (Darko, 2021; McKeown et al., 2008; Stockwell et al., 2024). This chapter examines the role of rap music as a culturally resonant and accessible tool for mental health engagement and expression among Black men, in the context of significant inequalities in mental health care and service engagement.

The chapter begins by defining key terminology and highlights current research showing inequalities faced by Black people in the UK. It then examines Black men's mental health and factors affecting engagement with mental health services, including systemic racism, cultural insensitivity in service provision, and the influence of gender and cultural norms on help-seeking behaviours. This leads to the chapter discussing rap music as a culturally significant art form, with research demonstrating that it can offer alternative approaches to engagement with mental health care. The chapter ends with a scoping review, which identifies gaps in the research literature regarding rap music's role in facilitating mental health expression among Black men in the UK. This provides a rationale for the study's aims and research questions.

1.2. Key Terminology

This thesis aims to use inclusive terminology, recognising that definitions are personal, context-dependent, and may vary across individuals.

1.2.1. Black

In this thesis, the term 'Black' encompasses individuals from the African diaspora, in particular, individuals with roots in Africa, the Caribbean, America, and other areas of the world impacted by slavery, colonialism, and migration (Rotimi et al., 2016).

While the term 'Black' will be referred to throughout, this thesis recognises that there is diversity and heterogeneity between Black individuals and communities (Abascal, Xu, & Baldassarri, 2021; Nguyen et al., 2017). Therefore, the research discussed does not aim to represent a monolithic Black experience but instead highlights shared experiences that have been identified.

1.2.2. Ethnic Minority

In the UK, the term 'ethnic minority' usually refers to all ethnic groups except for White British (HM Government, 2024). This term will be used to reflect the language used in the studies presented. However, this thesis acknowledges that other terms may be preferred (for example, 'People of the Global Majority'), to de-centre Whiteness and more accurately reflect the world population (Campbell-Stephens, 2020).

1.2.3. Male

The terms 'male' and 'men' will refer to the male gender, an identity associated with cultural and social roles, norms, and characteristics that are usually attributed to men (World Health Organization, n.d). While acknowledging the complexity of gender as a social construct, this thesis specifically focuses on adult Black men, highlighting how gendered expectations and cultural norms can impact experiences of mental health.

1.2.4. Hip-Hop and Rap Music

The terms hip-hop and rap are often used interchangeably, yet hip-hop refers to a broader culture involving rapping, deejaying, graffiti painting, breakdancing, and knowledge of self and hip-hop culture (Wells, 2019). Rap is a musical genre, often used as lyrical storytelling to address social and political issues (Kubrin, 2007; Wells, 2019). A more detailed overview of hip-hop and rap will be discussed in section 1.5.

While this thesis focuses on rap music's role in the mental health experiences of Black men, it recognises that not all Black men identify with or feel represented by rap or hip-hop culture. The focus reflects the experiences of those with a meaningful connection to the genre and does not aim to homogenise the diverse identities and interests of Black men.

1.3. Understanding Inequalities in Black Men's Mental Health: UK Context, Challenges and Barriers to Care

The relationship between Black men and mental health services in the UK is shaped by systemic inequalities and historical injustices. Situating this within a broader sociopolitical context is essential for understanding how rap may offer a culturally meaningful avenue for mental health expression and engagement.

1.3.1. Historical and Current Context in the UK

The experiences of Black communities in the UK are linked to the historical legacies of colonialism and slavery, which have constructed Black individuals as 'less than' and fundamentally 'other' (Keating et al., 2002; Reddie, 2020). These historical injustices continue to shape contemporary society through institutional and systemic racism, which is embedded in political, economic, and legal structures, and interpersonal racism, which manifests through conscious and unconscious prejudice (Bleich et al., 2019). This shapes the social, economic, and political experiences of Black individuals within British society (McKeown et al., 2008).

Following World War II, the UK experienced significant immigration from Caribbean countries, particularly between 1948 and 1971, a movement referred to as the arrival of the 'Windrush generation' (King & Torrington, 1996). These individuals were invited to the UK to help rebuild the post-war economy. However, they encountered widespread discrimination and exclusion in employment, housing and public services (Wardle & Obermuller, 2019). During the 1960s and 1970s, a disproportionate number of Caribbean boys were labelled as 'educationally subnormal' and placed in special schools with limited academic opportunities, achievement and job prospects, subsequently contributing to intergenerational disadvantage (Coard, 1971). Institutional racism was also evident in policing and the criminal justice system, with Black communities experiencing over-policing, racial profiling and higher rates of stop-and-search (Gilroy, 1982).

In response to rising tensions within UK society, civil disturbances such as the 1958 Notting Hill and 1981 Brixton riots took place in protest of racial mistreatment (Kurttila, 2014). The UK's first legislation to directly address racial discrimination was the Race Relations Act (1965), making it unlawful to discriminate on the grounds of

colour, race, or ethnic or national origins in public places. Amendments to the Race Relations Act in 1968 and 1976 extended the legislation to cover employment, housing and public services, as well as direct and indirect discrimination. The Macpherson Report (1999) was published following the racially motivated murder of Stephen Lawrence, a young Black male, concluding that the Metropolitan Police Service was institutionally racist and called for reforms across public services, including education, healthcare and law enforcement. However, despite protests, legislation and reports, structural racism has remained (Goodfellow & McFarlane, 2018). More recently, the Commission on Race and Ethnic Disparities Report (Sewell et al., 2021) faced criticism for downplaying institutional racism in the UK.

Current data reveal the racial disparities faced across multiple areas of life. Black Caribbean pupils experience permanent exclusion at a rate of 0.18%, which is approximately 1.5 times higher than the national average (0.11%), while Black African pupils face a permanent exclusion rate of 0.06%, which is lower than the national average but remains disproportionate compared to several other ethnic groups (Department for Education, 2024). Economic disparities are similarly stark, with Black people more likely to be unemployed compared to White people and paid less per hour on average for the same roles (Adams et al., 2018; Office for National Statistics, ONS 2022a). Black people are found to have lower financial income, savings, and assets than White British people (Khan, 2020). This inequality also extends into housing, with Black families being more likely to live in overcrowded and poor-quality housing (Department for Communities and Local Government, 2017).

Regarding health, 60% of Black people reported not believing that their health was as equally protected by the NHS compared to White people (UK Parliament, 2020). Research shows that Black people are more likely to experience poorer health outcomes, including higher rates of hypertension, diabetes, and maternal deaths, and lower life expectancy compared to White people (The Kings Fund, 2021). The COVID-19 pandemic brought these inequalities to the forefront, with Black and ethnic minorities being disproportionately affected by rates of infection and deaths (ONS, 2020).

In the criminal justice system, Black people make up 12% of the prison population, despite only accounting for 4% of the general population (House of Commons,

2024b; ONS, 2022b). A significant proportion of Black individuals are subject to police racial profiling and discrimination; The Lammy Review (2017) highlighted that compared to 35% of White people, 51% of ethnic minorities reported believing that the criminal justice system is racially discriminatory. Additionally, one report found that 75% of Black people do not believe that their human rights are equally protected compared to White people (Joint Committee on Human Rights, 2020). These persistent disparities highlight how historical and institutional racism continue to shape the lived experiences of Black communities in the UK, reinforcing cycles of disadvantage across generations.

1.3.2. Mental Health Disparities

The impact of systemic inequalities on Black mental health manifests in concerning patterns of diagnosis and treatment. Black communities are disproportionately affected by mental health difficulties (Fernando, 2017). In relation to diagnostic disparities, one study found that the prevalence of psychosis per 1,000 in the White population was 4.4 and for Black populations was 14.2 (Qassem et al., 2015). Rates of depression are also reportedly higher in Black and other minority ethnic groups (Race Equality Foundation, 2018). This is despite lower rates of diagnoses for other common mental health difficulties, such as personality disorder and obsessive-compulsive disorder (Race Equality Foundation, 2018). These statistics raise concerns relating to misdiagnosis, over-pathologisation, and the cultural appropriateness of Western diagnostic frameworks. Research indicates that clinicians may misinterpret culturally specific expressions of distress such as religious or spiritual beliefs, as symptoms of serious mental illness (Neighbors et al., 2003). Normal responses to systemic racism and discrimination, including hypervigilance or mistrust of systems can be inappropriately pathologized as paranoia (Metzl, 2010; Suite et al., 2007). Furthermore, the cultural appropriateness of standard diagnostic frameworks has been criticised, given their development and research primarily based on White, Western populations (Kleinman, 2004).

Racism has been identified as another factor explaining mental health disparities among Black communities, with research demonstrating that racism, chronic discrimination and systemic inequalities are determinants of poorer mental health outcomes and psychological wellbeing (Williams & Mohammed, 2013; Paradies et

al., 2015). Some studies on ethnic density, the proportion of people from the same ethnic group within a community, suggest that higher ethnic density can provide a protective effect by fostering social support, cultural affirmation, and resilience, potentially mitigating some mental health risks associated with racism (Halpern & Nazroo, 2000). For instance, being Black in an area where Black individuals constitute a smaller proportion of the population has been associated with higher odds of psychotic experiences (Schofield et al., 2016). However, the protective effect of ethnic density is not uniform across all groups. Other research indicates that Black Caribbean individuals do not experience the same mental health benefits from living in higher ethnic density areas, which may be related to experiences of poverty and unemployment within these communities (Bécares et al., 2012; Shankley & Laurence, 2022).

1.3.3. Black Men's Mental Health

Black men face a unique challenge at the intersection of gender and racial disparities in mental health. Male gender is known to be a determinant of mental health outcomes, with studies highlighting significant gender differences in mental health and mortality rates. In England, the suicide rate among men is three times higher than that of women (House of Commons, 2024a). While men are less frequently diagnosed with depression and anxiety disorders, they are more likely to experience substance misuse, alcohol-related problems, anger, aggression, and risk-taking behaviours (Liddon et al., 2017). Men are also less likely than women to access psychological therapies, with one report showing only 36% of male referrals to NHS talking therapies (NHS Digital, 2020). These disparities have been explained by research suggesting that men experience distress more inwardly than women, which influences diagnostic differences and how men access support (Wilkins, 2010; Wong et al., 2017).

Mental health disparities are exacerbated by experiences relating to race. Between 2007 and 2014, it was found that the risk of Black men diagnosed with psychosis was significantly higher at 3.2%, than that of White men at 0.3% (McManus et al., 2016). Black men are also disproportionately likely to die in circumstances involving restraint, often during mental health crises, and to receive inadequate mental health care during police interactions (Angiolini, 2017). In the criminal justice system, Black

men are over-represented in youth and adult prisons, accounting for four times their proportion in the general population (House of Commons, 2024b). They are also 9.7 times more likely to be stopped and searched by the police, and 1.5 times more likely to be imprisoned compared to White men (Home Office, 2019; Revolving Doors, 2020).

Beyond gender, culture and race-related factors, it is crucial to adopt an intersectional lens that acknowledges the complexity of individual identities. The term 'intersectionality' provides a framework for understanding how multiple social identities (e.g., class, sexuality, disability, age, religion) intersect to create individual experiences of oppression and privilege (Crenshaw, 1989). Research has found that Black LGBTQ+ men face unique challenges in accessing mental health support, often navigating both racial discrimination in LGBTQ+ spaces and homophobia within Black communities (Moore et al., 2020). Studies have also shown that socioeconomic status significantly impacts mental health outcomes, with working-class Black men facing additional barriers to accessing care (Williams et al., 2010).

Despite these elevated risks, Black men are less likely to seek support from voluntary mental health services, with evidence indicating lower engagement rates in both primary and secondary care (McKeown et al., 2008). Evidence suggests that there is a decreased likelihood of Black men seeking mental health support at the early stages of experiencing mental health difficulties (Darko, 2021). Consequently, services intervene at the more acute stages of mental health, for example, through involuntary inpatient admissions or the police which can be traumatic, therefore influencing how Black men experience mental health care (Stockwell et al., 2024).

1.3.4. Models of Help-Seeking

The underrepresentation of Black men in preventative and early-intervention mental health services can be understood through theoretical models of help-seeking. Help-seeking can be defined as the process of seeking support from formal (e.g., mental health services) or informal (e.g., family, friends, communities) sources when experiencing mental health challenges (Doll et al., 2021). Several theoretical models have been developed to explain help-seeking behaviours, including the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 2020), the Health Belief Model (Rosenstock et al., 1974),

and the Common-Sense Model of Self-Regulation (Leventhal, Phillips, & Burns, 2016). These models largely focus on how individual attitudes, perceptions, emotions, and appraisals impact help-seeking, therefore overlooking wider social contexts and structural barriers to accessing mental health care.

The Integrated Behavioural Model of Mental Health Help Seeking (IBM-HS, Hammer et al., 2024) was recently developed to address these limitations by integrating individual, structural, and cultural influences on help-seeking behaviours. The IBM-HS (Hammer et al., 2024) conceptualises help-seeking as a dynamic process involving determinants, beliefs, and mechanisms that collectively influence help-seeking intention and behaviour (see Appendix A for diagram). Determinants refer to broad factors that shape how individuals perceive and respond to mental health challenges. These include structural forces such as racism, classism, and access to resources, as well as cultural influences, past help-seeking experiences, perceived urgency or severity of mental health issues, mental health awareness, skills, social support, and environmental constraints like cost, availability of services, and language barriers.

Beliefs arise from these determinants and reflect specific thoughts, expectations, and emotional reactions related to help-seeking. They include perceptions about outcomes, anticipated social responses, and practical concerns related to accessing support. Mechanisms function as the drivers that translate these beliefs into intentions to seek help. The IBM-HS identifies three primary mechanisms: attitude (overall positive or negative evaluation of help-seeking), perceived norm (social pressure or approval related to help-seeking), and personal agency (confidence in one's ability to successfully seek help).

The interaction of these components shapes an individual's intention to seek help, which is influenced by how positively they evaluate help-seeking, the degree of social support or pressure they perceive, and their sense of personal control or efficacy. While intention is a key predictor of behaviour, the model acknowledges that structural and cultural barriers can inhibit action even when intentions are strong. This approach therefore provides a more nuanced understanding of help-seeking by recognising how individual motivations are shaped by broader social and cultural contexts, particularly for marginalised individuals.

In the context of Black men's mental health and help-seeking, the IBM-HS helps to explain how structural inequalities and other social factors can shape beliefs and intentions around access to care and the underutilisation of mental health support (see Appendix B for examples).

1.3.5. Barriers to Help-Seeking

In addition to theoretical models, research suggests different explanations for the underutilisation of voluntary mental health services, demonstrating how systemic inequalities, cultural factors, and gender-related barriers impact Black men's engagement with mental health care.

1.3.5.1. *History and current context of the NHS*

The relationship between the NHS and Black communities can be understood within the context of colonialism and institutional racism. The field of psychiatry has played a role in perpetuating racial oppression, particularly through the pathologisation of Black resistance to oppression and the misuse of psychiatric diagnoses to control Black individuals (Fernando, 2017). Historical examples include 'drapetomania', a mental illness that was diagnosed in enslaved people who attempted to escape, highlighting how psychiatric frameworks have been weaponised against Black communities (Metzl, 2010). In current practice, the disproportionate rates of Black individuals detained under the Mental Health Act (2018) highlights how systemic racism continues to manifest in mental health care through coercive practices and restricted autonomy.

The NHS was established in 1948 during a period of post-war migration from former British colonies, with the institution's development shaped by colonial perspectives and power dynamics (Kline, 2014). It can be argued that these historical foundations influence current service provision, where talking therapies services predominantly offer cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT), a modality criticised for its Westernised, individualistic approach that often fails to acknowledge systemic oppression and cultural contexts (Wood & Patel, 2017). The standardised and manual-based nature of CBT, although shown to have effective outcomes in studies and efficient for service delivery, has been criticised for lacking generalisability due to many studies using majority White European and American samples or failing to report race (De

Jesús-Romero et al., 2024; Stewart & Chambless, 2009). The lack of cultural representation within mental health professions exacerbates these issues. Recent data indicate that clinical psychology remains overwhelmingly White, with only 9.6% of clinical psychologists in England and Wales identifying as from an ethnic minority background (Clearing House for Postgraduate Courses in Clinical Psychology, 2023). This extends to other mental health professions, creating a significant cultural gap between service providers and Black service users (Kline, 2014).

This context can influence help-seeking and engagement with services. One recent review by the NHS Race and Health Observatory found that young Black men were deterred from seeking help due to their awareness of historical and ongoing injustices in mental health services (Kapadia et al., 2022).

1.3.5.2. Racism, stereotyping, and stigma

Experiences of racism, stereotyping, and stigma also create barriers for Black men's access to mental health care. In society, Black men are often depicted in stereotypes relating to danger, criminality, and deviance (Curry, 2018). These harmful stereotypes are deeply embedded in, and are perpetuated by media representation, political discourse, and institutional racism. They also manifest in their treatment within different systems such as criminal justice and mental health care. Research indicates that healthcare professionals' implicit biases can lead to differential treatment and diagnosis patterns, such as the higher rates in diagnosing psychosis (Hall et al., 2015). This has been shown to fuel mistrust towards mental health services, discourage engagement, and contribute to stigma (Keating et al., 2002).

The Breaking the Circles of Fear report (Keating et al., 2002) draws attention to how these societal perceptions exacerbate disengagement, with Black men being reluctant to seek help from services they perceive as discriminatory. Other barriers to accessing appropriate care were highlighted in this report, including experiences of fear, stigma, and culturally insensitive, inhumane, and unhelpful mental health care (Keating et al., 2002). Similar findings are demonstrated in more recent studies, with Black men naming mental health services as unkind, discriminatory, stigmatising, culturally naïve, and insensitive (Earl et al., 2011; Meechan, 2021; Memon et al., 2016). Furthermore, Black men have described feeling that professionals will not

understand informal and culturally relevant language used to talk about distress (Watkins & Neighbors, 2007). This suggests a failure to address long-standing issues and raises questions about the effectiveness of governmental and institutional efforts to promote culturally competent care.

1.3.5.3. *Cultural factors*

Cultural factors significantly influence how mental health is conceptualised, experienced, and addressed within Black communities. While recognising the heterogeneity of Black communities, research has identified several cultural patterns that can impact help-seeking behaviours. Within many Black communities, there is a strong emphasis on resilience, perseverance, and showing strength (Mattis et al., 2016). Although this can be protective in some contexts, it is also shown to create barriers to acknowledging and seeking help for emotional distress, as mental health can be perceived as a sign of weakness or moral failing (Mantovani et al., 2016).

Collectivist culture refers to a culture or society where the needs of the group are prioritised over the individual. This contrasts with the individualist nature of Western societies, which emphasises personal goals and independence, over and above groups or communities. Research suggests that historically, cultures originating from Africa have tended to be more collectivist, with a strong emphasis on seeking guidance and support from within the community (Graves, 2021). This creates both opportunities and challenges for Black individuals seeking mental health support. Studies have shown that cultural norms within Black communities, such as personal and family pride, led to individuals relying on informal support systems such as family, friends, and religious communities, who are viewed as more trustworthy and culturally aligned (Mantovani et al., 2016; Watkins & Neighbors, 2007). However, informal support within Black communities can also be hindered by constructs of mental health as being socially unacceptable (Meechan, 2021). Furthermore, it can create barriers to seeking professional support outside of the community (Graves, 2021). This preference may stem from cultural values and be a response to historical medical abuses and mental health discrimination.

Religion and spirituality also play a role in mental health help-seeking. One study found that within African-descended faith communities in the UK, mental health

problems were interpreted through religious interpretations, including concepts of spiritual warfare and demonic possession (Mantovani et al., 2016). While these beliefs can provide meaning and ways of coping, it has been found that they also contribute to fears of rejection, internalised stigma, and discrimination (Mantovani et al., 2016). However, it is important to avoid pathologising religious narratives, as they can represent historically adaptive responses to systemic oppression and provide valuable community support systems (Eyerman, 2001).

The failure of mental health services to effectively engage with different cultural ideas in developing culturally relevant care represents a systemic failure. The dominant individualistic, Westernised approach to mental health care often conflicts with collectivist cultural values and fails to recognise the potential therapeutic value of community and spiritual resources (Fernando, 2014). Furthermore, the reliance on informal support networks can place unsustainable burdens on communities already facing multiple systemic challenges (Edge & MacKian, 2010).

1.3.5.4. Gender and masculinity

The intersection of gender norms, racial identity, and cultural identity creates unique challenges for Black men's mental health help-seeking behaviours. There are several key constructs of masculinity that can influence this.

'Hegemonic masculinity' refers to the dominant form of masculinity that maintains men's social power (Connell, 1995). This concept typically embodies White, middle-class, heterosexual male characteristics and behaviours such as self-reliance, stoicism, strength, dominance, and autonomy, with emotional vulnerability constructed as a sign of weakness (Johnson et al., 2011). These norms shape how men are socialised and have been shown to lead to the internalisation of distress, therefore discouraging help-seeking and impacting engagement in mental health services (Wilkins, 2010; Wong et al., 2017). For Black men, this creates a challenge where they must navigate societal pressure to conform to hegemonic masculine ideals, while simultaneously being systematically excluded from achieving them due to racial oppression (hooks, 2004; Mincey et al., 2014; White & Cones, 1999).

'Toxic masculinity' describes rigid adherence to traditional masculine norms that can be harmful to mental health, including the suppression of emotions, endorsement of

violence, and rejection of help-seeking behaviours (Kupers, 2005). Research indicates that adherence to toxic masculine norms is associated with increased depression, anxiety, and substance abuse among Black men (Hammond, 2012).

'Black masculinity' represents a complex negotiation between hegemonic masculine ideals and Black cultural values (Curry, 2017; hooks, 2004). This includes alternative constructions of manhood that emphasise community responsibility, spiritual leadership and cultural resistance. However, these positive aspects often conflict with societal stereotypes that hypersexualise and criminalise Black masculinity (Cooper, 2005). Studies in the US have shown that Black masculinity is negatively associated with help-seeking, predicting greater public and self-stigma, and less positive help-seeking attitudes (Coleman-Kirumba et al., 2023; Johnson, 2018)

It has been suggested in the media that younger generations of men may be developing more flexible approaches to masculinity (The Times, 2024), which could allow for greater emotional expression and help-seeking behaviours. However, for Black men, these shifts occur within a context of persistent structural barriers and systemic racism that impacts experiences of mental health care.

1.3.6. Government Responses to Mental Health Inequalities

The issues discussed have been raised by the UK government as a problem for decades, however, preventative care remains an ongoing health inequality for Black men (Department of Health, 1998; NHS, 2019). While different explanations for these inequalities have been presented, it is argued that disproportionality within mental health is most likely explained by racism and discrimination (Synergi Collaborative, 2017), and it is well documented that systemic inequalities impact mental health (Centre for Mental Health, 2020).

The Black Mental Health and Wellbeing Alliance (2024) called on the UK government to address the significant disparities for Black individuals in financial income, housing, unemployment, incarceration, and school exclusions. Policy developments such as The NHS Race and Health Observatory (2020) and the NHS Patient and Carer Race Equality Framework (2021) were established with the aim of tackling ethnic inequalities in healthcare and developing anti-racist mental health

services. The NHS Long Term Plan (2019) also made a commitment to reduce health inequalities for Black and other ethnic minorities.

While these initiatives represent important steps toward addressing systemic racism, their implementation has been criticised for being slow, and there is limited evidence of sustained, meaningful impact. Policies have faced challenges such as underfunding, lack of coordination, or insufficient engagement with Black communities, leading to criticisms that these efforts reflect tokenistic rather than meaningful changes. Additionally, the absence of robust monitoring mechanisms makes it difficult to analyse progress and hold organisations accountable. This highlights the need for more effective measures and preventative changes to address discriminatory systemic practices affecting Black men's mental health.

1.3.7. Community Initiatives

There is a need for a shift in how mental health services support Black communities. Services should adopt strength-based approaches which recognise and build upon existing community resources (Centre for Mental Health, 2022). Meaningful change must also actively address the systemic inequalities impacting mental health and appropriate care. One example of positive change is demonstrated in the Shifting the Dial report (Centre for Mental Health, 2022). The report details outcomes from a three-year Birmingham-based programme supporting the mental health of young Black men aged 16-25.

In this programme, four culturally relevant initiatives were implemented to engage the young Black men (Centre for Mental Health, 2022). The Dear Youngers project provided psychological support through group sessions, mentoring, outreach, forums, and skill development, prioritising culturally familiar practices such as intergenerational dialogue (bringing different generations together to facilitate understanding and address issues) and spirituality (prayer and spiritual reflection). The Lightpost Theatre Company used creative performance to help young Black men explore issues such as racism, identity, masculinity, and belonging. The Light Bearers Project trained men as mentors and facilitators of drama workshops within schools while developing digital content to showcase their creative work. The Fix It Events brought together the young men, stakeholders, and policymakers to share

insights, problem-solve issues affecting Black men and promote systemic change. The events focused on themes including education, employment, youth violence, COVID-19, and the Black Lives Matter movement. Outcomes demonstrated improvements in participants' confidence, self-awareness, mental health literacy, and a sense of belonging.

The Shifting the Dial report (Centre for Mental Health, 2022) emphasised that effective mental health care requires a shift from crisis-driven responses, advocating for sustained partnerships with Black-led organisations and communities that involve genuine power-sharing rather than superficial involvement. These initiatives challenged traditional models of mental health support by demonstrating the usefulness of culturally relevant and creative interventions to support Black men in ways that mainstream services have failed to do. This example of positive change therefore shows the value of adopting mental health approaches that foster creativity, and a sense of empowerment and community.

Other culturally relevant approaches utilising creativity will be explored in the following section, which explores how hip-hop culture and rap can be powerful tools for facilitating mental health engagement for Black men.

1.4. The Role of Hip-Hop Culture and Rap in Mental Health: Origins, Interventions and Relevance to Black Men

Due to systemic, social, and cultural barriers, there is a need for mental health interventions tailored to Black men. Rooted in hip-hop and Black culture, rap serves as a powerful medium of self-expression. This section outlines its origins, cultural significance, and relevance to mental health and adapted interventions.

1.4.1. Hip-Hop Origins

Hip-hop is a cultural movement that has been characterised as having five key elements: DJing (creating music beats), breaking (also known as breakdancing), graffiti (visual art, often created in public spaces without authorisation), rapping (or MCing, the delivery of messages through words), and knowledge (self-awareness rooted in hip-hop's values of self-determination, resistance, and freedom; Love, 2016; Wells, 2019). Hip-hop is rooted in Black cultural traditions, drawing influence

from the storytelling of West African griots in the 13th century and Jamaican toasting in the 1950s (Wells, 2019). The musical genre's vocal style also draws from African American oral traditions including blues, jazz scat singing, street corner "playing the dozens", prison work songs, and civil rights protest songs (Rose, 1994).

Hip-hop emerged in popularity in the Bronx, New York, following the American civil rights movement in the 1970s. This time was characterised by rising racial tensions, economic collapse and deindustrialisation, all of which impacted the educational, economic, and social opportunities for Black people (Chang, 2005; Dimitriadis, 2001; Lipstiz, 1994). The systemic disinvestment in urban communities, termed 'planned shrinkage', particularly affected Black and Latino neighbourhoods (Wallace, 1985), and hip-hop became a way for Black communities to express their struggles and hopes in the face of adversity (Kubrin, 2007; Wells, 2019).

1.4.2. Rap: A Global Voice for Self-Expression

Since the 1970s, hip-hop culture has gained worldwide popularity. On Spotify, a popular music streaming platform, nearly one quarter of international streams are of hip-hop artists (Spotify, 2023). Its popularity within Black communities is supported by a public opinion survey conducted in 2018, showing that 67% of Black people reported hip-hop and rap music as the musical genres that best represent the US (Leu, 2024). Within a UK context, it was reported that hip-hop and rap accounted for 22% of single-track consumption, making it the second most consumed genre after pop music (Musicians' Union, 2020).

Rap music is a central part of hip-hop's global influence; it is a form of storytelling which uses rhyme, rhythmic speech and form, and informal language, often performed over a musical beat (Forman & Neal, 2012). The content of rap lyrics often reflects personal and collective experiences; for example, early American hip-hop pioneers such as Public Enemy, N.W.A and KRS-One popularised political and socially conscious rap, while more recent rappers Kendrick Lamar and J. Cole rap about race, mental health, and social injustice (Bradley, 2017). One study exploring common themes in hip-hop songs identified topics relating to social, economic and racial oppression, personal suffering, empowerment, praise of family values, work, achievement and women, educational importance, spirituality, love, loyalty, empathy, materialism, and substance misuse (Tyson et al., 2013). This demonstrates how rap

has become a tool for self-expression, enabling experiences to be shared across the world.

Hip-hop has influenced cultures beyond America. In the UK, different subgenres provide lyrical portrayals of the sociopolitical experiences of Black communities. UK Garage emerged in the 1990s as an underground dance music movement, with groups such as the So Solid Crew documenting the realities of inner-city London life (Bradley, 2013). This influenced the development of Grime music, which originated in East London council estates in the early 2000s. This subgenre, characterised by quick-fire delivery over electronic beats was popularised by artists such as Dizzee Rascal, Wiley, and Skepta, who rap about challenges faced by working-class Black and mixed-race young people, including austerity, housing inequality, and systemic racism (Hancox, 2013).

UK Drill, which evolved from its roots in Chicago Drill, emerged in South London around 2010. Artists including Headie One, Unknown T and 67 are known for rapping over gritty minimalistic beats with lyrics that reflect the harsh realities of inner-city life relating to violence, gang culture, and systemic neglect. Although controversial, drill has been recognised as an important way for marginalised voices to document their lived experiences (Fatsis, 2019). Beyond these subcultures, UK rap has also developed its own identity; rapper Stormzy raps about faith, mental health, and systemic racism and has become a British cultural icon and activist. Rapper and author Akala has used rap and written publications to critique colonial history and promote education about Black history.

Despite its international success, the corporatisation of rap music has increasingly moved towards lyrical messages focused on materialism and individualism, contrasting with hip-hop's origins and values of resistance and protest (George, 2005). Hip-hop has also received negative criticism within the media for being a genre that glorifies misogyny, violence, drug use, and homophobia. One study focusing on the lyrical references found in gangsta rap, a subgenre of rap, identified themes of respect, willingness to fight or use violence, material wealth, violent retaliation, objectification of women, and nihilism (Kubrin, 2006). Some argue that this promotes violence and contributes to racism due to negative perceptions and stereotypes that this music can perpetuate (e.g., stereotypes of Black men relating to

criminality, violence, hypersexuality). However, others state that the lyrics reflect a depiction of the difficult realities for many Black individuals and communities (Richardson & Scott, 2002).

1.4.3. Rap and Mental Health

Rap music can be a powerful tool for facilitating and highlighting social change, particularly within Black communities, where systemic and cultural barriers impede access to mental health support. It has been argued that rap provides a culturally relevant and non-stigmatising means for mental health expression and care (Elligan, 2000).

The lyrical self-expression in rap music has contributed to more open conversations about mental health difficulties, with influential artists rapping about their personal struggles (Sule & Inkster, 2020). This shift is evidenced in research demonstrating that references to mental health in rap have increased over time. One study analysed 125 popular American songs between 1998 and 2018 and found statistically significant increases in references to suicide, depression, and metaphors indicating mental health challenges (Kresovich et al., 2020). Another study observed an increased shift towards promoting more positive mental health discussions; gangsta rap in the 1990s was argued to perpetuate toxic masculinity which avoids emotional vulnerability, while recent rap is reported to more openly reflect on emotional distress (Hart, 2019). These changes may reflect broader cultural shifts with regards to how mental health is understood and talked about.

Research has also shown that hip-hop artists play a role in encouraging mental health discussions among Black men. Francis (2021) examined Twitter (now X) conversations following rapper Kid Cudi's depression disclosure, highlighting how his openness helped Black men engage in online discussions about mental health. Similarly, Francis (2018) found that Black men sought information about depression after Kid Cudi's disclosure, indicating that rap artists can influence help-seeking behaviours and public discourse around mental health.

1.4.4. Psychological and Physiological Effects of Music

Beyond its cultural and social resonance, music has powerful psychological and physiological effects that can help to explain its value for mental health. Music engages multiple brain regions and networks that influence emotional, cognitive and social functioning (Zaatar et al., 2024). For instance, research has shown that music activates neural circuits involved in emotion regulation, reward and memory, stimulating the release of neurochemicals such as dopamine, oxytocin and endorphins, which enhance mood, reduce stress and pain, and improve social bonding (Chanda & Levitin, 2013; Levitin, 2006; Koelsch, 2014; Salimpoor et al., 2011). Studies also show that imagining music activates similar neural circuits, particularly in the right hemisphere, which plays a key role in emotional processing and creativity (Blood et al., 1999).

Music produces measurable physiological changes through the autonomic nervous system, affecting heart rate, breathing, blood pressure, muscle tension, body temperature and skin conductance, a marker of emotional arousal related to sweating (Bernardi et al., 2006; Salimpoor et al., 2011). Music perceived as highly pleasurable has been shown to elicit “chills”, which indicate intense emotional and bodily responses (Panksepp & Bernatzky, 2002). Active engagement in music, such as performance and composition, can induce long-term neuroplastic changes and improvements in cognitive, emotional and motor functioning (Gaser & Schlaug, 2003; Zatorre, 2005). These findings demonstrate that music can be a powerful cultural, psychological and physiological tool that can influence emotional wellbeing.

1.4.5. Rap-Based Mental Health Interventions

There is a growing recognition and endorsement of expressive arts therapies, including music, dance, art, drama, and media, as valuable tools for treating mental health difficulties (Fancourt & Finn, 2019; Smriti et al., 2022). While there is no formally agreed upon framework for integrating hip-hop and rap into therapy (Levy, 2020), several models have been developed in the US and have demonstrated positive outcomes.

Rap Therapy (Elligan, 2000) aims to facilitate the exploration of emotions, self-expression, and coping strategies through rap. The therapy model involves

assessing the influence of rap in relation to self-identity, role play with clients creating their own lyrics, and maintenance work on behavioural and emotional difficulties. Hip-Hop Therapy (Tyson, 2002) involves using lyrical interpretation to connect with the clients' experiences. Hip-Hop and Spoken Word Therapy (Levy, 2012) uses established therapeutic interventions with creative processes like writing and recording hip-hop music to explore emotional and cognitive experiences. It is argued that these approaches are rooted in the idea that hip-hop and rap reflects the lived experiences of marginalised groups, therefore improving the cultural accessibility of the interventions (Kobin & Tyson, 2006).

Central to these interventions are several overlapping therapeutic frameworks and theories. CBT is a structured, time-limited psychological approach that focuses on the interplay between thoughts, emotions and behaviours, aiming to identify and change unhelpful cognitive patterns (Beck, 1976). In rap-based interventions, the processes of writing, analysing, and performing lyrics provide opportunities for cognitive restructuring, enabling clients to externalise distressing experiences, challenge maladaptive beliefs and rehearse adaptive coping strategies through rap. Social learning theory (SLT, Bandura, 1977) posits that people learn new behaviours, emotional reactions, and attitudes by observing others through modelling, imitation, and reinforcement. Collaborative lyric-writing and performance allow participants to model emotional expression and positive coping strategies, providing vicarious learning experiences that promotes emotional change.

Cultural and liberation psychology (Comas-Díaz, 2007; Martín-Baró, 1994) argue that mental health must be understood within sociopolitical and historical contexts, addressing not only individual distress but also systemic oppression and marginalisation. Given hip-hop's roots in social critique and resistance, rap-based interventions provide a culturally responsive space for individuals to connect their personal experiences to broader histories of injustice, fostering individual healing and collective empowerment (Levy, 2020).

Although structured interventions such as Rap Therapy, Hip-Hop Therapy and Hip-Hop and Spoken Word Therapy (Elligan, 2000; Levy, 2012; Tyson, 2002), are underpinned by psychological models, much of the emerging research also

examines broader rap-based interventions, some of which do not integrate theoretical frameworks or psychological models into their design or delivery.

Research examining the effectiveness of rap-based interventions suggests positive outcomes. A recent systematic review of hip-hop and rap mental health interventions in counselling settings between 2010 and 2022 analysed ten peer-reviewed studies, focused on adolescent and prison populations across the US, Netherlands, and Australia (Jefferson et al., 2025). The interventions addressed emotional expression and exploration, with reported benefits including reduced stress, anxiety, and depression, improved confidence and self-awareness, enhanced relationship building, and stronger self-image. Additional studies in prison settings have documented improvements in feelings of hope, emotional connection, and self-esteem (Baker & Homan, 2007; Edri & Benisimon, 2018; Tuastad & O'Grady, 2013).

In the UK, music interventions are increasingly adopted by community and prison-based organisations, particularly for individuals who struggle to engage with traditional mental health services (Millar et al., 2020). One community music project in Brighton demonstrated how rap-based interventions fostered emotional development and self-achievement among young people living in council estates, enabling them to become active participants in community development despite facing marginalisation (Dickens & Lonie, 2012). Similarly, a prison-based rap group focusing on developing improvised lyrics found positive outcomes for emotion management among young male prisoners (Short, 2014). These findings highlight rap music's potential as a valuable therapeutic tool for addressing mental health challenges among marginalised populations.

1.5. Scoping Review

The narrative review outlines the mental health inequalities faced by Black men, and the systemic, racial, cultural, and gendered barriers to mental health care and help-seeking. Creative, strengths-based approaches are needed to address these challenges. While other musical genres have historical significance to Black communities, rap was chosen due to its contemporary and widespread cultural significance, and its roots in articulating lived experiences such as mental health. Rap-based interventions have shown effective mental health outcomes, however,

there remains uncertainty about the scope and quality of existing research in this area for Black men. Therefore, to comprehensively map and synthesise existing literature on this topic, a scoping review was conducted in line with guidance from Peters et al. (2020). The review protocol, including search strategy and eligibility processes, was established prior to data collection. This approach enabled the systematic identification and mapping of existing literature to inform the current study's aims and research questions.

Relevant literature was identified through searches of PSYCHINFO, Academic Search Ultimate, CINHALL complete, Google Scholar, and Research Gate. These databases were selected to ensure comprehensive coverage of psychological, health, social science, and related interdisciplinary research relevant to rap music and mental health. Grey literature was also included to capture other forms of research, for example, those conducted through reports and theses, which may not be available through traditional academic publishing.

The following broad search terms were applied when searching the databases to generate as many relevant outcomes as possible: (Black OR African American OR African Caribbean OR Afro Caribbean) AND (Man OR Men OR Male OR Males) AND (Rap OR Hip-hop) AND (Mental health OR Wellbeing OR Trauma OR Adversity OR Racism OR Inequality OR Expression OR Masculinity OR Vulnerability OR Stigma OR Disadvantage OR Struggle).

The review included empirical and observational studies. Empirical research involves the systematic collection and analysis of data to investigate research questions or hypotheses. Observational research involves observing variables or participants without manipulating the environment. Articles were chosen for the review if they related to Black men, rap music and mental health, and were available in English. There was no restriction placed on type of methodology or date of publication.

Conceptual articles, including theoretical papers and critical commentaries, were excluded from the review as the aim was to examine outcomes rather than theoretical frameworks.

In total, 160 publications were generated through the searches. Duplicate records were identified and removed. The remaining titles and abstracts were screened for

relevance based on the inclusion criteria, resulting in the exclusion of studies that were unrelated to the topic, focused on the wrong population, were not in English, and were not empirical or observational. Publications that potentially met the criteria were retrieved in full for further assessment. At the full-text screening stage, additional exclusions were made due to lack of relevance, duplication, and conceptual focus. In addition to database searches, citation tracking of included studies was performed to identify any additional relevant articles. Two further articles were identified through reviewing the reference lists and related chapters of included studies and were subsequently assessed for eligibility using the same criteria. After this process, a total of six papers were included in the scoping review (see PRISMA-ScR flow diagram in Appendix C).

1.5.1. Scoping Review Findings

The scoping review synthesises findings from six studies. Due to the small number of studies identified, each study will be summarised and critically evaluated, before a synthesised description is provided.

1.5.1.1. *Ierardi and Jenkins (2011)*

Ierardi and Jenkins (2011) discuss the delivery of a music therapy programme within a short-term juvenile detention facility in the US. Residents, aged 10-21, were predominantly from African American backgrounds and faced socio-economic disadvantage and mental health difficulties. The music therapy used African drumming, blues and rap improvisation, and composition. Weekly group and individual sessions were facilitated by a music therapist and students.

The authors reported that although initial resistance and guardedness were common among group participants, trust and engagement increased over time. Group sessions often featured improvised drumming and collaborative rap, providing opportunities for musical leadership, mutual support, and creative risk-taking. Young people were reportedly able to articulate their identities, express complex emotions, and imagine more positive futures. Individual case examples were described to further illustrate outcomes from the music therapy programme. For instance, “Kevin” (pseudonym), a 17-year-old male, used rap composition to express themes of hopelessness, frustration, and family separation. His involvement in the creative

process also resulted in a sense of accomplishment, pride, improved planning, and problem-solving skills. This suggests that rap-based interventions can provide therapeutic benefits for Black men when delivered in secure settings.

However, several methodological limitations must be considered. The study is an observational account of a music therapy programme, the authors do not state the number of group attendees and there are no systematic outcome measures. Therefore, there is a lack of methodological rigour, which limits the ability to quantify therapeutic impact. The absence of structured pre and post intervention outcomes also makes it difficult to determine whether observed changes were directly attributable to the therapy or other contextual factors. The short-term nature of the detention facility also impacts the longitudinal exploration of rap therapy's long-term effects. Institutional restrictions on lyrical content may have limited participants' ability to fully articulate their experiences, potentially influencing the authenticity of their self-expression. Additionally, the setting limits the generalisability of the findings to non-institutional populations, especially those in the UK, and may not represent the experiences of Black men who are not in contact with the justice system.

1.5.1.2. Alvarez (2011)

Alvarez (2011) shares their work on the development of Beats, Rhymes, and Life (BRL), a programme based on Rap Therapy (Elligan, 2000), designed as a culturally responsive intervention for young people of colour living in urban neighbourhoods in California, US. The programme was established to address mental health disparities, trauma, and social disadvantage faced by Black and Latino youth, particularly young men. The BRL programme used rap composition, lyrical analysis, collaborative songwriting, and freestyle performance within a group therapy format.

Alvarez described observations from delivery of the programme. Participants reported the group as a space where they could articulate shared experiences of adversity, such as bereavement, trauma, and systemic racism, while expressing pride in their community and envisioning hope for the future. Lyrics reflected experiences of loss, violence, and resilience. The act of writing and performing rap was reported to support with emotion regulation, self-understanding, and empowerment, allowing young people to re-author their narratives. Furthermore, the

group setting facilitated teamwork, communication, and conflict resolution skills, and a sense of belonging and mutual encouragement. Participants highlighted how engagement in the programme helped them manage stress, connect with peers, and communicate more effectively, with several describing music and lyric-writing as vital outlets for coping with grief and maintaining psychological wellbeing. These findings indicate that rap-based programmes can have positive personal and social benefits for young Black men.

The evaluation of BRL's effectiveness is limited by methodological constraints. Alvarez's account lacks a defined sample, systematic data collection, and standardised outcome measures and is primarily observational and anecdotal. The absence of longitudinal evaluation limits longer-term understandings about the sustained impact of the programme. Furthermore, the absence of self-reported change and the focus on facilitator reflections raises questions about bias in reporting the outcomes. Additionally, although BRL is based in the community, its US focus and emphasis on young people highlights a gap in understanding how similar approaches might benefit Black men in UK community settings.

1.5.1.3. Jefferson and Ohrt (2024)

Jefferson and Ohrt (2024) investigated the effectiveness of a manualised hip-hop and rap lyric intervention for enhancing wellbeing among Black adult men in the US. The study involved five Black undergraduate men, aged 21–23, who participated in twice-weekly online intervention sessions. The intervention was developed by the lead researcher and is based on the Rap Therapy model (Elligan, 2000). It guided participants through a structured process of reading, analysing, and reflecting on rap lyrics, with sessions focusing on identifying emotions in lyrics, discussing personal relevance, and reframing negative thought patterns.

The study employed a single-case multiple baseline design, introducing the intervention at staggered intervals for each participant to monitor individual changes. This approach enhances internal validity by attributing observed effects to the intervention rather than external factors. Wellbeing was assessed using self-reported measures, including the Outcomes Rating Scale for overall wellbeing and the Satisfaction with Life Scale. The Session Rating Scale was used to assess session engagement. The findings were mixed; only one participant showed a clear

improvement in wellbeing, while others demonstrated minimal or inconsistent effects. Qualitative feedback indicated that participants valued the intervention, suggesting that rap-based approaches may be acceptable and engaging for Black male students in academic settings.

However, the study's reliance on self-reported measures presents limitations, such as the risk of social desirability and inaccurate self-assessment, potentially compromising data validity. The intervention was developed by the lead researcher and lacked prior validation, raising concerns about its efficacy and applicability. Additionally, the small sample size and use of American university students further limits the generalisability of the findings, as the experiences of students may not be representative of Black men with differing educational backgrounds and in other geographical contexts. External confounding variables, such as academic pressures, may have also influenced the outcomes.

1.5.1.4. Adeyola and Allen (2025)

Adeyola and Allen (2025) conducted a qualitative study exploring how hip-hop music facilitates discussions about anger, depression, and identity among Black adult men in the US. Five Black male undergraduate and graduate students, aged 18–24, participated in three face-to-face focus groups. Before each discussion, participants received a curated playlist of hip-hop songs reflecting the topics of anger, depression and identity, as well as broader issues affecting the Black community. Semi-structured and open-ended questions guided the focus group discussions and responses were analysed using qualitative coding.

The findings demonstrated that listening to hip-hop enabled participants to articulate their emotions. In discussions about anger, participants described it as a mask for sadness, a reaction to systemic injustices, and a response to external stressors such as racism and police brutality. Depression-related discussions highlighted experiences of emotional suppression and the reluctance to seek help due to pride and restrictive norms relating to masculinity. Participants discussed the benefit of active solutions, such as music, in overcoming feelings of depression. Additionally, listening to artists who were transparent about their mental health provided validation and representation, and facilitated healthy discussions about mental health and community support. When discussing identity, participants spoke about resisting

negative stereotypes, redefining Black masculinity, and the necessity of positive and progressive role models. The study concluded that listening to hip-hop can be a therapeutic and culturally responsive tool that enables Black men to express emotions and navigate mental health struggles. It also highlights the potential for hip-hop to foster self-expression, promote self-awareness, and solidarity.

However, there were no comparison groups, and the study lacks longitudinal data, making it difficult to assess the long-term impact of listening to hip-hop music on emotional expression. The pre-selected playlists, although thematically relevant, may have introduced biases by influencing participants' interpretations rather than allowing for more organic discussions. The use of focus groups, while valuable for discussing shared themes, may have constrained individual self-disclosure due to social desirability bias or group dynamics. Additionally, the small sample size and focus on young university students and graduates in the US limits the generalisability of the findings to wider Black male populations, particularly those from different socioeconomic backgrounds, age groups, and UK contexts.

1.5.1.5. Compton Dickinson and Souflas (2011)

Situated within the UK context, Compton Dickinson and Souflas (2011) present a case study of "Shadee" (pseudonym), an 18-year-old Black Caribbean man who was admitted to a high-security hospital in the UK following a criminal conviction for actual bodily harm. Shadee exhibited aggressive and sexualised behaviours, reportedly attributed to a history of encephalitis lethargica, a rare neurological condition that affected his cognitive and emotional functioning. Due to his behavioural difficulties, he had been rejected by multiple low-secure units, leading to his placement in high-security care, where he faced racial stereotyping and institutional stigma relating to his behavioural difficulties (for example, being labelled as "bad").

It was reported that during Shadee's four-year stay, music therapy, specifically rap, became a key part of his treatment. He expressed wanting to rap in his initial assessment and subsequently engaged in individual music sessions and a cognitive analytic music therapy group designed for Black patients. It was documented that rap allowed Shadee to self-reflect, explore his identity, express emotions, and process trauma, particularly regarding his absent father and the death of his

grandmother. His ability to tolerate frustration, engage in sessions and social interactions, concentrate, and regulate emotions also improved. His lyrics evolved from themes of grandiosity and fantasy to self-reflective expressions of vulnerability and emotional growth. Following the sessions, Shadee was transferred to a low-secure mental health unit, before being released into the community, where he continued pursuing his interests in rap through rapping and DJed in local clubs, studying music technology, and working in a music studio.

The study demonstrates that rap can be a powerful therapeutic tool for young Black men in forensic settings and highlights systemic issues such as racialised perceptions of dangerousness. However, its single-case, observational design limits generalisability, and researcher subjectivity may have introduced bias in assessing the intervention's impact. While this case provides an example of the positive potential of rap-based interventions for Black men in the UK, it does not address how rap might be used to support mental health outside of crisis or secure inpatient environments.

1.5.1.6. Short (2017)

Short (2017) presents a UK-based case study examining the therapeutic potential of freestyle rap within a community NHS music therapy group in an early intervention in psychosis service. The study discusses "Marcus" (pseudonym), a 35-year-old Black British man of African heritage, who experienced his first episode of psychosis and had a diagnosis of sickle cell anaemia.

A prior pilot project identified rap as the preferred musical genre among many clients referred to the service, particularly those from ethnic minority backgrounds, who are over-represented in psychosis services within the UK. The project highlighted barriers to engagement, including reluctance to participate in mental health support and fears of stigmatisation. The music group was therefore designed as a culturally relevant intervention, aiming to foster supportive relationships between participants and facilitators through a genre with social and historical resonance. The sessions were delivered within a psychodynamic framework.

It was reported that the rap therapy sessions engaged Marcus in freestyle rap, performance of self-written lyrics, and collaborative songwriting with other

participants. Marcus initially utilised the group to articulate experiences of aggression and emotional detachment and as therapy progressed, his lyrics became increasingly self-reflective, addressing personal challenges, relationships, and his experiences of illness. The therapeutic process was analysed through psychoanalytic constructs such as transference, containment, and attachment theory, which highlighted Marcus's interpersonal dynamics and his evolving engagement with the group. The collaborative nature of songwriting fostered Marcus' sense of trust and his ongoing participation in the group was associated with enhanced social interaction and a decreased reliance on drug use.

These findings suggest that community rap interventions delivered within a psychodynamic framework can facilitate psychological and social change for Black men with mental health difficulties. However, the study is limited by its single-case design, lack of long-term follow-up, and questions of cultural positioning, as the therapist, a White middle-class woman, facilitated a predominantly Black male group. Interpretations of therapeutic progress were based primarily on the therapist's observations rather than participant self-report, introducing further potential for bias. Consistent with other research in this area, this study is limited to a clinical sample, which constrains the generalisability of the findings to Black men in non-clinical contexts and their engagement with rap.

1.5.2. Synthesis of Findings and Gaps in the Literature

The studies discussed highlight benefits associated with rap-based interventions. Reported outcomes include increased emotional expression, identity exploration, social connection, self-esteem, and the development of adaptive coping strategies. Participation in rap therapy or creative music-making also fostered engagement and trust, particularly among groups that may otherwise be reluctant to access traditional mental health support.

However, most studies have been conducted in the US, often focusing on incarcerated youth, university students, or individuals engaged in mental health care (Adeyola & Allen, 2025; Alvarez, 2011; Ierardi & Jenkins, 2011; Jefferson & Ohrt, 2024). Studies conducted in the UK are restricted to secure inpatient and clinical settings (Compton Dickinson & Souflas, 2011; Short, 2017). In addition, the studies discussed have significant methodological limitations. Four of the six studies are

primarily observational or anecdotal relying on case studies, therapist observations, and programme descriptions without systematic data collection or standardised outcome measures (Alvarez, 2011; Compton Dickinson & Souflas, 2011; Ierardi & Jenkins, 2011; Short, 2017). Across all studies, sample sizes are small, limiting the generalisability of the findings. There is also a lack of longitudinal follow-up and minimal use of participant self-report or qualitative accounts to assess the sustained impact of rap-based interventions.

1.6. Research Rationale and Clinical Relevance

Despite growing evidence for the potential of rap music to improve the mental health of Black men, significant gaps remain in the literature. There is limited research regarding how Black men in the UK, particularly those not engaged with mental health or forensic services, use rap to support their mental health and wellbeing. This gap is critical, as research shows that Black men are less likely to access voluntary mental health care (Darko, 2021; McKeown et al., 2008; Stockwell et al., 2024). Barriers such as institutional racism and cultural insensitivity in service provision contribute to ongoing mistrust of mental health services (Earl et al., 2011; Meechan, 2021; Memon et al., 2016; Keating et al., 2002). Black men also face unique challenges in help-seeking and discussing mental health difficulties, due to stigma, systemic barriers, and gender and cultural norms (Boydell et al., 2011; Coleman-Kirumba et al., 2023; Johnson 2018; Keating et al., 2002; Mantovani et al., 2016; Mattis et al., 2016). Therefore, it is vital that preventative, culturally relevant mental health interventions are developed to engage Black men in support.

Rap music has been shown to provide a culturally meaningful platform for emotional expression, self-disclosure, and connection (Adeyola & Allen, 2025; Alvarez, 2011; Compton Dickinson & Souflas, 2011; Ierardi & Jenkins, 2011; Jefferson & Ohrt, 2024; Short, 2017). Clinical and community-based interventions have demonstrated the therapeutic potential of rap music in the US (e.g., Alvarez, 2011). However, the application of rap music in everyday, non-clinical settings within the UK remains unexplored. Although UK-based studies have highlighted rap's value within clinical and forensic contexts (Compton Dickinson & Souflas, 2011; Short, 2017), there is a gap in understanding how Black men engage with rap to address mental health challenges outside of these settings.

This study directly addresses this gap by examining how Black men outside of clinical or forensic contexts use rap music for mental health expression. By not restricting participation based on mental health diagnosis or service use, this research seeks to reflect the diversity of mental health experiences among Black men and capture the perspectives of a group that remains underrepresented in research and service provision. Furthermore, by exploring the role of rap in facilitating mental health expression, this study seeks to understand whether creative engagement with rap may help overcome barriers to talking about mental health, which may reduce stigma and promote earlier help-seeking.

The findings of this study could inform the development of culturally responsive mental health care. By highlighting how rap music supports mental health expression and disclosure in everyday contexts, services may benefit from integrating established or adapted rap-based interventions into preventative therapeutic practice. Additionally, partnering with Black-led creative and cultural organisations to co-develop community-based rap initiatives may facilitate earlier engagement, reduce stigma, and help rebuild trust between Black communities and mental health services (Centre for Mental Health, 2022). This study aligns with current policy priorities, including the NHS Race & Health Observatory (2020), the Patient and Carer Race Equality Framework (2021), and the NHS Long Term Plan (2019), which call for anti-racist and culturally competent mental health care. By centring Black men's lived experiences and engagement with rap music, this study supports efforts to challenge and dismantle the systemic inequities that have long impeded mental health care access and outcomes for Black communities.

1.7. Research Aims and Questions

Given the contextual gaps and methodological limitations in the current literature, this study aims to build on research by understanding the role of rap music in facilitating mental health expression among Black men within the UK. Research suggests that listening to rap and hip-hop music can open conversations about mental health and broader social issues among Black men (Adeyola & Allen, 2025; Francis, 2018, 2021), however there is little known about what makes this possible. Therefore, by focusing on a non-clinical, UK-based sample, this research aims to offer insight into whether and why rap music facilitates mental health disclosure

among Black men. Given rap's cultural prominence in the UK and its engagement with themes of mental health, adversity, and identity, it provides a relevant lens through which to explore these experiences.

The research questions are as follows:

- How do Black men describe the impact of creating rap music on their willingness to talk about mental health and adversity?
- What aspects of rap music do Black men identify as influencing their openness and disclosure about mental health?

2. METHODS

2.1. Chapter Overview

This chapter begins by providing context to the researcher's ontological and epistemological position relevant to the study's methodology. It then discusses the study's design, materials, participants, procedure, and ethical considerations. The chapter ends with a summary of the analytic approach used to analyse the results.

2.2. Ontological and Epistemological Position

Ontology and epistemology shape how we understand and investigate social phenomena. Ontology concerns the nature of reality and what can be known about it (Bhaskar, 1975), and epistemology addresses how knowledge of that reality can be acquired and validated (Steup & Neta, 2020). These philosophical foundations influence research processes relating to how decisions are made.

This research is grounded in a critical realist position. Ontologically, critical realism asserts that reality exists independently of our awareness or knowledge of it, while epistemologically it acknowledges that our understanding of this reality is conceptually mediated and socially produced. Therefore, critical realism posits that while an objective reality exists, our understanding of it is mediated through social, cultural, and historical contexts (Fletcher, 2017). This enables researchers to explore how participants make sense of their experiences while acknowledging that meaning is constructed within specific historical, social, and cultural contexts (Willig, 2019).

Epistemologically, this study adopts a relativist stance, recognising that knowledge is context-dependent and influenced by different individual perspectives.

Epistemological relativism maintains that multiple, potentially competing, interpretations of reality coexist, each shaped by specific social, cultural, and historical contexts (Burr, 2015). Consequently, knowledge is not viewed as absolute or universally fixed, but as socially negotiated and subject to revision.

A critical realist stance aligns with the study's aims and methodology as it recognises that Black men's experiences of creating rap music are shaped by both their

individual perspectives and broader sociocultural factors (Maxwell, 2012). By situating participants' narratives within these contexts, critical realism offers a lens to explore the lived realities of Black men and the systemic influences shaping their experiences.

2.3. Design

The study used qualitative methodology by conducting individual semi-structured interviews. Qualitative interviews were chosen as they allow for complex personal experiences to be explored through rich and in-depth conversations (Barker et al., 2015). The semi-structured approach was adopted as it enables the interview to follow a guide, ensuring that relevant topics are discussed, while also allowing for flexibility to explore emerging themes and unexpected areas of relevance (Kallio et al., 2016). This flexibility is valuable in under-researched areas, as it allows the interviewer to respond to new perspectives and experiences. Furthermore, this method allows for a conversational approach which can help build rapport, supporting participants to feel comfortable in sharing personal experiences.

2.4. Participants

The study aimed to recruit between 10 and 12 participants. This is consistent with research suggesting that conducting more than 10 interviews typically provides sufficient depth and breadth of data to generate meaningful insights in medium-scale projects, including doctoral theses (Braun & Clarke, 2013). Research also suggests that data saturation, the point at which no new themes or information are generated from additional interviews, often occurs within the first 12 interviews, depending on the complexity of the research topic and participant variability (Guest et al., 2006).

2.4.1. Inclusion Criteria

The following inclusion criteria was used in the study:

- Adults (aged 18 and above)
- Identify as male and Black or mixed heritage Black
- Create rap music in any capacity (e.g., writing lyrics, producing lyrics, performing)
- Live in the UK

- English speaking
- Able to access and use Microsoft Teams

2.4.2. Participant Demographics

Eleven participants consented to take part in the study. Participants ranged in age from 24 to 51 years ($M = 33.64$, $SD = 8.86$) and identified as being from a range of ethnic backgrounds. Table 1 summarises the demographic information collected during the interviews. All participants completed the interviews and there were no dropouts or requests to withdraw data.

Table 1.

Participant Demographic Information.

Pseudonym	Age	Ethnicity (Census)	Geographical Region (UK)
Michael	28	African	Yorkshire and the Humber
Daniel	24	African	Greater London
Jordan	28	White & Black Caribbean	Greater London
Reece	29	Black British	Greater London
Chris	25	Black British	Yorkshire and the Humber
Leon	42	White & Black Caribbean	West Midlands
Trey	33	African	Greater London
Aaron	51	Black Caribbean	East Midlands
Samuel	46	White & Black Caribbean	West Midlands
Kieran	33	White & Black Caribbean	North West England
Elijah	31	Black Caribbean	East Midlands

2.5. Materials

2.5.1. Interview Schedule

A semi-structured interview schedule was developed to explore the study's research questions (see Appendix D). The schedule was designed following recommendations by Bearman (2019) for constructing semi-structured interviews:

1. Articulate questions focused on the key area to be explored
2. Use an intuitive conversational structure
3. Refine the schedule with piloting and feedback

To facilitate rapport building and ensure an initiative conversational flow, the interview began with rapport-building questions about participants' interest in rap music and demographic information. The main questions focused on participants' experiences of creating rap, emotional responses to rap, and discussing mental health and adversity through rap. Prompting questions explored themes of emotional expression, vulnerability, and the therapeutic role of rap. The interview ended with a summary, consent reconfirmation, and debrief.

The interview schedule was developed collaboratively, incorporating feedback from both the research supervisor and members of the target demographic to enhance relevance and clarity. Specifically, the questions were reviewed and refined through consultation with the supervisor and two Black males who created rap music. This collaborative process aimed to ensure that the interview questions were accessible, engaging and appropriate, therefore improving the validity and depth of the data collected.

Demographic information was also collected during the interview, including age, census ethnicity group, and geographical location within the UK. This demographic information provides important context for understanding participants' experiences within their social and cultural contexts. It was also used to determine the representativeness and generalisability of the study.

2.5.2. Resources

All interviews were conducted virtually using Microsoft Teams, a secure video-calling platform with built in recording and transcription. Virtual interviews were chosen to enable greater flexibility and accessibility for the interviews.

An information sheet, consent form, and debrief sheet was developed for the study (see Appendix E, F and G). The research advertisement poster was made using Canva, an online graphic design platform (see Appendix H). These materials were

developed with feedback from the research supervisor and the target demographic, aiming to ensure that they were informative, accessible, and engaging.

Contact with participants was made through the university email system. All research data was stored through the University of East London Microsoft OneDrive, a secure personal data storing platform accessible to the researcher and research supervisor.

2.6. Procedure

2.6.1. Recruitment

Convenience sampling and snowball recruitment methods were employed to recruit participants for the study. A social media account was created on X, where the research recruitment poster was shared. In addition, several community-based music and youth organisations were contacted and asked to distribute the poster within their professional and personal networks. Further details of the recruitment strategy and the recruitment poster can be found in Appendix H.

2.6.2. Initial Contact and Informed Consent

Participants expressed interest in the study by contacting the researcher via university email. Participants were subsequently emailed an information sheet outlining the study's aims, procedures, and participant rights (see Appendix E), and the consent form to read and sign if they would like to take part (see Appendix F). The researcher provided participants with the opportunity to ask any questions about their involvement. Informed consent was obtained through electronic signatures or digital completion of the consent form. The researcher then arranged a suitable time and date for the interviews to take place on Microsoft Teams with those who provided informed consent.

2.6.3. Interview Process

Individual interviews were conducted virtually on Microsoft Teams and were expected to last between 45 and 60 minutes. The duration of interviews ranged from 32 minutes to 84 minutes, with an average length of 55 minutes. For interviews that extended beyond this time frame, participants provided consent to continue and were reminded that they could stop at any point if they wished.

At the start of each interview, participants were reminded of the study's purpose and their rights, including informed consent and their ability to withdraw from the study at any time without providing an explanation. Participants were asked for consent to record the interview on Microsoft Teams. The interview began with rapport-building and the collection of demographic information, followed by questions from the semi-structured interview schedule (see Appendix D).

The interview concluded with a debriefing process, during which participants' consent was reconfirmed, and their right to withdraw from the study was reiterated. The process for voucher reimbursement was explained and participants were subsequently emailed a voucher reimbursement form (see Appendix I) along with the study's debrief sheet (see Appendix G). Once the form was returned, participants were issued with a £10 Amazon voucher via email.

2.6.4. Interview Transcription

Interviews were recorded and automatically transcribed on Microsoft Teams. The researcher then manually corrected and verified the interview transcriptions. Interviews were transcribed verbatim, preserving the participants' use of vernacular language and rap references to maintain authenticity. Identifiable information was removed, and participants were given pseudonyms to ensure confidentiality. Transcripts were checked and read multiple times to ensure anonymity and accuracy. The anonymised transcripts were then securely stored and original recordings were deleted following transcript completion.

Where necessary, minor edits were made to the transcriptions to improve clarity and readability. This includes the removal of repeated words or incomplete sentences, as well as the use of ellipses to indicate where content has been omitted for conciseness without altering meaning.

2.6.5. Compensation

Participants received compensation for their time and contribution to the research in the form of individual £10 Amazon vouchers. This decision was informed by ethical research practices suggesting that compensation is appropriate when participants share sensitive personal experiences, topics may evoke emotional responses, time

commitment is substantial, and disclosure involves personal vulnerability (Head, 2009).

2.6.6. Data Management

Participant names and pseudonyms, contact details, consent forms, demographic information, interview transcriptions, and voucher reimbursement forms were securely and separately stored in encrypted Microsoft Excel and Word files on the university's OneDrive system, adhering to data protection guidelines.

2.7. Ethical Considerations

This research was conducted in accordance with the British Psychological Society's Code of Human Research Ethics (BPS, 2021) and received approval from the University of East London's Psychology Research Ethics Committee following minor amendments (see Appendix J).

2.7.1. Informed Consent

Informed consent was obtained through a process that emphasised voluntary participation and the right to withdraw. Participants received detailed information about the study's aims, procedures, and potential risks prior to participation. The information sheet outlined the study's purpose, interview format, data handling procedures, and participant rights in clear, accessible language (see Appendix E). Participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without explanation or consequence, and to the withdrawal of their data up to 3 weeks after the interview.

2.7.2. Confidentiality and Data Protection

Participant confidentiality was protected through data management procedures in line with research ethics guidelines and GDPR requirements (BPS, 2021; European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2016). All identifying information was removed or replaced with pseudonyms to ensure anonymity in the interview transcripts. This included names, geographical locations, and any other potentially identifying details mentioned during interviews such as names of rap songs or albums made by the participant. Audio recordings were deleted following

transcription verification, and anonymised transcripts were stored securely on the university's OneDrive.

2.7.3. Managing Distress and Risk Management

Given the sensitive nature of discussions around mental health, attention was paid to managing potential participant distress. The information sheet explicitly outlined the potentially sensitive nature of interview topics, allowing participants to make informed decisions about participation (see Appendix E). During interviews, participants were reminded they could pause, skip questions, take breaks, or withdraw from the study.

At the end of the interview, participants were verbally debriefed and offered the space to ask any questions or discuss any difficulties arising from the interview. A debrief sheet was sent to participants after their interviews, which contained contact information for relevant mental health support (see Appendix G).

A risk assessment was conducted prior to data collection, with protocols established for managing any safeguarding concerns that might arise during interviews. This included clear procedures for responding to disclosures of risk to self or others, aligned with university protocols and professional guidelines.

2.7.4. Researcher Supervision

The potential emotional impact of conducting the interviews was considered. Regular supervision sessions were scheduled with the research supervisor to address any methodological and emotional aspects of the research process. The researcher's positionality was also considered, in relation to specific experiences, knowledge, and identity that could influence research processes and interpretation of the data.

2.8. Analytic Approach

2.8.1. Rationale

This study employed reflexive thematic analysis (RTA) as its analytic approach (Braun & Clarke, 2021a). RTA involves systemically coding data from interview transcriptions and generating themes, enabling the exploration of semantic (explicit) and latent (underlying) meanings (Braun & Clarke, 2019). Throughout this process,

the researcher reflects on their positionality and how it influences data interpretation and theme development.

RTA is not rooted in any theoretical background which makes it a flexible analytic approach (Braun & Clarke, 2021a). This flexibility is useful for research in underexplored areas, as it facilitates an open, inductive approach without any theoretical constraints when examining and analysing the data. This is valuable for understanding and amplifying the voices of under-represented groups, such as Black men, whose perspectives are often overlooked in mental health research.

RTA aligns with the study's critical realist epistemological stance by capturing participants' explicit experiences and exploring how these experiences are shaped by broader social, cultural, and historical contexts. This enables better understanding about the interplay between individual experiences and systemic factors.

2.8.2. Steps

In analysing the data, this study adopted the six-phase approach to RTA (Braun & Clarke, 2021a).

2.8.2.1. *Data familiarisation*

Data familiarisation involved the process of conducting interviews, transcribing the data and reading the interview transcripts. The interview transcripts were read repeatedly, checking for accuracy and making note of initial observations, patterns, and meanings. Summaries of the interview transcripts were also written. During this process, the researcher made note of initial ideas and feelings that arose to discuss in supervision and inform future data analysis.

2.8.2.2. *Generating initial codes*

The coding process involved systematically analysing interview transcripts line by line, identifying meaningful segments that captured both semantic (explicit) and latent (implicit) experiences and meanings. Codes were assigned to segments of text and code labels were continuously refined throughout the process. This systematic categorisation of data formed the foundation for subsequent theme development.

2.8.2.3. *Generating themes*

Initial codes were collated into potential themes by looking for recurring patterns or broader meanings in the data. A theme represents a significant aspect of the data which helps to explain the research questions.

2.8.2.4. *Reviewing themes*

Themes were refined and reviewed to ensure that they meaningfully captured patterns across the dataset while also highlighting individual experiences. This involved checking themes against codes and the entire dataset.

2.8.2.5. *Defining themes*

Each theme was clearly defined and labelled to accurately reflect the study's focus and research questions. During the write up (final stage of RTA), participant quotes were identified that helped to define and capture the theme name.

2.8.2.6. *Write up*

The data were brought together in the final write up of this thesis. Themes were supported using anonymised extracts from the transcripts.

2.8.3. Quality Assurance

Quality assurance followed the principles outlined by Braun and Clarke (2021b), who conceptualise quality in reflexive thematic analysis (RTA) as an evolving process grounded in reflexive engagement, coherence, transparency, and contextual understanding of the data.

2.8.3.1. *Researcher reflexivity*

Throughout RTA, researcher reflexivity is maintained through reflections in supervision and a reflexive log. The reflections paid particular attention to emotional responses to the study, analytic decisions, and potential biases arising from the researcher's identity and personal and professional experiences.

My motivations to conduct this research developed out of personal and professional experiences. I am a mixed heritage Black Sierra Leonean and White Welsh female, born and raised in Wales. Growing up, I had limited connection to Black cultural

spaces outside of my family, making hip-hop and rap music a way for me to connect to that part of my identity and experience cultural representation. I have reflected on how personal experiences of navigating cultural identity may have shaped how I understood participants' narratives, particularly in relation to issues of racial discrimination and marginalisation.

Professionally, my work as an assistant psychologist in a young offenders' prison further influenced my interest in this area. Observing Black men using rap to express themselves more freely than in traditional therapy highlighted rap's potential as a tool for emotional expression and engagement. My broader clinical experience with marginalised groups, including refugees and prisoners, has deepened my awareness of systemic inequalities. While this may have enhanced my sensitivity to structural issues raised by participants, I remained mindful not to project my own experiences onto their accounts.

As a trainee clinical psychologist in the NHS, my role may have influenced how participants perceived me, either as part of a system they mistrusted or as someone seeking change. My training at the University of East London, grounded in critical and anti-racist frameworks, has supported my capacity to engage with issues of power and oppression. These influences inevitably shaped my analysis, and ongoing reflexivity allowed me to acknowledge and navigate these dynamics throughout the research process. I aimed to approach the data with a critical lens, reflecting on the influence of social, cultural, and historical contexts, while maintaining sensitivity to participants' individual experiences.

2.8.3.2. Transparency

Transparency was ensured by providing a detailed account of the research process, including data collection, transcription, coding, and theme development. This allows readers to trace how themes were generated and how interpretative decisions were made, contributing to the trustworthiness of the analysis.

2.8.3.3. Coherence

Analytic coherence was maintained through an iterative, recursive process of engagement with the data. Themes were developed inductively, closely aligned with the research questions, and were refined through revisiting the data. This process

supported the development of themes that were theoretically and conceptually coherent.

2.8.3.4. Data engagement, analysis, and interpretation

Themes were developed as patterns of shared meaning underpinned by a central organising concept. Participant quotes were integrated throughout the analysis to illustrate the themes and enhance the credibility of the findings.

The analytic process was informed by a reflexive engagement with the study's aims and epistemological stance. This approach ensured that the study remained sensitive to the nuances of participants' experiences. Efforts were also made to engage with semantic and latent levels of meaning in participants' narratives. Broader sociocultural influences shaping participants' experiences were also critically considered.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Chapter Overview

This chapter presents the results of the RTA. To contextualise the findings, details about how participants create rap are first provided. A thematic map is then used to visually illustrate the overarching themes and sub-themes. The subsequent sections provide an exploration of each theme, supported by direct quotation extracts from the interview transcripts. These extracts aim to ground the analysis in participants' lived experiences and enhance transparency around the interpretative process (Patton, 2002).

3.2. Participant Approaches to Creating Rap

Participants created rap in diverse ways, ranging from writing, performing, and producing to facilitating rap workshops within schools, the community, and prisons. Themes rapped about were personal and reflected broader societal issues, such as mental health, identity, inequality, and personal challenges.

Table 2 summarises participants' engagement with rap, including their mode of rap creation and lyrical themes. This provides context for understanding how their personal experiences and creative processes may shape their engagement with rap.

3.3. Thematic Summary and Map

The thematic map (Figure 1) presents three overarching themes which highlight how rap is used by participants as a form of therapy, a space for negotiating identity and vulnerability, and a means of building connection, community, and influencing others. Sub-themes were developed to illustrate the nuances within each theme.

Table 2.*Participants' Creative Engagement with Rap.*

Participant	Mode of Rap	Lyrical Themes
Michael	Writing	Love, injustice, life experiences, struggles
Daniel	Writing, recording	Motivation, empowerment, personal struggles, heartbreak, Black unity
Jordan	Writing rap and poetry	Social issues, personal experiences, systemic problems
Reece	Writing, recording, performing	Self-reflection, relationships, self-sabotage
Chris	Writing, selling lyrics	Masculinity, grief, resilience, personal struggles
Leon	Freestyling, writing, performing, workshops	Social critique, mental health, personal growth, education
Trey	Writing, producing, performing	Society, inequality, self-discovery, personal growth
Aaron	Writing, performing	Personal struggles, socio-political issues, identity
Samuel	Writing, performing, workshops	Reflection, life experiences, racism, personal growth
Kieran	Writing, performing, beatboxing	Self-reflection, spirituality, love, personal growth
Elijah	Writing, performing, spoken word	Social issues, identity, masculinity, personal experiences

Figure 1

Thematic Map Illustrating Themes and Sub-theme from the RTA.

3.4. Theme 1: Rap as Therapy

This theme focuses on the benefits and limitations of rap as “self-therapy” by participants to overcome challenges, express and release emotions, reflect on experiences, gain awareness, and find solutions to problems.

3.4.1. Overcoming Challenges: Rap Is a “Powerful Medicine”

This sub-theme captures how participants described using rap as a therapeutic tool, a way to find solutions, and as a means of escapism.

Many participants described rap as therapeutic, with Kieran noting it as a “powerful medicine.” Elijah described rap as a “powerful” form of “self-therapy”, emphasising its profound role helping him work through personal challenges. He also shared “I’m at a point now where once I write about something, it will not bother me the same way.” This suggests that the act of writing rap lyrics helped to support the impact of personal challenges.

Daniel similarly noted that rap was essential to his ability to overcome life’s challenges. He also described rap as “therapy”, helping him to “cope with many issues in life” and “move on”, explaining that without it, he would “be in a very dark place.” Reece referred to rap as a productive and constructive coping mechanism, stating “Rap is a form of self-therapy, just like alcohol and stuff like that. Obviously, it’s more productive.” This reflection emphasises rap as an avenue toward healthier coping strategies.

Participants shared specific examples of times where rap had helped them to overcome difficulties. Jordan described a recent period of feeling down and how rap helped him to alleviate emotional weight “Putting it down on a piece of paper and having it there and being able to recite it myself, all of a sudden the weight was lifted.” Chris expressed how rapping about a friend’s death allowed him to mourn in a way that facilitated being able to move forward, turning memories into meaningful rap lyrics. Trey shared how creating rap during a difficult adjustment to starting a new secondary school helped with isolation.

Participants described using rap to find solutions to personal challenges. Writing facilitated clarity, helping them process and resolve emotional difficulties. Chris explained that writing helped him recognise solutions to problems that initially felt overwhelming, stating “If I’m stressed and I write something, I feel like I can find solutions.” He also reflected on his belief in self-reliance, sharing that while he tries to talk to people sometimes, he ultimately prefers to find resolutions within himself. Leon echoed this, describing rap as a process of independently working through challenges:

I was able to deal with things, express myself about things, find my way through things, and it was all on my own. ... Whereas when you're part of something else, such as the NHS, I feel like you're, not being dictated to, that's the wrong word. But someone else is holding your hand through your therapy to help you find the answers yourself, whereas with rap you find the answers yourself completely and how to get there. (Leon)

Samuel shared an optimistic outlook, describing how rap has given him a space to explore challenges and potential solutions: “I’m quite an optimistic person as well so I liked to talk about the solutions to things, I hate this, I hate that, but I need more of this I need more of that, you know what I mean.”

For some participants, rap provided an escape from difficult realities. It allowed them to create alternative narratives, offering a relief from stress and adversity. They reflected on how his creative process during his youth was shaped by escapism. He described writing fantasy-based lyrics to detach from feelings of isolation in his real life: “Maybe it’s an escapism.” This highlights rap being used as a tool to create distance from personal challenges.

Kieran reflected on mixed experiences with bereavement counselling and CBT, acknowledging that although it had been helpful, it was not always consistent or accessible. He described how music became his primary source of support, especially while experiencing bereavement and homelessness, stating “Music got me through everything last year.” This suggests that creative expression can become a vital coping mechanism when professional support feels inaccessible.

Leon spoke about how rap offered an empowering sense of agency that traditional therapy could not. He emphasised the autonomy found in music: “I don’t think the therapy on its own ever would have got me to the place that hip-hop got me to, because hip-hop gave the power to me.” He described how experiences of CBT influenced his music, helping him challenge negative thoughts and emotions through lyrics. This suggests that while therapy introduced valuable strategies, rap provided a space where these insights could be built on to overcome mental health challenges.

3.4.2. Self-Expression and Catharsis: “It Feels Like a Cry on Paper”

This sub-theme describes how rap can be a useful medium for self-expression and catharsis. Participants described how rap has enabled them to openly express their experiences and feelings in a creative and constructive way.

Participants described rap as an outlet for self-expression, enabling them to explore and communicate their identities, experiences, and observations about the world. Michael reflected on how his writing integrated personal experiences and broader social issues: “I’ve written about love, I’ve written about injustice... I’m working on one presently, kind of infusing my personal life.”

Aaron described how rap became a space for processing experiences relating to identity, sharing “I was then able to start writing stuff that, kinda spoke about my experience as a Black kid in White suburbia.” His rap also addressed global socio-political issues like racism and injustice, therefore reflecting how his rap served as an evolving creative outlet for self-expression and advocacy about social issues affecting Black communities. Similarly, Trey reflected on using rap to explore and question complex societal questions and personal ideals, explaining “Perhaps a look at society. And perhaps a look at my own personal happiness in terms of like, what is that? What does ideal look like?”

Kieran wrote about his mixed-race identity and the nuanced challenges it brings, including experiences of prejudice from both Black and White communities. He explained:

There have been points where... I've expressed my struggles as someone who's mixed and has experienced prejudice... and [others] pretty much saying... you're not full Black though are you, so doesn't really matter? So my experience is invalid because I'm not full White or I'm not full Black. (Kieran)

Elijah also shared how his writing has reflected his experiences of racial profiling and discrimination, noting how wearing certain clothing items, like a durag, shaped how he was treated in different spaces: "You get stopped by the police, depending on what you wear... I remember writing about something during COVID about the way these guys wanted to try and treat me in Asda." Elijah's reflections demonstrate how rap can operate as personal expression, as well as resistance against racism and systemic biases.

Participants described rap as a helpful outlet for articulating emotions and thoughts that were difficult to express in other ways. Reece likened creating rap lyrics to keeping a diary, noting "Sometimes I don't really know how to express exactly what I'm feeling, but then I'll think of something and then I'll feel something at the moment, and then I'll be able to express it through music like that." Samuel reflected on how rap has allowed him to articulate feelings that were otherwise difficult to verbalise, describing rap as a "surrogate voice" that helped him to communicate with others. For Aaron, writing served as a medium to "clear [his] head" on days where his thoughts felt "scrambled."

When discussing the barriers to traditional mental health support, Jordan shared "It's too formal. I don't feel like you can, you can't do that with people, whereas let them express it in music. If they're creative, let them express it a certain way." This highlights how creative self-expression can feel like a more accessible and authentic form of communication compared to rigid therapeutic approaches.

Kieran described how creating rap has supported him in expressing feelings he struggles to describe in everyday conversation due to his dyspraxia:

It really helps me to express how I'm feeling and a lot of the time with my dyspraxia, I don't know if this coincides with it, but I think that sometimes I find it hard to describe things ... So, writing helps me do that, even though when I write, my writing can be quite abstract, you can feel what I'm saying, and I can feel what

I'm saying. ... It makes me feel just like I am being heard and that I can just get things off my chest and just express it in ways I didn't think I'd be able to ever.

(Kieran)

Kieran also spoke about using rap to express himself during difficult times, including experiences of loss and grief: "I lost quite a few people during COVID... the music I was making was helping me express that."

Leon shared insights from his personal life and professional work delivering rap workshops, illustrating how he has witnessed rap enabling emotional expression for individuals facing significant challenges. He described a friend who struggled to talk about his experiences but used rap to process and reflect on past trauma:

I know for a fact that he bottles up a lot as a person. And you won't get much out of him in the way of conversation. ... but you can play one of his songs and hear the whole, you know, everything you know, even the gritty detail of it. (Leon)

Leon further reflected on working with a young boy involved in gang activity, observing how drill music became a powerful medium for expressing frustration and anger. He suggested that creating and discussing rap could help break emotional barriers:

I think he's just a brick wall and I think if they were trying to really address whatever trauma he went through, if they was to say, I'll tell you what, you make a song about it, record it, we'll listen to it together and then we'll talk. I think that would break that wall down. (Leon)

Many participants emphasised the benefits of the "cathartic" nature of rap, describing it as a powerful method of releasing emotions. Jordan described rap as "helping you flow that emotional channel, channel that emotion into something." Aaron shared that the process of catharsis has "prevented [him] from having mental health issues." This again highlights the therapeutic nature of self-expression through rap.

Samuel noted that writing rap helped project his thoughts and experiences into words, preventing negative emotions from manifesting destructively: 'cause, if it didn't come out that way, it would have been probably coming out in other very

negative ways.” Chris similarly described the strength gained from “taking [his] emotions out” through rap and spoke it as a way to express feelings of rage.

Trey highlighted rap’s positive ability to provide an emotional outlet:

It’s great. It feels like you’re sort of venting it. It feels it’s got the same effect as venting, but in a less negative, less disruptive kind of like. Venting can be quite a negative thing, but it feels like it’s got that release that venting has. It feels like you’re getting it out. Do you know what I mean? ... It feels like a cry on paper.

(Trey)

3.4.3. Self-Awareness and Reflection: “A Record of Where My Mind Was”

Participants described how rap facilitated self-awareness and understanding, enabling them to process their emotions, reflect on personal growth, and make sense of their experiences.

For many participants, writing rap offered a meditative and reflective space to explore their emotions and experiences. Trey described the process as “meditative reflection” that enables him to “think through subconscious thoughts” in a helpful way. Leon shared that rap “helps you understand what you’ve been through”, suggesting that rap can be used as a tool to improve self-awareness.

Similarly, Samuel explained how writing allowed for an internal dialogue, offering a private space to question emotions and thoughts. He reflected on how writing became a way of engaging with his deeper feelings:

You confide into the pad ... it’s just you writing it down. And every day you’re wondering to yourself, is what I’ve written here the feeling or message I’ve felt up here? (points to head and heart). So it’s that dialogue with yourself. (Samuel)

Elijah echoed this, sharing how rap allows for greater self-awareness by prompting deeper questioning about himself and his thoughts:

Before you even finish writing, you're like, why do I think that? Why have I said that? Start getting deeper and deeper and then get back to the root level again. ... what does this mean? Do I think there's a bigger problem here? (Elijah)

Elijah noted that while he encourages others to seek professional support, his default approach is to process emotions through writing rap lyrics. He emphasised that writing allowed him to ask and answer his own questions, sharing that “90% of the time, I would openly say I’d go to writing about it, rapping about it, freestyling about it.”

Several participants described how rap served as a lyrical record of past emotions, allowing them to revisit and reinterpret their experiences over time:

Sometimes writing the bars you could be quite angry ... But then it’s months down the line, and you might actually forget how you actually felt. (Jordan)

Sometimes I’ll be performing some lyrics ... these could be lyrics that I’ve wrote eight years ago, and I could be doing them every day. And then one day I’ll really listen to what I was saying in the first place and relate back to it again. (Kieran)

Sometimes it can be 10, 20 years later that you listen to a song and you’re like OK, now I get it ... But then as you mature and life changes, you’re like, oh, bloody hell. That’s what that means. ... I used to describe it like people working on a tapestry. When you’re close you can see the stitches, but you can’t see the picture that you’re making. You need to step back from that tapestry. And then when you see that tapestry, you can see this. Oh, I’ve sewn this amazing battle scene or whatever. (Aaron)

Aaron’s tapestry metaphor illustrates how rap can function as immediate expression and a reflective lens. Initially, lyrics may feel fragmented (“the stitches”), but over time and with life experience, their broader meaning emerges, like stepping back to see the full tapestry. The “battle scene” imagery highlights struggle and resilience, framing past challenges as part of a coherent personal narrative. This reflects how rap can support real-time emotional expression and retrospective understanding, allowing participants to reflect on past and present experiences.

Samuel valued his old writings as a form of personal investment, recognising how they held long-term meaning and insights:

I recognise I was quite insightful at that point in my life as well in some ways. And in the way that I said things and when I look back now, I think, I like the way I phrased that. That's why I've kept everything. At some point, I'll be going through them. I see that as like money in the bank. Or there's a good investment I've made. All I've got to do is just keep it safe and go back to it and it'll give me value in some way at some point. (Samuel)

This suggests that rap can be used to capture and preserve emotional experiences. By revisiting their lyrics over time, participants were able to reflect on their past emotions, recognise personal growth, and gain new insights into their experiences. This process highlights how rap can offer immediate emotional release, and function as an evolving narrative, allowing for deeper self-awareness as perspectives shift with time and maturity.

3.4.4. Limitations of Rap as Therapy: "You Can't Always Therapise Yourself"

This sub-theme explores how despite rap being regarded as therapeutic by many participants, various limitations were identified. It was reported that rap could not always offer complete resolution of difficulties or replace professional mental health support and guidance from others.

Participants recognised the value of professional guidance in facilitating deeper emotional exploration. Although Reece expressed a preference for rap, describing it as a more "natural" form of self-expression, he shared "I reckon realistically the therapy session would probably be more beneficial." He also acknowledged the supportive role that professionals play, stating "Therapists ... help you to be able to ask yourself the questions and go deeper down a path ... you can't always therapise ... you can't always do that to yourself." This suggests an awareness that professional support may be more useful, while also highlighting the appeal of rap as a familiar, creative outlet, one that feels more accessible and indirect, even if not sufficient to fully address mental health challenges.

Aaron similarly noted limitations in rap as self-therapy: "I'm not a psychiatrist. I'm not a psychologist. I don't have the answers to all of my questions." These reflections highlight an understanding that rap, although described as a powerful form of "self-therapy", may not substitute for professional therapeutic support. It also

demonstrates how participants perceived professional support as complementary to their creative processes, providing the external perspective necessary for deeper emotional exploration.

Leon used an analogy to describe how an individual cannot support themselves without professional support: “You can’t self-diagnose and self-cure yourself ... you can’t break your leg and go right, I’m gonna [fix it], you’ve got to go to a doctor who’s going to plaster it properly.” This suggests that the limitations may not be inherent to rap itself but reflects an individual need for external guidance and support.

Samuel reinforced the importance of drawing on multiple sources for support, suggesting that no single approach could provide complete understanding:

Well, everyone is a person, innit, family, friends or professional. If you know if they’re not correct themselves, how do you know to be the best balanced position to give you the right advice? So I think you’ve always got to be accountable yourself to some extent anyway, and then seek counsel in several sources ... I’d say get the information and have it measured up against something. Searching, reading, getting your information from different sources. (Samuel)

This perspective reflects the participants’ broader sense of agency and responsibility in managing their wellbeing, while acknowledging that support, whether creative or professional, should be approached with reflection and discernment.

Some participants expressed concerns that rap, while cathartic, did not always facilitate a direct confrontation of personal difficulties. Aaron reflected on how the abstract nature of his lyrics, although therapeutic, sometimes prevented him from addressing issues directly: “While it’s very cathartic for me, sometimes I’m not directly addressing the issue or the problem ... I’m at ease with myself but potentially not repairing relationships as well as I could.” Elijah also described how expressing his emotions through rap can suppress further engagement with his difficulties. He shared “I’m at a point now where once I write about something, it will not bother me the same way... that’s good and bad... because all it takes is the right trigger for that still to be a problem.” This suggests that although rap can offer relief, it can also sometimes hinder long-term resolution. This sub-theme highlights the importance of

considering additional or complementary forms of support alongside creative expression.

3.5. Theme 2: Navigating Vulnerability, Identity, and Stigma Through Rap

This theme explores how participants navigate vulnerability, masculinity, and societal and cultural stigma through rap. It discusses how these challenges can influence conversations with loved ones and access to mental health support, and why rap is often chosen as the preferred mode of self-expression.

3.5.1. Masculinity and Stigma: “Forced to Be Tough”

Participants reflected on how restrictive cultural ideas of masculinity, particularly within Black communities, shaped their creative expression in rap. Several participants described how these norms limited how vulnerability could be expressed, leading them to adopt more masculine personas in their music.

Chris shared how his earlier engagement with creating poetry felt at odds with masculine ideals and prompted a shift in his writing:

I was more into writing poems and soft stuff. Then I started thinking this is too feminine for me, I need to find another character for myself ... I started writing some more hard stuff. (Chris)

This highlights an internal struggle between authentic self-expression and societal expectations. The shift towards “hard stuff” suggests a negotiation of identity, where softer, more vulnerable poetic expression was suppressed to align with traditional masculine norms.

Chris further reflected on how broader societal narratives influenced his approach to writing, sharing “It’s a bit of being more of a simp. I feel like it doesn’t attract women anymore, being that kind of a man.” Chris describes a pressure to conform to dominant masculine ideals, influenced by culture and perceived social rewards, such as approval and attraction. The implication is that vulnerability may be seen as a risk, encouraging him to adopt a persona that may mask deeper emotional struggles.

Chris stated that masculinity is “what the Black men expects from [him]”. A similar reflection from Jordan highlights the cultural complexities of masculinity and

vulnerability within the Black community: “As a Black male, you’re forced to be tough. Like you can’t show emotion, so being able to put it down on something that’s more accepted might help.” This suggests that rap can provide a culturally acceptable space for expressing emotions that might otherwise be suppressed, therefore highlighting rap’s role in allowing participants to challenge restrictive masculine norms in socially acceptable ways.

Beyond masculinity, participants discussed how societal stigma shaped their emotional expression within rap. Some reflected on the challenges of expressing vulnerability due to fear of being judged or misunderstood. Chris shared how he sometimes raps lyrics about suicidal feelings, reflecting on how this raises concerns for him about the impact on his reputation:

I think it will ruin my reputation in society. I don’t want to sound like somebody who can take out my life. A person who can take their life I think is considered a dangerous person. Because if you can take out your life, then you can take someone else’s life. (Chris)

This highlights the stigma surrounding mental health and masculinity. The fear of being perceived as “dangerous” for expressing suicidal thoughts reflects broader societal discomfort with vulnerability, particularly amongst men. This aligns with the notion that emotional restraint is often equated with strength, while expressions of struggle are pathologized or misunderstood.

Participants also discussed how stigma surrounding rap music shaped their creative identity. Many described how rap is perceived as “violent” or “negative”, contributing to a broader cultural narrative that stigmatises the genre and its creators.

Kieran reflected on how rap is often reduced to negative stereotypes:

People have this automatic thing with rap, where it’s violent, it’s in your face it’s degrading ... which it can be. But there are so many other artists that that don’t do that kind of thing. And I think nowadays when you have rappers like Dave or even these like hardcore gangster rappers in New York. One day they’ll just drop a song that’s them talking about their lives and their losses and their actual struggles where people go, oh, wait, no, there’s this side to them as well. (Kieran)

This highlights how vulnerability and struggle exist alongside tougher narratives, yet the latter often dominates mainstream perceptions. Jordan expressed how stigma shapes assumptions about his music, indicating how this can limit how artists are understood, often reducing complex identities to negative assumptions:

I make grime music. People can be like ah, I know this guy or because I do hop on drill beats as well and they're just like oh, OK, you're one of those guys. ... Yeah, there can be a negative stigma towards it before they listen. (Jordan)

The racial aspect of stigma was also discussed, with Reece identifying how rap is often used as a “scapegoat”, particularly in relation to societal issues, suggesting that this bias is underpinned by systemic racism: “It’s just anti-Blackness, really.”

Reece challenged the assumption that rap, particularly gangster rap, is inherently violent, drawing comparisons to other art forms: “I don’t think a genre can be negative. It’s like horror movies, I don’t think they’re necessarily negative, games aren’t inherently negative.” This perspective highlights a perceived hypocrisy, where rap is stigmatised in ways that other violent or provocative forms of art are not, reinforcing discriminatory cultural biases.

Daniel, however, expressed concern about rap music, critiquing the ethical implications of some of its content and the impact on younger audiences. He highlighted that they “disrespect women and incite others, gang up against each other” and expressed a desire for rap to be more “positive”.

In contrast, Trey reflected on how some rap music can be understood as creative storytelling, rather than a literal reflection of real-life experiences:

A lot of this rap is forgivable in the sense that if you’re able to just paint a scene in your head like a film, that’s literally all it is ... it’s just storytelling, it’s just like you tell your little stories, it’s exciting. It’s like watching an action film. (Trey)

Elijah highlighted the complexity of rap and its relationship to lived experiences, identity and reality, suggesting that artists may feel pressured to align their lives with the lyrical themes they rap about:

This is why rap and hip-hop is very tricky ... Some of it very much fuels and is violence-raged ... I feel like people end up living a life deliberately because they want to be able to adhere and feel like in order to be able to identify as being an artist from that genre, you've got to appear a certain way. (Elijah)

This suggests that stigma can shape not only public perceptions but also how artists construct and perform their identities, potentially encouraging them to conform to stereotypes to be seen as authentic.

3.5.2. Rap as a Safe Space for Vulnerability: "I'd Rather Not Put This on You"

Many participants shared that while they were able to have conversations with family and friends about difficult emotions, rap often felt like a more natural or accessible mode of expression.

Reece described how rap allowed him to articulate his experiences more precisely than conversations with loved ones, stating "They might not necessarily know the ins and outs, ... and I'll probably talk about a bit more concisely when I'm rapping." Similarly, Aaron suggested that writing rap often preceded conversations with others, sharing "It would probably pre-empt me talking to somebody rather than replace me talking to somebody."

Some participants expressed concerns about how disclosures might impact relationships. Elijah shared that while he was more open with his family now, he still exercised caution when discussing certain topics, particularly if they could affect how his loved ones viewed others. He explained "I don't want to use the word incriminate, not in a legal sense, but if it's something that then impacts someone else, I don't like to speak on things that may involve other people's business." Instead, he used rap to share experiences indirectly, saying "I can speak metaphorically and mask it through different things."

Elijah also highlighted concerns about burdening others with his emotions, explaining that "I'd rather not put this on you" when talking about sharing his problems with friends. This may reflect an underlying worry about overloading loved ones and the desire to protect others from emotional distress. He also reported worries about friends sharing his disclosed problems more broadly: "a lot of people do not know

how to keep information to themselves.” This suggests that rap can provide a more private and controlled form of expression, allowing participants to process emotions without risking misunderstandings, discomfort, or wider unwanted disclosure.

Jordan explained how expressing emotional struggles in rap elicited more positive responses than direct conversations with peers, who might dismiss such disclosures as “soft.” He shared: “If I went to some friends... they might laugh... Whereas if I put all of that on music... they’d be like, oh, this is good, man.” Elijah similarly described rap as a safe space for vulnerability: “it’s socially acceptable within this subculture... to now be vulnerable in this space.” This highlights the potential of rap as a culturally relevant and safe medium for providing an emotional release.

While participants recognised the value of professional mental health support, many felt that rap was a more immediate, accessible, and empowering outlet for expressing emotions and dealing with difficulties. Aaron reflected on his reluctance to seek professional support:

It would be the music before seeking professional help. And that disappoints me a little bit in myself. ... The reason why it disappoints me a little bit is I had a friend that committed suicide recently and we didn’t talk. I never knew that that was in his mind. So, I think it’s good to talk and I think there is an issue with men in general not speaking enough. (Aaron)

This reflection highlights the tension between recognising the importance of open conversations and the comfort found in creative expression. However, Aaron also shared ambivalence about professional support, sharing:

I’m very much an advocate of now, even more so since my friend passed that men in particular talk and speak up and let somebody know if you’re going through something. But yeah, whether that’s professional. ... Not sure why I’m reluctant, but yeah. (Aaron)

3.5.3. Barriers to Help-Seeking: “Why Would You Trust That System?”

Participants described multiple personal and systemic barriers that shaped their experiences of emotional disclosure and seeking professional mental health support.

Several participants described concerns about connecting with professionals who did not share their cultural or racial backgrounds, creating feelings of disconnection and reluctance. Reece shared concerns about a potential cultural disconnect with a therapist: “I just got matched with like a random White lady from Portsmouth and I was just like. I don’t want to talk to you. I’m sorry. I just don’t feel comfortable to.” He acknowledged his potential bias, however he also compared it to cultural preferences in everyday life: “It’s like I wouldn’t go to a White barber ... they’re probably sick, but I just wouldn’t.” This highlights the importance of culturally familiar and accessible mental health support.

Jordan similarly discussed the lack of Black representation within mental health services: “I feel like within the Black community, there’s not too many people that look like you in that system, in those positions, do you get what I mean?” He reflected on other factors that can impact help-seeking, explaining “It could be cultural background, it could be area, it could be age, it could even be occupation. They dunno what you’re going through.” This suggests that a lack of shared cultural understanding, alongside other characteristics, can deepen feelings of discomfort about seeking professional support.

Systemic mistrust was another barrier, shaped by participants’ experiences with institutions such as the NHS and police. Leon reflected on his past fears about opening up to professionals:

When I was young, I was very angry and very violent up fighting all the time, but over the stupidest little things ... And I think if you then go and express that to someone, they might think you need to take this ridiculously strong medication or you need to be sectioned under the Mental Health Act because you're a danger to yourself or someone else. So, I think there’s worry on what the system will do.
(Leon)

This fear of being misunderstood, pathologized, and punished reflects deeper concerns about systemic racism and mistrust of authority. Leon described how his mistrust was shaped by negative experiences with the police:

I just felt attacked constantly, you know, like getting pulled over by the police for nothing. I got beat up by the police once when I was young. And although I was out of order, I didn't do anything to get beaten up, you know? So, I think you feel constantly attacked. So why would you trust that system at all? You feel like the doctor, the NHS would be part of that system somewhere down the line. (Leon)

Aaron shared similar concerns, shaped by witnessing his mother's struggles navigating the healthcare system: "I remember my mum would really battle with our GP, for instance, just to be heard because she was a Black woman." This demonstrates how negative experiences with healthcare can extend to mistrust of mental health services, where fear of judgement and systemic bias hinders help-seeking.

Jordan reflected on the intimidating nature of therapy, likening it to interrogations, which may reflect a wider mistrust of mental health systems:

How can you then have someone who's gonna sit down, piece of paper like, OK, you have to sit on this table? Nah, that's interrogation ... Even if you did that to me, I'd be sitting there, no comment, no comment. (Jordan)

For some, practical barriers like long waiting lists, inconsistency in service provision, and discharges due to cancelled sessions also impacted engagement. Kieran described his challenges accessing bereavement counselling and CBT through the NHS and difficulties with affording private therapy "Because I cancelled for that reason they had to stop. And they were like yeah, you'll have to come back to it ... But I didn't have the funds for it or anything like that." This led Kieran to use rap as a more reliable coping strategy, reflecting how structural barriers can push individuals towards creative approaches to overcome mental health challenges.

Some participants reflected on internal struggles that made it difficult to seek help. Chris described how fluctuating emotions affected his motivation to access therapy, sharing: "I think because sometimes I think I'm too emotional. ... I can need therapy like right now. But by the time I'm making the appointments, those emotions are gone." This suggests that fleeting emotional states and self-stigma around being "too emotional" could delay or prevent help-seeking. The sense of not feeling ready or

needing support by the time therapy becomes available highlights how accessibility and timing can be crucial.

Reece also expressed feelings of discomfort about professional therapy and shared that despite believing in its value: “It’s sitting down with someone who you don’t know ... I’ve definitely got a self-stigma around sitting down and just being able to explain myself to a professional.” This discomfort may reflect a self-stigma around vulnerability, shaped by fears of judgement and a reluctance to open up to strangers.

Trey described how concerns about being misunderstood or judged can deter emotional disclosure, particularly when speaking to professionals:

Every new person is a perspective. They hear you differently, perhaps what you say, the words you say, may be received differently. If, for example, you’re in a room of 15 psychologists, and you were saying your rhyme, you’d get maybe 15 different interpretations and that’s what you’re getting rid of, by sort of putting it to paper and putting it in a vacuum kind of thing. (Trey)

This suggests that creative expression, such as rap, can offer a safer and more controlled way to process emotions, reducing fears about misinterpretation.

3.5.4. Openness and Protection in Rap: “A Shield for What You Can't Say in Person”

Rap emerged as a space where participants navigated vulnerability, openness, and self-protection. Although rap provided an outlet for personal expression, it also acted as a shield, allowing participants to be selective about the depth of their disclosures.

Participants reflected on how rap is often regarded as an authentic art form, where vulnerability is encouraged. Reece highlighted the distinctiveness of rap, explaining “It’s a big thing for it to be very personal. And also it’s a big thing for you to be unique. Whereas I think with singing, it doesn’t necessarily have that.” He contrasted rap with other music genres like R&B and jazz, where it is more acceptable for artists to perform lyrics written by others. In contrast, rap was perceived as a genre where personal storytelling is expected. This expectation of personal narrative encourages vulnerability, suggesting rap as a space for authentic emotional expression.

Elijah echoed this, indicating that rap allows individuals from tough or hardened backgrounds to reveal deeper emotional experiences: “You could see the hardest of people bring themselves down to a level because it’s on rap.” This suggests that rap can act as an acceptable medium for vulnerability, breaking down barriers that might exist in other areas of life.

Despite rap’s openness, participants also described how it provided a protective barrier. Leon reflected on how the act of performing or writing rap could shield deeper emotions:

I think it creates a buffer between you and them, or the listener, and I think it’s more like a blanket around you... there’s definitely some kind of shield when you put something in a song that you wouldn’t be able to do in person.

This suggests that rap can allow for emotional expression while maintaining a degree of distance and protection, which Leon also described as a “safety barrier.” Trey similarly emphasised the freedom that comes with expressing emotions through rap, describing it as “writing to a vacuum.” He shared “There’s freedom in that. It’s not directed to anybody and there’s no barriers really. It can be as bright or dark as you like.” This suggests that the creative process can provide an emotional release without the pressure of interpretation or judgement.

Aaron reflected on the duality of rap as a form of openness and protection. On stage, he described embodying an extroverted persona, stating:

Because while I am Mr. big show-off on stage, he knows no fear. I’m quite the introvert in real life. ... I do that through my music and yeah, I’ll say probably through a mask of music. ... When I’m on stage, I am definitely a persona. (Aaron)

For Aaron, performance provided safety, allowing him to share vulnerable experiences while concealing them beneath his stage persona. He highlighted the anonymity that performance can bring, sharing:

You can take your most personal issue into a crowd of 2,000 people and rap at the top of your voice, and nobody knows what you’re talking about. You’re just

exposing everything about your troubled childhood, and they have no idea.
(Aaron)

This illustrates how rap can function as a performative tool that mediates vulnerability, enabling participants to articulate deeply personal experiences while maintaining psychological distance. The audience acts as an emotional buffer, allowing disclosure without direct exposure.

Similarly, Samuel described rap as a “surrogate voice” that allows him to express thoughts that might otherwise remain unspoken.

Participants described how they regulated disclosure in their rap lyrics. Chris shared how concerns about reputation and cultural stigma influenced his rap. Discussing topics that he considered as sensitive, including suicidality and LGBTQ+, he reflected “I talk about things the Black man enjoys, like music, football. But I don’t like talking about LGBTQ because it’s not culturally acceptable.” This highlights the tension between expressing emotional truths and protecting one’s social image and reflects how wider social and cultural factors within Black communities impacts disclosure in rap.

Jordan also reflected on this tension, expressing caution about how his lyrics might affect others: “Anything seriously deep I don’t need to put in the music ‘cause sometimes things are a bit too personal, and especially if you’re talking about things like let’s say my ex or whatever then that’s her business, too.” Kieran similarly expressed a preference for abstract writing, explaining “I always want to do it in an abstract kind of way. ... I don’t like to mention my family members.” This highlights an ethical consideration in their creative process, avoiding disclosures that could harm relationships.

Participants described how their approach to vulnerability and emotional openness evolved over time. Leon reflected on his journey, sharing how he avoided seeking help in his youth, believing he could manage alone: “I was angry at the world. I felt that the world owed me something ... I wouldn’t have gone to the systems, but now I know they can help.” He reflected on how age and maturity changed his perspective, sharing “Now I’d reach out to people, but now I’m aware of... I’m just older and more

mature.” Similarly, Elijah noted that he only became comfortable talking about personal issues in his twenties, stating “I got to 23 years old before I became willing to talk about things.” Samuel further reflected on the value of maturity in understanding himself: “It was like a puzzle, you’re figuring yourself out and it’s a never-ending puzzle because as you grow, you get more experiences, or you look at the same experiences but differently. That’s the value maturity brings.” This suggests that the journey toward vulnerability and openness is not static but evolves with time and personal growth.

3.6. Theme 3: Rap as Connection, Validation, and Social Influence

This theme explores how rap can foster connections to others and cultural heritage, considers the influence of Black male representation in encouraging emotional openness through rap, and examines its potential role as a tool for support and raising awareness.

3.6.1. Connection and Culture: “It’s That Togetherness”

This sub-theme captures how participants’ engagement with rap can foster interpersonal and cultural connection, a sense of understanding, and as a bridge to conversations with others.

Many participants reflected on rap’s ability to connect them with others: “it’s that togetherness” (Elijah). Kieran described rap as foundational to forming his friendships, sharing “pretty much every friendship group I’ve got has been through music... through rap.” This demonstrates rap’s capacity to unite people around shared creative interests. Leon reflected on his experiences of organising post-COVID hip-hop events aiming to help with isolation; he highlighted a “real community feeling in UK hip-hop”, suggesting how hip-hop culture can provide social connection during times of emotional difficulty and challenge.

Jordan observed that sharing emotional content through rap allowed listeners to feel a sense of solidarity: “everybody’s going to be like, oh, this is so sick... Thank you for putting this out. I felt the same way. Now I’m not going through it alone.” Michael similarly described how his rap lyrics created indirect but meaningful connections with others. He reported that when he shared his lyrics with his brother, who then passed them onto others, he felt as though he was actively “building a community or

linkage to people. Even when it's not me doing it directly... you know that you're affecting lives." This suggests that rap can foster a wide emotional impact and sense of interconnectedness.

Participants reflected on how rap acts as a way to foster connection and understanding among individuals from varied cultural and socioeconomic backgrounds. Daniel highlighted how his music, although rooted in Black experiences, can resonate widely: "Anybody can listen to the music, Indians, the Whites, the Koreans, the Japanese, the Chinese, the Caribbeans... It will be in line with what people are facing in real life." Similarly, Leon observed rap's inclusive appeal beyond individuals from working-class backgrounds, describing it as inherently "inviting" and capable of capturing "every class of people."

Rap was described as a tool of communication, offering ways to foster shared understanding and relatability. Chris reflected on rap's power in enabling others to see past superficial impressions of him: "Some people might assume that you're emotionless because you never show emotions, but when people read your pieces... They understand your lows, your highs, people understand you better." He described writing lyrics to articulate his own and others' experiences, creating a mutual emotional connection: "I do that to comfort my own experience. Just to say that I'm not alone also." Elijah further reflected on how rap has allowed for empathetic understanding; he spoke about the concept of "verstehen", the attempt to view experiences through another's eyes: "You're explaining the world through their eyes that they're afraid to explain to themselves, but you're making it more relatable." He highlighted the importance of this among men: "Especially if it's a guy, it's something that most people can relate to." This suggests that rap can serve as a reciprocal form of emotional validation, fostering a mutual sense of comfort and understanding between artist and listener.

Participants spoke about rap's ability to facilitate conversations about personal difficulties. Leon described how his lyrical style evolved to become emotionally transparent, making it easier to initiate conversations about mental health. Through his music, he could share feelings that would otherwise remain unspoken: "Expressing my feelings in music helped me say things I wouldn't have been able to say in person." Leon also highlighted the subtle yet impactful way rap lyrics can hint

at emotional struggles, noting how even “one line in a song can subtly allude to stress” which opens up discussions by “admitting to every listener that you've struggled.” Similarly, Kieran discussed how his rap lyrics became entry points for conversations around his experiences as a mixed-race man. Explaining his lyrics to others prompted meaningful discussions, particularly recalling dialogues with a close friend who shared a similar identity.

Kieran described how his abstract lyricism acted as a conversational bridge, stating that listeners would often derive personal meanings that prompted discussions about shared experiences: “Sometimes when people ask me ‘what do you mean by that?’ I'll go, ‘Oh, what did I mean by that?’ But a lot of the time it's kind of like I'll have a lot of different hidden meanings.” Elijah also emphasised rap’s potential to facilitate conversations indirectly: “If you say certain things to your partner or something, they may not get it. But if you send a poem...that’s another entry point.” This highlights the practical advantage of rap and other forms of creative expression as a useful way to communicate with others indirectly.

Participants described their experiences with rap within a broader historical and cultural context, recognising its roots in Black expression and as a way to connect to their cultural heritage. Kieran emphasised rap as “one of, if not the rawest form of expression musically” and Jordan spoke about rap as a historical form of Black musical resilience and unity: “You gotta think there were all them slavery chants... banging pots and tins... it’s embedded in the culture. Like the music’s in you regardless.”

Elijah described a sense of pride and emotional connection derived from being part of the cultural legacy of rap music, sharing: “It feels good when this thing is still here... that’s been given to us by technically speaking, our forefathers.” He highlighted rap as a meaningful opportunity to connect with his culture, reinforcing a powerful sense of community rooted in shared history and identity:

Sometimes it’s the opportunity to be able to connect with, I guess where a long line of you and the people have come from. ... So that’s a feel good moment as well for me.... It’s that feeling of using something that has so much history behind it. (Elijah)

3.6.2. Representation: “When You See It More, It Reaffirms You’re Not Alone”

This sub-theme explores how representation in rap can provide validation and encouragement for emotional expression and openness among participants.

Participants emphasised how representation in rap validates their emotional experiences and encourages emotional openness. Witnessing Black male artists publicly express vulnerability reassured participants that emotional authenticity was acceptable and empowering: “When you see it more, it reaffirms that you're not alone.” (Elijah)

Elijah reflected on seeing friends and family have a “willingness to express themselves” through rap growing up, and how this influenced him to start freestyling about his experiences. Reece similarly highlighted how: “from a Black male perspective... when you’re seeing other Black males, you’re looking up to them and then you're hearing them be open, it reaffirms that you can be open as well.” He also shared: “Like Future for example, everyone says, yeah, toxic king, all of that. But some of the stuff he's talking about is deep stuff ... the way you can relate to it is different.” This suggests that relatable rappers can normalise emotional expression and reduce the stigma of expressing vulnerability among Black men.

Aaron recalled the impact of experiencing representation, particularly through artists like Public Enemy, whose political music provided a sense of belonging and identity affirmation during isolated experiences of growing up in a predominantly White area. Other participants described how contemporary rappers’ openness about topics traditionally stigmatised within Black communities, such as sexuality, empowered them to embrace their own identities. Kieran specifically highlighted the influence of bisexual rap artists on his journey toward greater self-expression:

When Frank Ocean came out as bi and everyone was like, oh, I don't know, then they was like, oh, no, it doesn't matter. ... Tyler The Creator ... now he's come out as bi and as a queer person myself who's bisexual ... and mixed race, hearing these things come out in this generation, it's helped me to express myself (Kieran)

Participants also highlighted how seeing rappers perceived as tough express vulnerability provided reassurance that emotional openness was acceptable, even

within traditional ideals of masculinity: “You could see people that are that hardened, you know, hardened criminal. You could see someone who’s a mass murderer. You can see the hardest of people bring themselves down to a level because it’s on rap.” (Elijah). The visibility of vulnerability in rap appears to make emotional expression feel safer and more attainable, potentially reducing barriers related to masculinity and emotional openness.

Kieran emphasised the pressures faced by Black and mixed-race individuals who “have to represent a lot harder”, sometimes leading to “toxic coping mechanisms.” However, Kieran identified a generational shift, where increased representation of emotional authenticity and vulnerability in rap has influenced meaningful conversations within families and communities. He shared: “I’ve talked to friends of mine that are mixed race or are Black, Hispanic, or Indian, and they have only just recently had conversations with their dads... realising the older generation had it so hard.” For Kieran, rap offered a valuable space to “bridge the gap between generations” and normalise mental health conversations within Black communities.

3.6.3. Mutual Support and Impact: “You Might Plant the Seed”

This sub-theme explores how rap can play a role in facilitating mutual support and encouragement between the artist and listener, and can be an impactful tool for learning and raising awareness.

Participants described the impact of receiving positive listener and audience responses to their music. Michael expressed how his friends’ appreciation validated his creative efforts, encouraging him to continue making rap. Reece highlighted the pride and affirmation experienced when sharing emotionally resonant songs: “the sense of pride is unmatched.” Aaron reflected on the empowering feeling of recognition and validation he experiences during performances:

It’s the place that I feel most comfortable in the whole world. ... And for so much of your life, when you don’t matter, or you’re just another number, or you’re just another person ... you or your crew are the most important people in in the room
(Aaron)

Kieran emphasised the emotional validation and sense of enjoyment achieved through performance, stating, “when I see them rock with it... I can use this as a medicine for myself and for them ... I wouldn’t trade it for the world. I don’t ever want to retire from this.”

Many participants described rap as being able to provide support and encouragement within their personal relationships and wider communities. Aaron articulated this idea through the metaphor of abstract art, explaining “If there are people listening to my work, I want it to be the piece of art that keeps giving... From that piece of abstract art, you take what you take from it as the viewer.” Aaron’s perspective suggests that rap can act as a reflective canvas, offering listeners the ability to take personal meaning from his lyrics which they may benefit from.

Participants articulated how they use rap to positively influence others and help them overcome personal challenges. Leon shared “I’ve had people message me to say they were suicidal and they’re listening to my music and it helped them get through.”. Similarly, Daniel reported: “Sometimes I create lyrics to motivate people... maybe people are going through illnesses... heartbreaks... lyrics that motivate those people and help them to move on.”

Elijah described intimate interactions like “drive and chill” where he uses rap to create supportive and safe spaces for his friends that are experiencing distress: “Come on, we’re going for a drive... now we’re gonna freestyle.” This highlights the potential trust that rap can cultivate, providing emotional release and comfort through shared creativity. Elijah also encourages personal experimentation with rap, advocating for his loved ones to engage in writing to help them overcome difficulties: “Have you ever tried writing it down?... Doesn’t need to be the best thing in the world... just for you.”

Leon recalled an experience delivering a rap workshop in a prison, observing its power supporting an isolated prisoner:

We did the [rap] workshop... it’s the first time he’d left his cell apart from food and dinner... he got on the mic... We didn’t address his issues... but just getting him out of his shell... his love for the music got him out. (Leon)

Participants emphasised the role rap can play in positively impacting listeners, promoting social awareness and facilitating opportunities for learning and critical reflection. Leon highlighted rap's educational potential: "There's some wicked businessmen in hip-hop... you can listen to them, and they probably give you some advice on investing or something." Chris echoed this, describing rap as an avenue to gain insights into diverse experiences and cultures: "You can learn a lot about other people... it's something where you can explore other people."

Samuel reflected on rap's ability to make every day struggles visible, recalling his surprise at hearing Ice Cube address topics such as unemployment and subsequently recognising his own potential to rap about his lived experiences:

I was really surprised when Ice Cube was rapping about trying to get a job... that's a reality for a lot of people... There's so much more I can rap about now, about trying to be a diligent father. ... I understand Bashy's music; he's talking about mortgages. (Samuel)

Participants also described how rap could spark curiosity and critical reflection. Aaron shared instances where listeners returned to him years later to discuss lyrics that had sparked their interest or changed their perspective. This suggests that rap can serve as a powerful catalyst for ongoing exploration and learning:

People telling me that they've got stuff out of my lyrics, people that have learned stuff or been sparked to go on and investigate stuff... 10-12 years later coming to me and saying, you know, when you said that on that tune, what were you talking about? (Aaron)

Participants recognised rap's potential to provoke societal awareness and dialogue. Leon reflected on rap's relationship with social consciousness, noting that although heightened awareness could lead to uncomfortable realisations, rap was crucial in exposing important realities: "There's a lot addressed in hip-hop ... borderline conspiracy theory... if these things turn out to be facts, then I think the paranoia maybe should be there... it makes you more aware." Aaron reinforced this perspective, distinguishing rap's role in highlighting societal issues from providing definitive answers: "My job is to make you aware that these issues are there. It's not

to provide the answers.” This positions rap as a way for listeners to engage with and learn about social issues.

Elijah similarly highlighted rap’s power to prompt reflection and debate among listeners, particularly in live performance contexts where audiences were fully engaged:

Sometimes I look out and I’m like, ‘hmm, that’s gonna ruffle some feathers, cool, let’s go for it’... when everyone’s tuned in... you’re just listening. It’s that moment for me that’s the most powerful thing I get out of it. You might plant the seed that sparks so many different debates. (Elijah)

Elijah reflected on using rap to bring attention to issues affecting Black communities, such as racism and discrimination. This suggests that rap can facilitate reflection and dialogue, improve societal awareness and potential shifts in understanding social issues.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Chapter Overview

This chapter critically discusses the findings of the current study in relation to the study's research questions, relevant literature, and theoretical frameworks. A critical review of the study is presented before discussing the implications for research, practice, and policy. The chapter ends with researcher reflections and a conclusion.

4.2. Study Aims and Findings

Existing research, predominantly conducted in the US, suggests that rap and hip-hop can open conversations about mental health and broader social issues (Adeyola & Allen, 2025; Francis, 2018, 2021), as well as have therapeutic benefits (Adeyola & Allen, 2025; Alvarez, 2011; Compton Dickinson & Souflas, 2011; Ierardi & Jenkins, 2011; Jefferson & Ohrt, 2024; Short, 2017). Crucially, Black men are less likely to engage with voluntary mental health services (Darko, 2021; McKeown et al., 2008; Stockwell et al., 2024), meaning that their experiences and perspectives are often underrepresented in both early intervention services and existing research. This study therefore sought to address a critical gap in the literature by exploring how Black men in the UK use rap music to express mental health experiences outside of academic, clinical, or forensic settings.

Three overarching themes developed out of the RTA. The following sections present these findings in relation to the two research questions, namely, how Black men describe the impact of creating rap music on their willingness to talk about mental health and adversity, and what aspects of rap music they identify as influencing their openness and disclosure. These themes are discussed alongside existing literature and theory to contextualise how rap facilitates emotional expression.

4.2.1. 'Rap as Therapy'

The theme 'Rap as Therapy' captures the therapeutic benefits of rap. Participants reported using rap to overcome personal challenges and experience self-expression, catharsis, self-awareness, and reflection. These benefits align with common

processes in psychological therapy, including emotional processing, self-reflection, and the development of new coping skills. These findings extend previous literature by showing that the benefits of rap for Black men's wellbeing are not limited to listening or structured interventions but can also arise through self-directed creation (Adeyola & Allen, 2025; Alvarez, 2011; Compton Dickinson & Souflas, 2011; Jefferson & Ohrt, 2024; Short, 2017). Participants' experiences also contrast with some research exploring structured rap interventions. Jefferson and Ohrt (2024) investigated a manualised hip-hop and rap lyric intervention with Black undergraduate men in the US, finding that only one participant showed improvement in wellbeing, and the remaining demonstrated minimal or inconsistent effects. While some studies involving structured rap interventions have reported positive outcomes, these mixed results suggest that autonomy and routine personal engagement in rap could be important factors in enhancing psychological benefits.

Participants reported that creating rap lyrics provided a safe outlet for articulating personal challenges, including mental health, trauma, loss, and broader socio-political issues affecting Black communities. The process of lyrical creation was described as cathartic, allowing the expression of emotions and experiences that might otherwise remain unspoken or be managed through maladaptive coping strategies. These findings build on research by Adeyola and Allen (2024), who found that listening to hip-hop lyrics facilitated open discussions among Black men in the US, on topics relating to anger, depression, identity, and social issues such as racism. Additionally, the results support research demonstrating that rap-based interventions help Black men to articulate experiences of adversity (Alvarez, 2011; Ierardi & Jenkins, 2011; Short, 2017).

A novel contribution of this study is that participants used rap in everyday coping, rather than within structured clinical, forensic, or educational interventions, demonstrating its role as an accessible tool for emotional expression. This aligns with broader literature on expressive writing; writing about difficult experiences has been shown to facilitate emotional disclosure, cognitive reappraisal, and improvements in psychological health (Pennebaker, 1997). Similarly, creative practices can support stress reduction and emotion regulation (Stuckey & Nobel, 2010; Slayton et al., 2010). Neuroscience research further demonstrates that music

engages brain networks involved in emotional regulation and stress modulation (Koelsch, 2014; Zaatar et al., 2024), which may help to explain why participants experienced rap as therapeutic.

Participants also noted the limitations of rap as a standalone therapeutic strategy. The benefit of external, or professional psychological support was acknowledged, with participants explaining that rap may prevent the full resolution of mental health difficulties due to challenges in solving problems independently. This suggests that the self-directed use of rap may not be able to address difficulties requiring structured intervention or specialised support. This aligns with clinical guidance suggesting that self-guided coping strategies (e.g., self-help books) can be powerful but often require integration into structured psychological therapies (Baguley et al., 2010). Therefore, while rap can provide meaningful psychological benefits, it may be most effective when combined with professional support or delivered within an intervention format such as Rap Therapy (Elligan, 2000).

4.2.2. 'Navigating Vulnerability, Identity, and Stigma Through Rap'

The second theme 'Navigating Vulnerability, Identity, and Stigma Through Rap' illustrates how rap can provide a safe way for participants to navigate barriers to emotional expression, within cultural and societal constraints.

Participants described rap as a preferred avenue for self-expression, with the process of creating lyrics often preceding conversations with others. Vulnerability expressed through rap elicited more positive responses than direct conversations, suggesting that rap can be a socially acceptable medium for expressing vulnerability. Rap offered a "mask" and "shield" through which participants could self-express vulnerability indirectly, particularly relating to stigmatised or sensitive topics such as suicidality and grief. Features of rap, including the use of storytelling, metaphors, live performance, and artistic persona, acted as a creative protective barrier, allowing emotional distance and safety for expression. Rap music also gave participants autonomy over disclosure, allowing them to selectively control their lyrics and what was shared.

The findings suggest that rap can function as a performed identity, allowing participants to express vulnerability through a protective lyrical persona while

maintaining distance. This performative stance enabled emotional sharing, framing disclosure as artistry rather than personal exposure. This aligns with Goffman's (1959) 'frontstage/backstage' framework: the rap persona operated as a controlled 'frontstage' for presenting personal experiences in a socially acceptable format, while the 'backstage' represents a private space for navigating emotions internally. Past studies with Black males found that structured engagement in rap-based interventions can shift lyrical content toward greater vulnerability and emotional openness (Compton Dickinson & Souflas, 2011; Short, 2017). The present study extends these findings by showing that self-initiated rap creation provides a similar protective persona in everyday contexts outside of structured interventions.

Despite rap being a preferred avenue for self-expression, participants described pressures to portray themselves as "tough" and "strong", reflecting dominant masculinity ideals in Black communities. These expectations made vulnerability in rap and other contexts feel risky, unacceptable, and stigmatised, and participants identified concerns relating to being misunderstood, having a damaged reputation, and impacted relationships. These findings build on Adeyola and Allen (2025), who found that Black men suppressed feelings due to masculinity norms. The results are further contextualised by literature on masculinity and help-seeking (Coleman-Kirumba et al., 2023; Graves, 2021; Hammond, 2012; Johnson, 2018; Mantovani et al., 2016; Mattis et al., 2016), which illustrates how cultural constructions of strength constrain emotional openness. The findings suggest that masculinity norms extend beyond daily interactions into artistic practice, with rap providing a controlled space for Black men to express vulnerability while managing expectations of strength.

Further illustrating the complexities of navigating societal judgement, participants described how the safety and acceptability of disclosure through rap could be limited by concerns about confidentiality and stigma, particularly when addressing sensitive topics such as family issues or LGBTQ+ identity. This supports research findings that harmful societal attitudes towards the LGBTQ+ community can restrict openness around lived experiences and identity (Suppes et al., 2021). Therefore, it is important to consider how intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1989) and stigma associated with marginalised identities can influence self-expression through rap.

Participants reflected on the negative impact of being stereotyped through their association with rap and hip-hop culture, often being misunderstood as “gangster” or “violent”, reflecting broader racial biases and discrimination in society and media (Reyna et al., 2009; Scott, 2020). While some participants advocated for more “ethical” rap, others framed rap as an authentic representation of the lived realities of Black communities. This builds on Adeyola and Allen (2025), whereby Black men expressed a desire for changing Black masculinity ideals, more positive and progressive showcasing and reducing stereotypes. Differing perspectives reflect current debates about rap, with genres such as drill being criminalised, arguably silencing artistic expressions of trauma, violence, and marginalisation (Debo-Aina, 2021). Therefore, this study suggests that although rap can offer a safe and culturally acceptable medium for expression for Black men, societal stigma associated with the genre may impact the authenticity of self-expression.

Rap was shown to be a strategy for negotiating vulnerability due to professional mental health support feeling unsafe and inaccessible. Participants highlighted barriers to professional mental health help-seeking, including cultural disconnection, racism, mistrust, stigma, and accessibility and practical issues (e.g., cost). Participants also described a fear of being pathologized, misunderstood, punished, or sectioned under the Mental Health Act, which reflects widely documented experiences of Black men being disproportionately sectioned and imprisoned (Angiolini, 2017; Stockwell et al., 2024). This also builds on past literature which found that stigma, lack of cultural representation, and mistrust impacts Black men’s engagement with mental health care (Boydell et al., 2011; Earl et al., 2011; Kapadia et al., 2022; Keating et al., 2002; Meechan, 2021; Memon et al., 2016). These barriers increased reliance on rap as a coping strategy, suggesting that everyday self-directed engagement in rap can act as an accessible alternative to traditional mental health support, extending previous research on structured interventions.

4.2.3. ‘Rap as Connection, Validation, and Social Influence’

The third theme, ‘Rap as Connection, Validation, and Social Influence’, further highlights the social and cultural dynamics that influence emotional openness in rap. These findings extend prior work by showing that rap can foster connection, validation, and social influence even outside structured therapeutic interventions,

highlighting the potential of everyday, self-directed engagement with rap (Adeyola & Allen, 2025; Alvarez, 2011; Short, 2017).

Rap was shown to have utility as a tool for fostering both interpersonal connection and indirect connection to wider communities through the sharing of music. Participants described how rap lyrics reflecting lived experiences created a platform for shared understanding and relatability across different cultural and social backgrounds. This facilitated emotional expression through direct conversations (e.g., openly discussing personal experiences) and more indirect forms (e.g., discussing abstract lyrical content). Additionally, participants described how rap connected them to their heritage as a genre rooted in Black cultural resistance. They also referred to rap as an “authentic” genre, where expressing vulnerability is accepted and encouraged. This highlights the accessibility and relevance of the everyday use of rap as a medium for emotional disclosure and connection with others.

Participants described how witnessing Black male representation in rap validated their own lived experiences, encouraging greater self-expression and emotional disclosure. They highlighted how artists who openly showed lyrical vulnerability helped to challenge societal norms around emotional suppression and made the expression of vulnerability feel acceptable. Research has shown that parasocial figures, public figures with whom individuals form one-sided connections to, can promote healthy attitudes and behaviours, reduce stigma around mental health, enhance emotional coping, foster identity exploration, and provide a sense of community (Hoffner & Bond, 2022). Therefore, the current findings suggest that authentic, emotionally open Black male rappers may reinforce adaptive approaches to vulnerability and mental health disclosure in everyday contexts. This is consistent with research findings that Black male artists’ openness about mental health positively influenced Black men’s willingness to seek information and engage in online discussions about their own wellbeing (Francis, 2018, 2021). Additionally, Black men have reported that listening to artists who were transparent about mental health provided validation and representation and facilitated healthy discussions about accessing community support (Adeyola & Allen, 2025).

Participants in this study spoke about how the increasing visibility of gay and bisexual Black male rappers influenced the authentic self-expression about their own identity, therefore challenging conventional norms and stigma within hip-hop culture and Black communities. This aligns with findings from Adeyola and Allen (2025), where Black men expressed a desire to re-define Black masculinity, and the necessity of positive and progressive role models in rap. Other research highlights a growing trend among rappers toward positive mental health discussions and more open reflections about emotional experiences (Hart, 2019; Kresovich et al., 2020; Sule & Inkster, 2020). These findings further demonstrate that everyday engagement with rap can provide socially supportive, culturally meaningful ways to challenge traditional masculinity norms and foster emotional openness.

Participants described how they used rap not only for personal expression but also as a means of supporting others, both directly (e.g., encouraging friends to self-express through rap) and indirectly (e.g., releasing lyrics as a form of advice or motivation). Using rap as a supportive tool was reported to generate feelings of pride and fulfilment and strengthened social bonds. This supports research which found that rap-based interventions led to a sense of accomplishment and pride (Ierardi & Jenkins, 2011), and belonging and mutual encouragement (Alvarez, 2011) among Black men. These findings suggest that the everyday use of rap can function as an informal, culturally resonant support system for Black men, aligning with previous research highlighting the importance of culturally trustworthy networks within Black communities (Mantovani et al., 2016; Watkins & Neighbors, 2007).

Participants emphasised rap's ability to facilitate social commentary and awareness, demonstrating its educational role in highlighting issues such as racism, discrimination, and inequality. This may have provided an indirect way to express personal struggles while situating it within the context of broader issues affecting Black communities. This points to hip-hop's capacity for community resistance and empowerment through increasing social awareness (Kubrin, 2007; Wells, 2019). Together, these findings highlight the role of rap in everyday practice as an informal, culturally resonant support system that extends traditional peer networks, acting as a shared resource for coping and collective resilience.

4.2.4. Theoretical Relevance

Situating the study's findings within theory offers further insights into how rap music shapes Black men's emotional expression.

The findings align with the IBM-HS (Hammer et al., 2024), which conceptualises help-seeking as a dynamic process influenced by the interaction between individual, structural, and cultural factors (see Appendix A). The barriers described by participants, including systemic mistrust, stigma, and lack of culturally relevant care, reflect the determinants described within the IBM-HS, such as structural inequalities (e.g., racism, lack of accessible services) and cultural pressures (e.g., masculinity norms, stigma). These determinants appeared to shape participants' beliefs around the anticipated outcomes of emotional disclosure, influencing their reluctance to seek formal mental health support directly.

Rap music emerged as a mechanism that positively influenced participants' attitudes towards emotional disclosure, reinforced perceived social norms about vulnerability within a culturally validated context, and enhanced their personal agency by empowering them through creative expression. In line with IBM-HS's mechanisms (attitude, perceived norm, and personal agency), rap appeared to facilitate greater intention towards help-seeking behaviours by providing a culturally acceptable form of self-expression and connection with others. However, consistent with the IBM-HS, despite strong intentions fostered through expression in rap, participants identified structural barriers that continued to impact engagement with formal mental health support, highlighting the need for broader systemic change.

The study's findings can also be explained by psychological and social theories underpinning existing rap interventions (Rap Therapy, Elligan, 2000; Hip-Hop Therapy, Tyson, 2002; Hip-Hop and Spoken Word Therapy, Levy, 2012). CBT emphasises self-reflection, emotional processing, and identifying cognitive distortions that can impact mental health (Beck, 1976). Participants reported that rap allowed them to discuss mental health difficulties, self-reflect, gain awareness, and overcome personal challenges, therefore functioning similarly to therapeutic processes in CBT. SLT posits that behaviours are learned through observing others (Bandura, 1977). Participants described how they connected with rap artists who openly expressed vulnerability, therefore modelling new ways of engaging with

emotional expression. This mirrors the influence of role models in SLT, where the visibility of Black male artists discussing mental health challenges served to normalise vulnerability and redefine masculinity for participants.

The findings can be further situated within cultural and liberation psychology (Martín-Baró, 1994; Comas-Díaz, 2007). Participants' use of rap, a genre rooted in Black cultural resistance and resilience, demonstrated how cultural tools can facilitate emotional disclosure in ways that traditional, Westernised therapeutic models often fail to. Participants' narratives of using rap to critique racism, advocate for social change, and reclaim agency over their stories reflect liberation psychology's emphasis on transforming oppressive realities through collective voice and action. Additionally, the intersecting influences of race, male gender, and other identities, captured through an intersectional lens (Crenshaw, 1989), demonstrate how inequalities related to identities act as both barriers and facilitators to emotional disclosure.

4.3. Critical Review

This section provides a critical review of the current study, drawing on Yardley's (2015) evaluative criteria for qualitative research: sensitivity to context, commitment and rigour, coherence and transparency, and impact and importance. This section also considers the key limitations of the research.

4.3.1. Sensitivity to Context

Sensitivity to context refers to the researcher's attentiveness to contextual factors that shape the research process, data, and interpretation (Yardley, 2015). This research was conducted with sensitivity to the historical, socio-political and cultural context surrounding Black men's mental health and the use of rap as a form of self-expression. The introduction discusses empirical and theoretical literature, positioned within broader discourses of systemic and racial inequality, as well as cultural, gender, and societal factors.

Sensitivity to context was also demonstrated through reflexivity in the research process. This included engaging in critical reflection of my positionality as a researcher. Reflexive journaling and supervision were used to reflect on potential

biases and ensure ethical engagement with participants and their narratives. Consideration of the researcher's relationship to the topic and to the communities represented, is included in the methods and discussion as part of a commitment to transparency.

4.3.2. Commitment and Rigour

Commitment and rigour in qualitative research refer to the researcher's engagement with the topic, data, and participants, as well as the methodological care taken throughout the research process (Yardley, 2015). Commitment was demonstrated through sustained engagement with literature on the topic of Black men's mental health and rap music, informed by an academic and personal interest. Furthermore, the semi-structured interviews allowed for flexibility, allowing participants to shape the conversations and prioritise their narratives.

Rigour was upheld through reflexive engagement and methodological transparency. RTA was conducted following steps outlined by Braun and Clarke (2021a), with consideration of quality assurance (Braun & Clarke, 2021b), outlined in the methods section. As a reflexive researcher, I played an active and interpretative role in the analysis, approaching the data with sensitivity to my own positionality. Rather than seeking coding consensus or reliability, themes were developed through iterative, creative, and interpretive engagement with the data. This process involved constructing themes as meaning-based, interpretative stories that captured emotional, cultural, and social meanings behind participants' accounts. Throughout the analysis, I reflected on how my own experiences and assumptions shaped the analytic lens and questions I brought to the data. Coding was conducted inductively, and participant themes were reviewed and refined through engagement with the dataset, focusing on coherence, nuance, and depth. Data extracts were selected for their illustrative clarity, to centre participant voices, and to reflect the range and diversity of experiences shared.

4.3.3. Coherence and Transparency

Coherence and transparency refer to the clarity, consistency, and logic of the research narrative, as well as the openness with which the research process is described (Yardley, 2015).

Coherence was achieved through application of a critical realist epistemology, which underpinned the research design and analytical approach. This philosophical stance informed the choice of RTA, which aimed to identify underlying patterns in participants' accounts, while also acknowledging the role of broader social and cultural factors.

Transparency was supported through detailed documentation of the research process and analysis. To further enhance transparency, an example of coded interview data is included in Appendix K, and excerpts from the researcher's reflexive journal are presented in Appendix L to demonstrate ongoing critical engagement and reflexivity. The discussion of the study's limitations contributes to transparency by acknowledging the constraints of the research.

4.3.4. Impact and Importance

This study met its aim of exploring how rap music influences Black men's willingness to talk about mental health and adversity and identifying factors that impact emotional disclosure. By centring the voices of Black men in the UK, an underrepresented group in both mental health research and practice, the study provides an understanding of the social, cultural, and structural factors that shape engagement with emotional expression through rap.

The findings highlight how rap can offer therapeutic benefits, a safe outlet for navigating stigma and societal pressures, and foster social connection and support. To the author's knowledge, this is the first qualitative study in the UK to explore Black men's use of rap as a form of emotional expression. As such, the study offers novel contributions to research, practice, and policy.

4.3.5. Limitations

While this study offers valuable insights, several limitations must be acknowledged to critically contextualise the findings.

This study met its recruitment aims, with the final sample size aligning with Braun and Clarke's (2013) recommendations for qualitative research. However, the perspectives captured may not fully reflect the breadth of experiences among Black

men who create rap in the UK. While the study sought to explore diverse viewpoints, there are important limitations regarding representativeness.

Participants were primarily recruited through social media and community networks, which may have led to a self-selecting sample of men who already use rap as a form of emotional expression or who were more comfortable speaking about mental health. Therefore, Black men who use rap more privately, do not associate it with emotional expression, or feel greater stigma or ambivalence around mental health expression may have been underrepresented. Furthermore, the sample did not include participants under age 24, which limits insight into how adolescents or emerging adults engage with rap music as a form of self-expression. This is a notable limitation, as young people face distinct mental health challenges and barriers to help-seeking (Hendrickx et al., 2020) and may relate to rap differently.

The sample did not appear to include Black men who are often described as 'harder to reach', such as those with lived experience of the criminal justice system, individuals involved in gang-related activity, or those engaging with more heavily stigmatised subgenres like drill. These groups may use rap as a crucial medium for expressing psychological distress, particularly in the face of systemic exclusion, racialised policing, and socioeconomic disadvantage (Debo-Aina, 2021; Hall et al., 2022; Moore et al., 2025; Rosen & Cruz, 2018). Additionally, they are significantly underrepresented in research and mental health practice, due to institutional mistrust, surveillance, and lack of culturally safe engagement strategies (Canada et al., 2022; Debo-Aina, 2021; Solbakken et al., 2024). Their absence in this study highlights a critical gap, as including their perspectives could further demonstrate the ways in which rap is used among marginalised populations to navigate mental health.

In designing the study, an inclusive recruitment approach was adopted, with minimal exclusion criteria, to capture a range of experiences from men who may or may not be engaged with mental health services. This was due to existing research on rap-based interventions being conducted within secure, clinical, or academic contexts (Adeyola & Allen, 2025; Alvarez, 2011; Compton Dickinson & Souflas, 2011; Ierardi & Jenkins, 2011; Jefferson & Ohrt, 2024; Short, 2017), therefore limiting its generalisability. However, no explicit questions were asked about participants'

current wellbeing, mental health histories, or engagement with services. As such, it is difficult to determine the extent to which the sample included individuals with experiences of mental health difficulties or engagement with services. Nevertheless, participants openly discussed their relationships with therapy, their ambivalence about mental health support, and their reasons for disengaging, suggesting that the sample did reflect a variety of experiences across the help-seeking spectrum.

Although the research was grounded in a critical realist epistemology, it is important to recognise that the findings are interpretative and shaped by the researcher's positionality. Reflexive practices were used to examine assumptions and power dynamics, however the researcher's own experiences and relationship to the topic inevitably influenced the analytic process. This may have shaped the emphasis placed on certain narratives over others.

4.4. Implications and Recommendations

The findings of this study offer important implications for research, practice, and policy in relation to improving mental health support for Black men in the UK.

4.4.1. Research

Building on gaps in the literature, this study demonstrates the value of capturing the lived experiences of Black men using qualitative methods and makes several novel contributions. By moving beyond dominant Westernised models of mental health, often framed around clinical, medicalised, and problem-focused approaches, the findings suggest that self-directed rap creation can provide therapeutic benefits, facilitate vulnerability, and foster social and cultural connection. Unlike prior research which focuses on listening to rap or structured rap interventions (Adeyola & Allen, 2025; Alvarez, 2011; Compton Dickinson & Souflas, 2011; Ierardi & Jenkins, 2011; Jefferson & Ohrt, 2024; Short, 2017), the findings highlight how the act of creating rap independently can offer many emotional, social and cultural benefits. This is the first study to examine every day, self-directed rap engagement among Black men in the UK, and captures how masculinity norms, racial stereotyping, and marginalised identities shape self-expression in rap. These findings suggest that self-directed creative engagement with rap can be a valuable avenue for exploring culturally

grounded mental health practices that are often overlooked in standard clinical approaches.

The findings highlight several broader directions for future research, which could include more diverse and marginalised populations, including other racialised backgrounds, adolescents, drill artists, non-English speakers, individuals with limited access to technology or those with current or prior involvement with the criminal justice system. These groups face unique barriers to engaging with traditional mental health services (Debo-Aina, 2021; Hendrickx et al., 2020; Middle & Welch, 2022; Pandey et al., 2021; Rebbapragada et al., 2021), which may influence how they relate to rap as a tool for self-expression. A small number of UK-based studies have demonstrated mental health benefits of rap interventions among prisoners and other marginalised groups (Dickens & Lonie, 2012; Compton Dickinson & Souflas, 2011; Short, 2014). However, further research is needed to explore how different social contexts shaped by marginalisation can influence how rap is created. Given the stigmatisation of rap subgenres like drill, future research could explore how young Black men use drill to express lived experiences, navigate vulnerability and resist dominant social narratives. This could help challenge stigmatising stereotypes and offer a more nuanced understanding of drill as a form of self-expression.

Additional research could explore questions such as which aspects of rap (e.g., lyric writing versus performance) most meaningfully facilitate emotional disclosure and other therapeutic benefits, or how engagement with rap compares with other creative practices in supporting mental health. Longitudinal and mixed-methods designs would allow investigation of the sustainability of benefits from creating rap and provide comparisons with conventional psychological therapies, such as CBT. In addition, examining engagement with other culturally relevant art practices may expand understanding of alternative tools for emotional expression. Collaborating closely with Black men and community organisations through co-designed studies is crucial to ensure that research is meaningful and grounded in lived experiences.

4.4.2. Practice

The findings of this study present several important implications for mental health and community practice in the UK. Prior to this study, several rap-based interventions developed in the US demonstrated promising therapeutic benefits (e.g.,

Elligan, 2000; Levy, 2012; Tyson, 2002), yet their application remains limited in the UK. The mental health benefits described by participants in this study further demonstrates the need for investment in UK-specific cultural adaptation of established rap interventions to reflect the British sociocultural context.

The findings of this study extend our understanding by demonstrating how UK-based Black men engage with rap creation as a culturally meaningful means to self-express, navigate vulnerability, and seek social connection in everyday, non-clinical contexts. This direct insight highlights the relevance of preventative and strengths-based approaches to mental health, suggesting that self-directed, routine engagement with rap can act as a powerful preventative strategy, providing a bridge to emotional expression and social connection for a group that is often reluctant to seek traditional support. There is a clear need for services that prioritise early engagement with individuals who may be at risk of mental health difficulties but are unlikely to access formal voluntary support.

Existing community and third sector organisations are well placed to provide preventative mental health care to Black men. The *Shifting the Dial* report provides one example of the benefits of creative, community-led mental health approaches (Centre for Mental Health, 2022). However, community organisations often operate outside of statutory services and are frequently under-resourced and under-invested (UK Grantmaking, 2024). The therapeutic benefits identified by participants suggest that traditional mental health services should build equitable, sustained partnerships with community organisations, recognising their expertise and co-producing culturally relevant interventions (BPS, 2022). However, there is a risk of cultural appropriation when rap practices are incorporated into clinical settings without attention to their roots in resistance, critique and community empowerment. Therefore, any integration of rap into mental health practice must involve genuine community collaboration, shared decision-making and respect for community ownership.

For practitioners working within traditional mental health services, the findings highlight the importance of recognising rap as a legitimate avenue for therapeutic engagement and social connection. Psychological models and clinical practices should remain flexible and inclusive of alternative forms of self-expression. This may require interrogation of dominant psychological frameworks that prioritise talking

therapies. In this context, the role of music therapists is particularly valuable. As trained professionals who facilitate emotional expression and psychological processing through music, they are well-positioned to support the integration of creative approaches into mental health care (Wheeler, 2015).

Another area with increasing relevance is social prescribing, in which healthcare professionals refer individuals to non-clinical services (e.g., community arts, music, exercise) to support wellbeing (Bickerdike et al., 2016). The therapeutic and social benefits of rap identified by participants suggest that self-directed rap creation could be a useful form of social prescribing. Integrating rap into social prescribing pathways via partnerships with music studios, youth centres, or community organisations may offer culturally relevant, low-level entry points into mental health support.

The findings also have important implications for education and youth work. Embedding creative and culturally relevant practices such as rap into school-based mental health promotion initiatives may support earlier identification of distress and promote mental health conversations (Kelly, 2013). Such efforts may align with initiatives to decolonise the school curriculum and make it more inclusive (Begum & Seini, 2019). Incorporating musical expression into early intervention strategies may foster psychologically safe environments in which young Black boys and adolescents feel validated and empowered to articulate their experiences.

This study contributes to understandings about help-seeking processes, particularly when situated within the IBM-HS (Hammer et al., 2024). The findings offer insights into how creative and culturally relevant approaches can impact the various dynamics that influence mental health help-seeking among Black men.

4.4.3. Policy

At a policy level, it is well established that there is a need for broader investment in community-informed, culturally situated mental health interventions. However, despite national calls to improve equity in mental health care (NHS England, 2019), Black men remain underserved.

The Breaking the Circles of Fear report (Keating et al., 2002) highlighted the mutual mistrust between Black communities and mental health services, outlining a cycle in which discrimination, fear, and exclusion prevented Black individuals from accessing appropriate care. Participants described experiences of culturally inaccessible mental health care, suggesting that over two decades later, these 'circles' remain largely unbroken and little systemic progress has been made. Breaking this cycle calls for investment in culturally relevant services, genuine community collaboration, and the adoption of preventative and creative approaches (Black Mental Health and Wellbeing Alliance, 2024; Centre for Mental Health, 2022).

Participants described struggling with a lack of cultural representation in mental health services, therefore highlighting the urgent need to increase the representation of Black professionals to better reflect and serve the communities they support. Alongside this, sustained investment in anti-racist training and accountability structures is essential to ensure that services are culturally safe, accessible, and responsive. Mental health services should consider partnering with cultural influencers, musicians, and community organisations to communicate mental health messaging in ways that genuinely resonate with Black men.

Participants also emphasised the importance of Black male rappers as role models in challenging stigma and modelling emotional openness, suggesting that such figures could play a pivotal role in reshaping narratives around mental health. Integrating these voices into prevention and early intervention strategies could help to normalise help-seeking, reduce stigma, and foster a sense of validation for Black men navigating mental health challenges.

4.5. Researcher Reflections

This research was shaped by my personal and professional connections to issues of identity, race, and cultural expression. I was mindful of how my identity could have influenced how participants engaged with me, as well as my data interpretation.

Growing up as a mixed-race woman in a predominantly White area and working in largely White professional spaces heightened my sensitivity to participants' experiences of marginalisation, belonging, and self-expression through rap. For some participants, particularly those who navigated cultural identity in White spaces,

my background may have created a sense of shared understanding and trust. For others whose upbringing was more racially diverse, it may have created distance, potentially impacting disclosure.

As a woman interviewing men about mental health, gendered norms around masculinity may have shaped disclosure, possibly enabling greater openness for some while prompting self-censorship for others. Although I share certain experiences of racialisation, I am not a Black man, and participants may have adjusted what they shared according to how much they felt I could relate to them.

My background and commitment to culturally responsive care may have led me to overemphasise rap's benefits when analysing the data. I therefore engaged in a reflexive approach to remain critically aware of potential bias. I aimed to maintain a balanced analysis by attending to both the strengths and limitations of rap, as well as incorporating critical perspectives on rap that were shared by participants.

Prior to data collection, I sought feedback from two Black men, both of whom reported finding the interview schedule engaging and appropriate. Although this offered some assurance that the process would be respectful and relevant, I remain aware that more meaningful and sustained involvement of participants and communities is essential in shaping research that truly reflects their experiences.

The aim of this study is not to essentialise cultural expressions or suggest that rap music is a 'one-size-fits-all' solution, nor to exclude or minimise the mental health experiences of individuals from other racial or cultural backgrounds. The research emerged from a personal interest and passion for Black mental health, and a desire to highlight the voices of Black men, voices that are overlooked or marginalised in clinical and research settings.

I was struck by the openness, vulnerability, and insight offered by participants. Their willingness to share deeply personal experiences through the lens of rap was inspiring and reinforced the importance of creating spaces, within and beyond research, where the voices of Black men can be brought to the forefront. I leave this project with improved awareness of the power of music and culture, and the urgent need for more culturally inclusive mental health care.

4.6. Conclusion

This study offers a novel contribution to research on Black men's mental health and rap music, providing further evidence for its therapeutic potential and the need for culturally relevant interventions that build on existing individual and community strengths. Future research, practice, and policy efforts must recognise the value of culturally relevant, creative approaches to mental health, particularly for Black men whose experiences have been marginalised in research and practice. While rap alone may not be a replacement for professional support, it can be a powerful entry point into emotional expression, navigating identity and facilitating social connection. When embedded within culturally responsive services, rap could have the potential to support mental health in ways that are empowering, authentic and accessible for Black men in the UK.

5. REFERENCES

- Abascal, M., Xu, J., & Baldassarri, D. (2021). People use both heterogeneity and minority representation to evaluate diversity. *Science Advances*, 7(11), eabf2507. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abf2507>
- Adams, L., Ni Luanaigh, A., Thomson, D., & Rossiter, H. (2018). *Measuring and reporting on ethnicity and disability pay gaps* (Research Report 117). Equality and Human Rights Commission. <https://www.equalityhumanrights.com/>
- Adeyola, F., & Allen, J. L. (2025). Rap & Relax: A qualitative study exploring Black men's reality of anger, depression and identity using hip-hop based discussions. *Journal of Evidence-Based Social Work*, 22(1), 104–128. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26408066.2024.2441874>
- Ajzen, I. (2020). The theory of planned behavior: Frequently asked questions. *Human behavior and emerging technologies*, 2(4), 314-324. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbe2.195>
- Alvarez III, T. T. (2011). Beats, rhymes, and life: Rap therapy in an urban setting. In S. Hadley & G. Yancy (Eds.), *Therapeutic uses of rap and hip-hop* (pp. 117–120). Taylor & Francis Group.
- Angiolini, E. (2017). *Report of the independent review of deaths and serious incidents in police custody*. <https://www.shekubayohinquiry.scot/sites/default/files/2024-05/SBPI-00496%20-%20Dame%20Elish%20Angiolini%20QC%20report%20of%20the%20independent%20review%20of%20deaths%20and%20serious%20incidents%20in%20police%20custody%20January%202017.pdf>
- Baguley, C., Farrand, P., Hope, R., Leibowitz, J., Lovell, K., Lucock, M., ... & Williams, C. (2010). *Good practice guidance on the use of self-help materials within IAPT services*. Improving Access to Psychological Therapies (IAPT)

Programme.

<https://eprints.hud.ac.uk/id/eprint/9017/1/goodpracticelacock.pdf>

Baker, S., & Homan, S. (2007). Rap, recidivism and the creative self: A popular music programme for young offenders in detention. *Journal of Youth Studies*, 10(4), 459-476. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13676260701262566>

Bandura, A. (1977). *Social learning theory*. Prentice-Hall.

Barker, C., Pistrang, N., & Elliott, R. (2015). *Research methods in clinical psychology: An introduction for students and practitioners*. John Wiley & Sons.

Bearman, M. (2019). Eliciting rich data: A practical approach to writing semi-structured interview schedules. *Focus on Health Professional Education: A Multi-Professional Journal*, 20(3), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.11157/fohpe.v20i3.387>

Bécares, L., Shaw, R., Nazroo, J., Stafford, M., Albor, C., Atkin, K., ... & Pickett, K. (2012). Ethnic density effects on physical morbidity, mortality, and health behaviors: a systematic review of the literature. *American journal of public health*, 102(12), e33-e66. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2012.300832>

Beck, A. T. (1976). *Cognitive therapy and the emotional disorders*. International Universities Press.

Begum, N., & Saini, R. (2019). Decolonising the curriculum. *Political Studies Review*, 17(2), 196-201. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1478929918808459>

Bernardi, L., Porta, C., & Sleight, P. (2006). Cardiovascular, cerebrovascular, and respiratory changes induced by different types of music in musicians and non-musicians: the importance of silence. *Heart*, 92(4), 445-452. <https://doi.org/10.1136/hrt.2005.064600>

Bhaskar, R. (1975). *A realist theory of science*. Leeds Books.

- Bickerdike, L., Booth, A., Wilson, P. M., Farley, K., & Wright, K. (2017). Social prescribing: less rhetoric and more reality. A systematic review of the evidence. *BMJ open*, *7*(4), e013384. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2016-013384>
- Black Mental Health and Wellbeing Alliance. (2024). *Black mental health manifesto*. Black Mental Health and Wellbeing Alliance. <https://www.bmhwa.co.uk/the-manifesto>
- Bleich, S. N., Findling, M. G., Casey, L. S., Blendon, R. J., Benson, J. M., SteelFisher, G. K., ... & Miller, C. (2019). Discrimination in the United States: experiences of Black Americans. *Health Services Research*, *54*(2), 1399-1408. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-6773.13220>
- Blood, A. J., Zatorre, R. J., Bermudez, P., & Evans, A. C. (1999). Emotional responses to pleasant and unpleasant music correlate with activity in paralimbic brain regions. *Nature neuroscience*, *2*(4), 382-387. <https://doi.org/10.1038/7299>
- Bradley, A. (2017). *Book of rhymes: The poetics of hip-hop* (Revised ed.). Basic Civitas Books.
- Bradley, L. (2013). *Sounds like London: 100 years of Black music in the capital*. Serpent's Tail.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2013). *Successful qualitative research: A practical guide for beginners*. SAGE Publications.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2019). Reflecting on reflexive thematic analysis. *Qualitative Research in Sport, Exercise and Health*, *11*(4), 589–597. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2159676X.2019.1628806>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2021a). *Thematic analysis: A practical guide*. SAGE Publications.

- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2021b). One size fits all? What counts as quality practice in (reflexive) thematic analysis? *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 18(3), 328–352. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14780887.2020.1769238>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2023). Toward good practice in thematic analysis: Avoiding common problems and be (com)ing a knowing researcher. *International journal of transgender health*, 24(1), 1-6.
- British Psychological Society. (2021). *BPS code of human research ethics* (4th ed.). The British Psychological Society. <https://www.bps.org.uk/news-and-policy/bps-code-human-research-ethics>
- British Psychological Society. (2022). *Using community psychology approaches to reduce the impact of inequality through the Community Mental Health Framework*. The British Psychological Society. <https://www.bps.org.uk/guideline/using-community-psychology-approaches-reduce-impact-inequality-through-community-mental>
- Burr, V. (2015). *Social constructionism* (3rd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315715421>
- Campbell-Stephens, R. (2020). *Global Majority; Decolonising the language and Reframing the Conversation about Race*. <https://www.leedsbeckett.ac.uk/-/media/files/schools/school-of-education/final-leeds-beckett-1102-global-majority.pdf>
- Canada, K., Barrenger, S., Bohrman, C., Banks, A., & Peketi, P. (2022). Multi-level barriers to prison mental health and physical health care for individuals with mental illnesses. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 13(3), 777124. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2022.777124>
- Centre for Mental Health. (2022). *Shifting the Dial: Evaluating a three-year programme to promote young Black men's mental health and wellbeing*. Centre for Mental Health. https://www.centreformentalhealth.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Shifting-the-Dial_Digital.pdf

- Chanda, M. L., & Levitin, D. J. (2013). The neurochemistry of music. *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 17(4), 179-193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2013.02.007>
- Chang, J. (2005). *Can't stop won't stop: A history of the hip-hop generation*. St. Martin's Press.
- Clearing House for Postgraduate Courses in Clinical Psychology. (2023). *Equal opportunities data for 2023 entry*. <https://www.clearing-house.org.uk/system/files/2024-05/Equal%20opportunities%20data%20for%202023%20entry.pdf>
- Coard, B. (1971). Making black children subnormal in Britain. *Integrated Education: Race and Schools*, 9(5), 49-52. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0020486710090509>
- Coleman-Kirumba, L. M., Cornish, M. A., Horton, A. J., & Alvarez, J. C. (2023). Experiences of Black men: Forms of masculinity and effects on psychological help-seeking variables. *Journal of Black Psychology*, 49(1), 32-57. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0095798422109812>
- Comas-Díaz, L. (2007). Ethnopolitical psychology: Healing and transformation. In E. Aldarondo (Ed.), *Advancing social justice through clinical practice* (pp. 91–118). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Compton Dickinson, S., & Souflas, P. (2011). Rapping round the system: A young Black man's journey through a high-security hospital. In S. Hadley & G. Yancy (Eds.), *Therapeutic uses of rap and hip-hop* (pp. 353–357). Taylor & Francis Group.
- Connell, R. W. (1995). *Masculinities*. University of California Press.
- Cooper, F. R. (2005). Against bipolar Black masculinity: Intersectionality, assimilation, identity performance, and hierarchy. *UC Davis Law Review*, 39(3), 853–906. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228222330_Against_Bipolar_Black_Masculinity_Intersectionality_Assimilation_Identity_Performance_and_Hierarchy

- Crenshaw, K. W. (1989). Demarginalizing the intersection of race and sex: A Black feminist critique of antidiscrimination doctrine, feminist theory, and antiracist politics. *University of Chicago Legal Forum*, 1989(1), 139–167.
<https://chicagounbound.uchicago.edu/uclf/vol1989/iss1/8/>
- Curry, T. J. (2017). *The man-not: Race, class, genre, and the dilemmas of Black manhood*. Temple University Press.
- Curry, T. J. (2018). Killing boogeymen: Phallicism and the misandric mischaracterizations of Black males in theory. *Res Philosophica*, 95(2), 235–272.
- Darko, J. (2021). How can general practice improve the mental health care experience of Black men in the UK? *British Journal of General Practice*, 71(704), 124–125. <https://doi.org/10.3399/bjgp21X715097>
- De Jesús-Romero, R., Holder-Dixon, A. R., Buss, J. F., & Lorenzo-Luaces, L. (2024). Race, ethnicity, and other cultural background factors in trials of internet-based cognitive behavioral therapy for depression: Systematic review. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 26, e50780. <https://doi.org/10.2196/50780>
- Debo-Aina, O. (2021). Silencing the Story of the Streets: An Investigation into How the Media and Political (Mis) Representations of UK Drill Music Affects the Lives and Identities of Black Youth in South London. *Leeds Student Law & Criminal Justice Review*, 1, 136-165.
<https://heinonline.org/HOL/LandingPage?handle=hein.journals/lslcjr1&div=10&id=&page=>
- Department for Communities and Local Government. (2017). *Annual report and accounts 2016-2017*. UK Government.
https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a82c4e6ed915d74e62378af/59955_DCLG_ARA_2017_Web_Accessible.pdf

- Department for Education. (2024). *Permanent exclusions*. <https://www.ethnicity-facts-figures.service.gov.uk/education-skills-and-training/absence-and-exclusions/permanent-exclusions/latest/>
- Department of Health. (1998). *Independent inquiry into inequalities in health report*. The Stationery Office. <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a759e7c40f0b67b3d5c7e6f/i h.pdf>
- Dickens, L., & Lonie, D. (2012). Rap, rhythm and recognition: Lyrical practices and the politics of voice on a community music project for young people experiencing challenging circumstances. *Emotion, Space and Society Music*, 9(1), 59-71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emospa.2012.11.003>
- Dimitriadis, G. (2001). *Performing identity/performing culture: Hip-hop as text, pedagogy, and lived practice*. Peter Lang.
- Doll, C. M., Michel, C., Rosen, M., Osman, N., Schimmelman, B. G., & Schultze-Lutter, F. (2021). Predictors of help-seeking behaviour in people with mental health problems: a 3-year prospective community study. *BMC psychiatry*, 21, 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-021-03435-4>
- Earl, T. R., Alegría, M., Mendieta, F., & Linhart, Y. D. (2011). “Just be straight with me:” An exploration of Black patient experiences in initial mental health encounters. *American Journal of Orthopsychiatry*, 81(4), 519–529. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2016-012337>
- Edge, D., & MacKian, S. C. (2010). Ethnicity and mental health encounters in primary care: help-seeking and help-giving for perinatal depression among Black Caribbean women in the UK. *Ethnicity & Health*, 15(1), 93–111. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13557850903418836>
- Edri, O., & Bensimon, M. (2018). The role of music among prisoners and prison staff: A qualitative research study. *European Journal of Criminology*, 16(6), 633-651. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1477370818775295>

- Elligan, D. (2000). Rap therapy: A culturally sensitive approach to psychotherapy with young African American men. *Journal of African American Men*, 5(3), 27–36. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12111-000-1002-y>
- European Parliament and Council of the European Union. (2016). *General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Regulation (EU) 2016/679)*. Official Journal of the European Union.
- Eyerman, R. (2001). *Cultural Trauma: Slavery and the Formation of African American Identity*. Cambridge University Press.
- Fancourt, D., & Finn, S. (2019). What is the evidence on the role of the arts in improving health and wellbeing? A scoping review. *World Health Organization*.
<https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/329834/9789289054553-eng.pdf>
- Fatsis, L. (2019). Policing the beats: The criminalisation of UK drill and grime music by the London Metropolitan Police. *The Sociological Review*, 67(6), 1300–1316.
- Fernando, S. (2014). *Mental health worldwide: Culture, globalization and development*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Fernando, S. (2017). *Institutional racism in psychiatry and clinical psychology: Race matters in mental health*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Fletcher, A. J. (2017). Applying critical realism in qualitative research: Methodology meets method. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 20(2), 181–194. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645579.2016.1144401>
- Forman, M., & Neal, M. A. (Eds.). (2012). *That's the joint!: The hip-hop studies reader* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- Francis, D. B. (2018). Young Black men's information seeking following celebrity depression disclosure: Implications for mental health communication. *Journal of Health Communication*, 23(7), 687-694.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10810730.2018.1506837>

- Francis, D. B. (2021). "Twitter is really therapeutic at times": Examination of Black men's Twitter conversations following hip-hop artist Kid Cudi's depression disclosure. *Health Communication, 36*(4), 448-456.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10410236.2019.1700436>
- Gaser, C., & Schlaug, G. (2003). Brain structures differ between musicians and non-musicians. *Journal of neuroscience, 23*(27), 9240-9245.
<https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.23-27-09240.2003>
- George, N. (2005). *Hip Hop America*. Penguin Books.
- Gilroy, P. (1982). The myth of black criminality. In M. Eve & D. Musson (Eds.), *The Socialist Register* (pp. 19–19). Merlin Press.
- Goffman, E. (1959). *The presentation of self in everyday life*. Anchor Books.
- Goodfellow, M., & McFarlane, L. (2018). Race and racism in the UK. In L. Macfarlane (Ed.), *New thinking for the British economy* (pp. 150–159). openDemocracy.
- Graves, T. (2021). *Individualism and Collectivism: Well Being Within the African American Community* (Master's thesis, Eastern Kentucky University).
<https://encompass.eku.edu/etd/718/>
- Guest, G., Bunce, A., & Johnson, L. (2006). How Many Interviews Are Enough? An Experiment with Data Saturation and Variability. *Field Methods, 18*(1), 59–82. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1525822X0527990>
- Hall, B., Khan, R., & Eslea, M. (2022). Criminalising Black trauma: grime and drill lyrics as a form of ethnographic data to understand "gangs" and serious youth violence. *Genealogy, 7*(1), 1-18.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/genealogy7010002>
- Hall, W. J., Chapman, M. V., Lee, K. M., Merino, Y. M., Thomas, T. W., Payne, B. K., Eng, E., Day, S. H., & Coyne-Beasley, T. (2015). Implicit Racial/Ethnic Bias Among Health Care Professionals and Its Influence on Health Care

Outcomes: A Systematic Review. *American Journal of Public Health*, 105(12), e60–e76. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2015.302903>

Halpern, D., & Nazroo, J. (2000). The ethnic density effect: results from a national community survey of England and Wales. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 46(1), 34-46. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002076400004600105>

Hammer, J. H., Vogel, D. L., Grzanka, P. R., Kim, N., Keum, B. T., Adams, C., & Wilson, S. A. (2024). The integrated behavioral model of mental health help seeking (IBM-HS): A health services utilization theory of planned behavior for accessing care. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 71(5), 315–327. <https://doi.org/10.1037/cou0000754>

Hammond, W. P. (2012). Taking it like a man: Masculine role norms as moderators of the racial discrimination–depressive symptoms association among African American men. *American Journal of Public Health*, 102(S2), S232–S241. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2011.300485>

Hancox, D. (2013). *Stand up tall: Dizzee Rascal and the birth of grime*. Guardian Shorts.

Hart, R. (2019). Man Down: The Evolution of Masculinity and Mental Health Narratives in Rap Music. *Reinvention: An International Journal of Undergraduate Research*, 12(1), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.31273/reinvention.v12i1.430>

Head, E. (2009). The ethics and implications of paying participants in qualitative research. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 12(4), 335–344. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645570802246724>

Hendrickx, G., De Roeck, V., Maras, A., Dieleman, G., Gerritsen, S., Purper-Ouakil, D., ... & Tremmery, S. (2020). Challenges during the transition from child and adolescent mental health services to adult mental health services. *BJPsych bulletin*, 44(4), 163-168. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjb.2019.85>

HM Government. (2024). *Writing about ethnicity*. Ethnicity Facts and Figures. <https://www.ethnicity-facts-figures.service.gov.uk/>

- Hoffner, C. A., & Bond, B. J. (2022). Parasocial relationships, social media, & well-being. *Current opinion in psychology*, 45, 101306.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2022.101306>
- Home Office. (2019). *Police powers and procedures, England and Wales year ending 31 March 2019*. <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/police-powers-and-procedures-england-and-wales-year-ending-31-march-2019>
- hooks, b. (2004). *We real cool: Black men and masculinity*. Routledge.
- House of Commons Library. (2024a). *Suicide statistics*. UK Parliament.
<https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/cbp-7749/>
- House of Commons Library. (2024b). *UK Prison Population Statistics*. UK Parliament. <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/sn04334/>
- Ierardi, F., & Jenkins, N. (2011). Rap composition and improvisation in a short-term juvenile detention facility. In S. Hadley & G. Yancy (Eds.), *Therapeutic uses of rap and hip-hop* (pp. 253–257). Taylor & Francis Group.
- Jefferson, L., & Ohrt, J. (2024). The effectiveness of a manualized hip-hop and rap intervention on wellbeing among Black emerging adult men: A multiple baseline design. *Journal of Poetry Therapy*, 37(4), 225–239.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/08893675.2023.2269316>
- Jefferson, L., O'Neill, S., & Lomax, C. (2025). Hip-hop and rap music interventions on mental health and wellbeing: A systematic review. *Journal of Creativity in Mental Health*, 19(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15401383.2024.2305294>
- Johnson, B, G. (2018). *The relationship between masculinity and stigma: Predicting help-seeking behaviors in men* [Honors thesis, Georgia Southern University]. <https://digitalcommons.georgiasouthern.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1431&context=honors-theses>
- Johnson, J. L., Oliffe, J. L., Kelly, M. T., Galdas, P. M., & Ogradniczuk, J. S. (2011). Men's discourses of help-seeking in the context of depression. *Sociology of*

Health & Illness, 34(3), 345–361. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9566.2011.01372.x>

Joint Committee on Human Rights. (2020). *Black people, racism and human rights* (HC 559). UK Parliament.
<https://committees.parliament.uk/publications/3376/documents/32359/default/>

Kallio, H., Pietilä, A. M., Johnson, M., & Kangasniemi, M. (2016). Systematic methodological review: Developing a framework for a qualitative semi-structured interview guide. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 72(12), 2954–2965. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.13031>

Kapadia, D., Zhang, J., Salway, S., Nazroo, J., Booth, A., Villarroel-Williams, N., Bécares, L., & Esmail, A. (2022). *Ethnic inequalities in healthcare: A rapid evidence review*. NHS Race and Health Observatory.

Keating, F., Robertson D., Francis E., & McCulloch A. (2002). *Breaking the Circles of Fear: A Review of the relationship between mental health services and African Caribbean communities*. The Sainsbury Centre for Mental Health.
https://www.centreformentalhealth.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/breaking_the_circles_of_fear.pdf

Kelly, L. L. (2013). Hip-hop literature: The politics, poetics, and power of hip-hop in the English classroom. *English Journal*, 102(5), 51-56.
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/24484092?seq=1>

Khan, O. (2020). *The colour of money: How racial inequalities obstruct a fair and resilient economy*. Runnymede Trust.
<https://www.runnymedetrust.org/publications/the-colour-of-money>

King, S., & Torrington, A. (1996). *Birth of the Windrush Generation*. Windrush Foundation.

Kleinman, A. (2004). Culture and Depression. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 351(10), 951–953. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMp048078>

- Kline, R. (2014). *The “snowy White peaks” of the NHS: A survey of discrimination in governance and leadership and the potential impact on patient care in London and England*. London Middlesex University.
<https://doi.org/10.22023/mdx.12640421.v1>
- Kobin, C., & Tyson, E. H. (2006). Thematic analysis of hip-hop music: Can hip-hop in therapy facilitate empathic connections when working with clients in urban settings? *The Arts in Psychotherapy*, 33(4), 343-356.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aip.2006.05.001>
- Koelsch, S. (2014). Brain correlates of music-evoked emotions. *Nature reviews neuroscience*, 15(3), 170-180. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn3666>
- Kresovich, A., Collins, M. K. R., Riffe, D., & Carpentier, F. R. D. (2021). A content analysis of mental health discourse in popular rap music. *JAMA Pediatrics*, 175(3), 286–292. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2020.5155>
- Kubrin, C. E. (2005). Gangstas, thugs, and hustlas: Identity and the code of the street in rap music. *Social Problems*, 52(3), 360–378.
<https://doi.org/10.1525/sp.2005.52.3.360>
- Kubrin, C. E. (2006). I see death around the corner: Nihilism in rap music. *Sociological Perspectives*, 48(4), 433–459.
<https://doi.org/10.1525/sop.2005.48.4.433>
- Kupers, T. A. (2005). Toxic masculinity as a barrier to mental health treatment in prison. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 61(6), 713–724.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/jclp.20105>
- Kurttila, H. (2014). *Brixton 1981–2011: Rioting, newspaper narratives and the effects of a cultural vanguard* (Master's thesis, University of Oulu).
<https://oulurepo.oulu.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/39171/nbnfioulu-201403131174.pdf>
- Lammy, D. (2017). *The Lammy Review: An independent review into the treatment of, and outcomes for, Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic individuals in the*

criminal justice system. UK Government.

<https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a82009040f0b62305b91f49/ammy-review-final-report.pdf>

Leu. (2024). *Music genre preferences in modern America by ethnicity 2018*.

<https://www.statista.com/statistics/864610/music-genre-modern-america-ethnicity/>

Leventhal, H., Phillips, L. A., & Burns, E. (2016). The Common-Sense Model of Self-Regulation (CSM): a dynamic framework for understanding illness self-management. *Journal of behavioral medicine*, 39(6), 935-946.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10865-016-9782-2>

Levitin, D. J. (2006). *This is your brain on music: The science of a human obsession*. Dutton.

Levy, I. (2020). Hip-hop and spoken word therapy in urban school counseling.

Professional School Counseling, 23(1), 1-9.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/2156759X1983443>

Levy, I. P. (2012). Hip-hop and spoken word therapy with urban youth. *Journal of Poetry Therapy*, 25(4), 219-224.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/08893675.2012.736182>

Liddon, L., Kinglerlee, R., & Barry, J. A. (2017). Gender differences in preferences for psychological treatment, coping strategies, and triggers to help-seeking.

British Journal of Clinical Psychology, 56(1), 6–23.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/bjc.12147>

Lipsitz, G. (1994). *Dangerous crossroads: Popular music, postmodernism, and the poetics of place*. Verso.

Love, B. L. (2016). Complex personhood of hip-hop & the sensibilities of the culture that fosters knowledge of self & self-determination. *Equity & Excellence in Education*, 49(4), 414–427.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10665684.2016.1227223>

- Macpherson, W. (1999). *The Stephen Lawrence inquiry: Report of an inquiry by Sir William Macpherson of Cluny*. The Stationery Office.
<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-stephen-lawrence-inquiry>
- Mantovani, N., Pizzolati, M., & Edge, D. (2016). Exploring the relationship between stigma and help-seeking for mental illness in African-descended faith communities in the UK. *Health Expectations*, 20(3), 373–384.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.12464>
- Martín-Baró, I. (1994). *Writings for a Liberation Psychology* (A. Aron & S. Corne, Eds.). Harvard University Press.
- Maxwell, J. A. (2012). *A realist approach for qualitative research*. SAGE Publications.
- McKeown, M., Robertson, S., Habte-Mariam, Z., & Stowell-Smith, M. (2008). Masculinity and emasculation for Black men in modern mental health care. *Ethnicity and Inequalities in Health and Social Care*, 1(1), 42-51.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/17570980200800007>
- McManus, S., Bebbington, P. E., Jenkins, R., & Brugha, T. (2016). *Mental health and wellbeing in England: the adult psychiatric morbidity survey 2014*. NHS Digital.
https://files.digital.nhs.uk/pdf/q/3/mental_health_and_wellbeing_in_england_full_report.pdf
- Meechan, H. (2021). *Understandings of mental health and support for young Black men living in the UK* [Doctoral dissertation, University of Surrey].
<https://openresearch.surrey.ac.uk/esploro/outputs/journalArticle/Understandings-of-mental-health-and-support/99598022002346>
- Memon, A., Taylor, K., Mohebati, L. M., & Sundin, J. (2016). Perceived barriers to accessing mental health services among Black and minority ethnic (BME) communities: a qualitative study in Southeast England. *BMJ Open*, 6(11), e012337. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2016-012337>

- Mental Health Act 1983 (UK). (2018). *UK Government legislation*.
<https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1983/20/contents/enacted>
- Metzl, J. M. (2010). *The protest psychosis: How schizophrenia became a Black disease*. Beacon Press.
- Middle, R., & Welch, L. (2022). Experiences of digital exclusion and the impact on health in people living with severe mental illness. *Frontiers in digital health, 4*, 1004547. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fdgth.2022.1004547>
- Millar, S., Steiner, A., Caló, F., & Teasdale, S. (2020). COOL Music: a 'bottom-up' music intervention for hard-to-reach young people in Scotland. *British Journal of Music Education, 37*(1), 3-17. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1017/S0265051719000226>
- Mincey, K., Alfonso, M. L., Hackney, A., & Luque, J. S. (2014). Being a Black man: Development of the Masculinity Inventory Scale (MIS) for Black men. *Journal of Men's Studies, 22*(3), 167–179. <https://doi.org/10.3149/jms.2203.167>
- Moore, K. E., Stuewig, J. B., & Tangney, J. P. (2016). The effect of stigma on criminal offenders' functioning: A longitudinal mediational model. *Deviant behavior, 37*(2), 196-218. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01639625.2014.1004035>
- Moore, K. L., Lopez, L., Camacho, D., & Munson, M. R. (2020). A qualitative investigation of engagement in mental health services among Black and Hispanic LGB young adults. *Psychiatric Services, 71*(6), 555-561. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ps.201900399>
- Musicians' Union. (2020). *UK music by numbers 2020*.
<https://musiciansunion.org.uk/news/uk-music-by-numbers-2020>
- Neighbors, H. W., Trierweiler, S. J., Ford, B. C., & Muroff, J. R. (2003). Racial differences in DSM diagnosis using a semi-structured instrument: The importance of clinical judgment in the diagnosis of African Americans. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior, 44*(3), 237–256. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1519777>

Nguyen, B. M. D., Alcantar, C. M., Curammeng, E. R., Hernandez, E., Kim, V., Paredes, A. D., ... & Teranishi, R. T. (2017). *The Racial Heterogeneity Project: Implications for educational research, practice, and policy*. ACT, Inc. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED583600.pdf>

NHS Digital. (2020). *Mental Health Act statistics, annual figures: England, 2019-2020*. <https://files.digital.nhs.uk/99/3916C8/ment-heal-act-stat-eng-2019-20-summ-rep%20v1.1.pdf>

NHS England. (2019). *The NHS Long Term Plan*. <https://www.longtermplan.nhs.uk/>

NHS England. (2021). *Patient and Carer Race Equality Framework (PCREF)*. NHS England. <https://www.england.nhs.uk/mental-health/pcref/>

NHS Race and Health Observatory. (2020). *Establishment of the NHS Race and Health Observatory*. NHS Race and Health Observatory. <https://www.nhsrho.org/>

Office for National Statistics. (2020). *Coronavirus (COVID-19) related deaths by ethnic group, England and Wales: 2 March 2020 to 15 May 2020*. <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/birthsdeathsandmarriages/deaths/articles/coronaviruscovid19relateddeathsbyethnicgroupenglandandwales/2march2020to15may2020>

Office for National Statistics. (2022a). *Ethnicity pay gaps in Great Britain: 2012 to 2022*. <https://www.ons.gov.uk/employmentandlabourmarket/peopleinwork/earningsandworkinghours/articles/ethnicitypaygapsingreatbritain/2012to2022#:~:text=In%20the%20UK%20in%202022,has%20been%20consistent%20since%202012>

Office for National Statistics. (2022b). *Ethnic group, England and Wales: Census 2021*. <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/culturalidentity/ethnicity/bulletins/ethnicgroupenglandandwales/census2021>

- Pandey, M., Maina, R. G., Amoyaw, J., Li, Y., Kamrul, R., Michaels, C. R., & Maroof, R. (2021). Impacts of English language proficiency on healthcare access, use, and outcomes among immigrants: a qualitative study. *BMC Health Services Research*, *21*, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-021-06750-4>
- Panksepp, J., & Bernatzky, G. (2002). Emotional sounds and the brain: the neuro-affective foundations of musical appreciation. *Behavioural processes*, *60*(2), 133-155. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0376-6357\(02\)00080-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0376-6357(02)00080-3)
- Paradies, Y., Ben, J., Denson, N., Elias, A., Priest, N., Pieterse, A., ... & Gee, G. (2015). Racism as a determinant of health: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *PloS one*, *10*(9), e0138511. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0138511>
- Patton M. Q. (2002). *Qualitative research & evaluation methods* (3rd ed.). Sage.
- Pennebaker, J. W. (1997). Writing about emotional experiences as a therapeutic process. *Psychological Science*, *8*(3), 162–166. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9280.1997.tb00403.x>
- Peters, M. D. J., Godfrey, C., McInerney, P., Munn, Z., Tricco, A. C., & Khalil, H. (2020). Updated methodological guidance for the conduct of scoping reviews. *JBI Evidence Synthesis*, *18*(10), 2119–2126. <https://doi.org/10.11124/JBIES-20-00167>
- Qassem, T., Bebbington, P., Spiers, N., McManus, S., Jenkins, R., & Dein, S. (2015). Prevalence of psychosis in Black ethnic minorities in Britain: analysis based on three national surveys. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, *50*(7), 1057–1064. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00127-014-0960-7>
- Race Equality Foundation. (2018). *Racial disparities in mental health: Literature and evidence review*. <https://raceequalityfoundation.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/mental-health-report-v5-2.pdf>
- Race Relations Act 1965, c. 73. (1965). UK Parliament. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1965/73/contents>

- Race Relations Act 1968, c. 71. (1968). UK Parliament.
<https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1968/71/contents>
- Race Relations Act 1976, c. 74. (1976). UK Parliament.
<https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1976/74/contents>
- Rebbapragada, N., Furtado, V., & Hawker-Bond, G. W. (2021). Prevalence of mental disorders in prisons in the UK: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BJPsych Open*, 7(S1), S283-S284.
<https://doi.org/10.1192/bjo.2021.755>
- Reddie, A. G. (2020). Racial justice for the Windrush generation in Great Britain. *The Ecumenical Review*, 72(1), 73-86. <https://doi.org/10.1111/erev.12488>
- Revolving Doors Agency. (2020). *Disproportionate Imprisonment of Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic people*. <https://revolving-doors.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Disproportionate-Imprisonment-of-BAME-people-September-2020.pdf>
- Reyna, C., Brandt, M., & Tendayi Viki, G. (2009). Blame it on hip-hop: Anti-rap attitudes as a proxy for prejudice. *Group Processes & Intergroup Relations*, 12(3), 361-380. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1368430209102848>
- Richardson, J. W., & Scott, K. A. (2002). Rap music and its violent progeny: America's culture of violence in context. *Journal of Negro Education*, 71(3), 175-192. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3211235>
- Rose, T. (1994). *Black noise: Rap music and Black culture in contemporary America*. Wesleyan University Press.
- Rosen, J. D., & Cruz, J. M. (2018). Overcoming stigma and discrimination: Challenges for reinsertion of gang members in developing countries. *International journal of offender therapy and comparative criminology*, 62(15), 4758-4775. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306624X18785517>

- Rosenstock, I. M., Strecher, V. J., & Becker, M. H. (1988). Social learning theory and the health belief model. *Health education quarterly*, 15(2), 175-183.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/109019818801500203>
- Rotimi, C. N., Tekola-Ayele, F., Baker, J. L., & Shriner, D. (2016). The African diaspora: history, adaptation and health. *Current opinion in genetics & development*, 41, 77-84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gde.2016.08.005>
- Salimpoor, V. N., Benovoy, M., Larcher, K., Dagher, A., & Zatorre, R. J. (2011). Anatomically distinct dopamine release during anticipation and experience of peak emotion to music. *Nature neuroscience*, 14(2), 257-262.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/nn.2726>
- Schofield, P., Das-Munshi, J., Becares, L., Morgan, C., Bhavsar, V., Hotopf, M., & Hatch, S. L. (2016). Minority status and mental distress: a comparison of group density effects. *Psychological medicine*, 46(14), 3051-3059.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291716001835>
- Scott, C. D. (2020). Policing Black sound: performing UK Grime and Rap music under routinised surveillance. *Soundings*, 75(75), 55-65. <https://doi.org/10.3898/SOUN.75.03.2020>
- Sewell, T., Aderin-Pocock, M., Chughtai, A., Fraser, K., Kakkar, A., Khalid, N., Moyo, D., Muroki, M., Oliver, M., Shah, S., & Olulode, K. (2021). *The report of the Commission on Race and Ethnic Disparities*. UK Government.
<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-report-of-the-commission-on-race-and-ethnic-disparities>
- Shankley, W., & Laurence, J. (2022). Community ethnic density, ethnic segregation, and ethnic minorities' common mental disorders in the UK. *Health & Place*, 73, 102723. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthplace.2021.102723>
- Short, H. (2014). "No Maths, No Physics (So I Spray My Bars with Lyrics)": Rap/Music Therapy with Young Men at a Young Offender Institution. *British Journal of Music Therapy*, 28(1), 25-39.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/135945751402800103>

- Short, H. (2017). "Big up West London crew": One man's journey within a community rap/music therapy group. *Music Therapy Perspectives*, 35(2), 151–159.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/mtp/miw030>
- Slayton, S. C., D'Archer, J., & Kaplan, F. (2010). Outcome studies on the efficacy of art therapy: A review of findings. *Art therapy*, 27(3), 108-118.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/07421656.2010.10129660>
- Smriti, D., Kaimal, G., & Wang, X. (2022). Creative arts therapies for the mental health of emerging adults: A systematic review. *The Arts in Psychotherapy*, 79, 101888. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aip.2021.101861>
- Solbakken, L. E., Bergvik, S., & Wynn, R. (2024). Breaking down barriers to mental healthcare access in prison: a qualitative interview study with incarcerated males in Norway. *BMC psychiatry*, 24(1), 292.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-024-05736-w>
- Spotify. (2023, August 10). *Nearly a quarter of all streams on Spotify are hip-hop*. Spotify Newsroom. <https://newsroom.spotify.com/2023-08-10/hip-hop-50-murals-new-york-atlanta-miami-los-angeles/>
- Steup, M., & Neta, R. (2020). Epistemology. In E. N. Zalta (Ed.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Fall 2020 Edition). Stanford University.
- Stewart, R. E., & Chambless, D. L. (2009). Cognitive–behavioral therapy for adult anxiety disorders in clinical practice: A meta-analysis of effectiveness studies. *Journal of consulting and clinical psychology*, 77(4), 595-606.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0016032>
- Stockwell, H., Roche, E., & Billings, J. (2024). Pathways to care and compulsory admission: A systematic review and meta-analysis of the international evidence. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 11(1), 47–57.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(23\)00297-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(23)00297-4)

- Stuckey, H. L., & Nobel, J. (2010). The connection between art, healing, and public health: A review of current literature. *American journal of public health*, 100(2), 254-263. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2008.156497>
- Suite, D. H., La Bril, R., Primm, A., & Harrison-Ross, P. (2007). Beyond misdiagnosis, misunderstanding and mistrust: Relevance of the historical perspective in the medical and mental health treatment of people of color. *Journal of the National Medical Association*, 99(8), 879–885. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2574307/>
- Sule, A., & Inkster, B. (2020). Rap's battle with mental health: How hip-hop's progressive narratives are helping to tackle stigma. *The BMJ Opinion*. <https://blogs.bmj.com/bmj/2020/12/09/raps-battle-with-mental-health-how-hip-hops-progressive-narratives-are-helping-to-tackle-stigma/>
- Suppes, A., van der Toorn, J., & Begeny, C. T. (2021). Unhealthy closets, discriminatory dwellings: The mental health benefits and costs of being open about one's sexual minority status. *Social Science & Medicine*, 285, 114286. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2021.114286>
- Synergi Collaborative Centre. (2017). *The Synergi Collaborative Centre: A national initiative to reframe, rethink and transform the realities of ethnic inequalities in severe mental illness and multiple disadvantage*. <https://www.synergicollaborativecentre.co.uk/>
- The King's Fund. (2021). *The health of people from ethnic minority groups in England*. The King's Fund. <https://www.kingsfund.org.uk/publications/health-people-ethnic-minority-groups-england>
- The Times. (2024, January 30). Young men seek vulnerable role models over traditional heroes. *The Times*. <https://www.thetimes.co.uk/article/young-men-vulnerable-role-models-baby-reindeer-the-bear-6nlk9vljs>
- Tuastad, L., & O'Grady, L. (2013). Music therapy inside and outside prison – A freedom practice? *Nordic Journal of Music Therapy*, 22(3), 210-232. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08098131.2012.752760>

- Tyson, E. H. (2002). Hip-hop therapy: An exploratory study of a rap music intervention with at-risk and delinquent youth. *Journal of Poetry Therapy*, 15(3), 131–144. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1019795911358>
- Tyson, E. H., Detchkov, K., Eastwood, E., Carver, A., & Sehr, A. (2013). Therapeutically and socially relevant themes in hip-hop music: A comprehensive analysis of a selected sample of songs. In S. Hadley & G. Yancy (Eds.), *Therapeutic uses of rap and hip-hop* (pp. 137–159). Routledge.
- UK Grantmaking. (2024). *UK Grantmaking 2024: The state of UK funding*. <https://www.ukgrantmaking.org/2024/>
- Wardle, H., & Obermuller, L. (2019). “Windrush generation” and “hostile environment”: symbols and lived experiences in Caribbean migration to the UK. *Migration and Society*, 2(1), 81-89. <https://doi.org/10.3167/ARMS.2019.020108>
- Watkins, D. C., & Neighbors, H. W. (2007). An initial exploration of what 'mental health' means to young Black men. *Journal of Men's Health & Gender*, 4(3), 271–282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmhg.2007.06.006>
- Wells, E. B. (2019). *Hip-Hop education*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Wheeler, B. L. (Ed.). (2015). *Music therapy handbook*. Guilford Publications.
- White, J. L., & Cones, J. H. (1999). *Black man emerging: Facing the past and seizing a future in America*. W. H. Freeman.
- Wilkins, D. (2010). *Untold problems: A review of the essential issues in the mental health of men and boys*. Men's Health Forum. https://www.menshealthforum.org.uk/sites/default/files/pdf/untold_problems.pdf
- Williams, D. R., & Mohammed, S. A. (2013). Racism and health: Pathways and scientific evidence. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 57(8), 1200–1226. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764213487340>

- Williams, D. R., Mohammed, S. A., Leavell, J., & Collins, C. (2010). Race, socioeconomic status, and health: complexities, ongoing challenges, and research opportunities. *Annals of the new York Academy of Sciences*, 1186(1), 69-101. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-6632.2009.05339>
- Willig, C. (2019). *Epistemological reflexivity and the theory of knowledge*. In *Introducing qualitative research in psychology* (4th ed., pp. 15–35). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Wong, Y. J., Ho, M. R., Wang, S. Y., & Miller, I. S. K. (2017). Meta-analyses of the relationship between conformity to masculine norms and mental health-related outcomes. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 64(1), 80–93. <https://doi.org/10.1037/cou0000176>
- Wood, S., & Patel, V. (2017). Assessment and treatment approaches for diverse populations. In S. Wood & V. Patel (Eds.), *Clinical psychology: A global perspective* (pp. 123–145). Cambridge University Press.
- World Health Organization. (n.d.). *Gender*. <https://www.who.int/health-topics/gender>
- Yardley, L. (2015). Demonstrating validity in qualitative psychology. In J. A. Smith (Ed.), *Qualitative psychology: A practical guide to research methods* (3rd ed., pp. 257–272). SAGE Publications.
- Zaatar, M. T., Alhakim, K., Enayeh, M., & Tamer, R. (2024). The transformative power of music: Insights into neuroplasticity, health, and disease. *Brain, behavior, & immunity-health*, 35, 100716. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbih.2023.100716>
- Zatorre, R. (2005). Music, the food of neuroscience?. *Nature*, 434(7031), 312-315. <https://doi.org/10.1038/434312a>

6. APPENDICES

Appendix A: The Integrated Behavioural Model of Mental Health Help Seeking Diagram (Hammer et al., 2024)

Appendix B: Examples of the Integrated Behavioural Model of Mental Health Help Seeking (Hammer et al., 2024)

Example 1. Black male, aged 28, experiencing low mood and work-related stress.

Determinants

- Structural forces: Works in a corporate sector and his employer offers private health insurance which covers therapy. Experiencing microaggressions at work.
- Cultural influences: Nigerian-British background, family values perseverance and strength, but younger generations in his circles talk about mental health.
- Environmental constraints: Lives in rural area, so limited access to therapists with shared cultural and racial background, which is his preference.
- Past help-seeking experiences: Positive experience of counselling while studying at university.
- Evaluated need: Recognises that low mood is impacting work and social life.
- Mental health perceptions, knowledge and skills: Knows how to self-refer to therapy via private health insurance.
- Social support: Partner and close friends encourage help-seeking.
- Other determinants: Sees Black male role models online who speak about therapy positively.

Beliefs

- Outcome beliefs: He *believes/thinks* that therapy will help him manage stress, talk about experiences of racism and improve mood.
- Experiential beliefs: He *feels* nervous about accessing therapy, particularly if the therapist is from a different cultural background.
- Beliefs about others' expectations: Friends expect him to seek help, family may find it unusual but will not oppose it.
- Beliefs about others' behaviour: Believes that friends would also seek therapy if struggling with low mood.
- Logistical beliefs: Able to afford sessions due to private health insurance and flexibility with scheduling sessions as he works from home.

Attitudes

- Attitude (Instrumental): He *believes* that he should access therapy and that it will help him.
- Attitude (Experiential): He *anticipates* finding it useful, however he feels anxious about the prospect of opening up to a new and unfamiliar person, particularly if they do not share the same cultural/racial background.

- Perceived norm (Injunctive): His friendship group values openness about mental health.
- Perceived norm (Descriptive): He has seen other Black men he knows accessing therapy.
- Personal agency (Autonomy): He feels in control of his decision to seek help.
- Personal agency (Capacity): He knows the steps he needs to take to self-refer for therapy and feels capable of acting on this. He feels able to search among the private sector to find a therapist that shares a similar background to him.

Intention: Strong intention to access therapy, despite worries about the therapist.

Prospective behaviour: He engages in help-seeking by scheduling and attending sessions with a therapist.

Example 2. Black male, aged 57, experiencing anxiety and sleep difficulties.

Determinants

- Structural forces: Lives in city where mental health services are available, but limited culturally competent services. Aware of disproportionate rates of sectioning for Black men and over-representation in secure units.
- Cultural influences: Jamaican parents who migrated to the UK during the Windrush era. Grew up in a close-knit Caribbean community where stoicism and “getting on with it” were seen as virtues, especially in the face of racism.
- Environmental constraints: Mental health services are available in the city; however family responsibilities limit opportunities for looking into getting support.
- Past help-seeking experiences: He and his friends were badly mistreated by the police as teenagers.
- Evaluated need: He recognises that his anxiety and sleep problems are impacting his relationships with his family, but he tells himself “it’s normal, it’s just stress”.
- Mental health perceptions, knowledge and skills: He knows where to look for mental health support but thinks that his anxiety and sleep will get better if he ignores thinking about it and gets on with things.
- Social support: Friends from his generation rarely talk about mental health or emotional struggles. Family conversations focus on resilience and faith.
- Other determinants: Awareness of racial injustice in health, policing and employment shapes his mistrust of institutions.

Beliefs

- Outcome beliefs: He *believes* that engaging with mental health services could lead to being medicated, labelled or stigmatised, which might damage his reputation in his community.
- Experiential beliefs: A previous GP encounter left him *feeling* dismissed, he *feels* worried that might happen with a therapist.
- Beliefs about others' expectations: His family expects him to be self-reliant, feels that seeking help would be seen as a weakness.
- Beliefs about others' behaviour: Rarely sees older Caribbean men in his community seeking help for mental health and hears more about managing quietly.
- Logistical beliefs: Believes accessing the 'right' kind of therapy would be too difficult and time-consuming.

Attitudes

- Attitude (Instrumental): He *believes* therapy will not address the real issue, which is the stress of living in a society where Black men face many inequalities and are under supported.
- Attitude (Experiential): He *anticipates* that therapy would worsen *feelings* of frustration and stress.
- Perceived norm (Injunctive): Community norms discourage public disclosure of personal struggles, prioritising keeping problems "in the family".
- Perceived norm (Descriptive): His peers typically avoid formal help and rely on informal supports like family, church and community.
- Personal agency (Autonomy): Feels constrained by cultural expectations and past systemic injustices.
- Personal agency (Capacity): Does not feel equipped to navigate the help-seeking process or advocate for culturally relevant care.

Intention: Low intention to seek support for his anxiety and sleep problems.

Prospective behaviour: Avoids help-seeking and continues to manage his mental health difficulties independently.

Appendix C: PRISMA-ScR Diagram Demonstrating Scoping Review Literature Search

Appendix D: Interview Schedule

Opening

- Introduction to the interview: introductions, rationale for study, confidentiality, practical considerations (length of interview, remind they can take a break if needed, do not have to answer all of the questions, can stop/withdraw at any point) and re-confirm consent.
- Establish rapport, for example, asking opening questions such as “What do you like about rap music? What genre of do you enjoy listening to? Favourite artists/songs and why?”
- Ask about age and ethnicity (self-description and list of census ethnicity categories).

Main

- In what way do you create rap music? (prompts: writing lyrics, producing content?). How often?
- What is your experience of creating rap music?
- How does it make you feel?
- What are the positives/negatives of creating rap music?
- When creating rap music, have you ever spoken about experiences of mental health, trauma and adversity? Example?
- How does doing that affect you or make you feel?
- What elements of rap make it easier/harder to talk about these difficulties?
- Does doing so feel similar or different to talking to those close to you (e.g., family, friends, partners), or professionals in healthcare contexts? Why is that?
- Is there anything else you would like to add?

Prompting questions

- Have you used rap as an emotional outlet? Why?
- Does creating rap music enable you to express vulnerability? Why?
- Does creating rap music ever feel therapeutic? Why?
- Are there times when it does not feel therapeutic? Why?

Closing

- Summary of content discussed.
- Ask participants what pseudo name they would like to have for the analysis and write up of the project (give option for them to give their own or provide a list of names).
- Debrief – re-confirm consent, check in, reflections about experience and sign posting to further support.
- Explain voucher form
- Thank and share gratitude with participant for time.

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET
Version 1.0 | 31.03.2024

**Crafting Lyrics, Breaking Barriers: Exploring the Role of Rap Music in
Facilitating Mental Health Expression among Black Men in the UK**

Principal Investigator: Lynette Meredith
Email: u2388775@uel.ac.uk

This information sheet provides information about a research study that you could take part in. If you would like to participate, it is important that you read and understand the information provided below and complete the consent form.

Who am I?

My name is Lynette Meredith, and I am studying Clinical Psychology at the University of East London. As part of this professional doctorate, I am conducting a research project.

What is this research about?

This project is trying to understand whether creating rap music helps Black men to talk about difficulties such as mental health, trauma and adversity.

Rap music has worldwide popularity and cultural significance within the Black community. Research shows that lyrical references to mental health have increased over the years. This project could help to improve our understanding of whether creating rap music impacts Black men's willingness to talk about life challenges. This

may have helpful implications for mental health services aiming to make therapy more culturally relevant and engaging.

Can you take part?

I am looking for participants to take part in this study who:

- Are aged 18 and above,
- Identify as male,
- Are Black or mixed heritage Black,
- Create rap music in any capacity (e.g. writing lyrics, performing).

What will the research involve?

If you decide to take part, I will arrange a suitable time to meet with you virtually (via video call on Microsoft Teams) for one interview discussion lasting around 45-60 minutes. We will discuss your experience of creating rap music and whether it has helped you to speak about mental health and other life challenges.

What are the advantages and disadvantages of taking part?

Participating in this study will allow you to contribute to the research evidence-base relating to rap music and mental health. I hope that you will enjoy having the space to talk about your experiences of creating rap music. You will also be reimbursed with a £10 Amazon voucher for your contributions to this research project.

As the interviews will involve discussing whether rap influences disclosure about mental health, trauma and adversity, there might be some conversations that you find difficult or distressing. I will do my best to ensure that the interview feels like a safe space. You do not have to answer all of the questions asked and can take a break at any point if needed. Information about accessing support will be provided to you afterwards. You are also free to leave the research project at any time without giving a reason.

How will your information be used?

The interviews will be video recorded and automatically transcribed by Microsoft Teams. Once I have checked the transcriptions for accuracy and anonymised any

identifiable information, the recordings will be deleted within 48 hours. The transcripts will then be stored securely to help me remember what you say so that I can analyse and write up the research findings.

Your name and any other identifiable information will not be used in the write up and publication of this research study and your participation will be confidential.

Anonymised quotes of what you have said may be included in the report.

All information relating to your participation (including your consent form and transcriptions) will be stored on a secure and encrypted University of East London OneDrive. A back-up will be stored on the research supervisor's OneDrive. Examiners of the doctoral thesis report may also wish to see the anonymised transcripts. All research data will be destroyed after a maximum of 3 years.

For the purposes of data protection, the University of East London is the Data Controller for the personal information processed as part of this research project. The University processes this information under the 'public task' condition contained in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Where the University processes particularly sensitive data (known as 'special category data' in the GDPR), it does so because the processing is necessary for archiving purposes in the public interest, or scientific and historical research purposes or statistical purposes. The University will ensure that the personal data it processes is held securely and processed in accordance with the GDPR and the Data Protection Act 2018. For more information about how the University processes personal data please see www.uel.ac.uk/about/about-uel/governance/information-assurance/data-protection

What will happen to the results of this research?

The information that you have shared with me will be written up as a doctoral thesis and submitted for assessment. The thesis will be publicly available on the University of East London's online Research Repository. Findings may be disseminated to a wide range of audiences through journal articles and blogs. If you take part, you will also be given the option to receive a summary of the results. Your identity will remain anonymous.

Do you have to take part?

You do not have to take part in this study if you do not wish to. Participation is entirely your decision. You can also change your mind at any time and leave the study without giving a reason.

You can request to withdraw your data from being used after you have taken part in the study, provided that this request is made within 3 weeks of the interview. If you withdraw from the study after this point, information from your interview discussion may still be used for the purpose of evaluating and writing up the research findings. All identifiable information will be removed.

Who has reviewed the research?

This research study has been reviewed and has received a favourable ethical opinion from the University of East London School of Psychology Research Ethics Committee (SREC). This means that the Committee's evaluation of this ethics application has been guided by the standards of research ethics set by the British Psychological Society.

How can you find out more or contact if you have any questions or concerns?

If you have any questions or concerns about this research project, please email me on u2388775@uel.ac.uk. You can also contact the following people:

Director of Studies: Dr Lorna Farquharson, School of Psychology, University of East London, Water Lane, London, E15 4LZ.

Email: l.farquharson@uel.ac.uk

or

Chair of School Ethics Committee: Dr Trishna Patel, School of Psychology, University of East London, Water Lane, London E15 4LZ.

Email: t.patel@uel.ac.uk

Thank you for your time and considering taking part in this study.

I look forward to meeting those of you who take part.

CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN A RESEARCH STUDY
Version 1.0 | 31.03.2024

**Crafting Lyrics, Breaking Barriers: Exploring the Role of Rap Music in
Facilitating Mental Health Expression among Black Men in the UK**

Principal Investigator: Lynette Meredith
Email: u2388775@uel.ac.uk

This consent form is to show that you have agreed to take part in this research study. Please read each statement below carefully and select whether you agree.

- | | |
|--|--------|
| 1. I have read and understand the participant information sheet for this research study. | YES/NO |
| 2. I have been able to consider the information provided to me about the study, ask questions and have them answered. | YES/NO |
| 3. I understand that participation in this study is my choice and that I can withdraw at any time before or during the interview, without explanation. | YES/NO |
| 4. I agree to my interviews being recorded. | YES/NO |
| 5. I understand what will happen to my information once the research has been completed. | YES/NO |

- | | |
|---|--------|
| 6. I understand that my personal information and recording of the interview will be stored securely and remain confidential. Only the research team will have access to this information, to which I give my permission. | YES/NO |
| 7. I understand that anonymised information from my interview (including quotes) may be used in research reports, articles in academic journals and conference presentations resulting from the study, which will not personally identify me. | YES/NO |
| 8. I would like to receive a summary of the research findings once the study is completed. | YES/NO |
| 9. I agree to take part in this study. | YES/NO |

.....

PARTICIPANT NAME
(IN BLOCK CAPITALS)

DATE

SIGNATURE

.....

RESEARCHER NAME
(IN BLOCK CAPITALS)

DATE

SIGNATURE

PARTICIPANT DEBRIEF SHEET
Version 1.0 | 31.03.2024

Crafting Lyrics, Breaking Barriers: Exploring the Role of Rap Music in Facilitating Mental Health Expression among Black Men in the UK

Principal Investigator: Lynette Meredith
Email: u2388775@uel.ac.uk

Thank you for taking part in my research project, which is exploring whether rap music helps Black men to talk about experiences of mental health, trauma, and adversity. I really appreciate you taking the time to talk to me about your experiences and I hope you have found it interesting.

How will your data be managed?

The University of East London is the Data Controller for the personal information processed as part of this research project. The University will ensure that the personal data it processes is held securely and processed in accordance with the GDPR and the Data Protection Act 2018. More detailed information is available in the Participant Information Sheet, which you received when you agreed to take part in the research.

What will happen to the results of this research?

The experiences that you have shared with me will be written up as a doctoral thesis and submitted for assessment. The thesis will be publicly available on the University of East London's online Research Repository. Findings may be disseminated to a wide

range of audiences through journal articles and blogs. You can also receive a summary of the results. Your identity will remain anonymous.

Can you withdraw or change your mind about taking part?

You can withdraw at any point without giving a reason. You can request to withdraw your data, provided that this request is made within 3 weeks of the interview. If you withdraw from the study after this point, information from your interview discussion may still be used for the purpose of evaluating and writing up the research findings. All identifiable information will be removed.

What if you have been adversely affected by taking part?

If you have found any parts of our discussions to be distressing, please consider speaking with someone that you trust such as a family member or friend. If you would like to consider getting mental health support or accessing psychological therapy, please speak to your GP who can make a referral to a local service. There are also different organisations that you can contact or look at for additional support and information, included on the next page. **If you are in an emergency crisis and feel that your life is at risk, call 999 or go straight to your local A&E department.**

Who can you contact if you have any questions or concerns?

If you have any questions or concerns about this research project, please email me on u2388775@uel.ac.uk.

You can also contact the following people:

Director of Studies: Dr Lorna Farquharson, School of Psychology, University of East London, Water Lane, London, E15 4LZ.

Email: l.farquharson@uel.ac.uk

or

Chair of School Ethics Committee: Dr Trishna Patel, School of Psychology, University of East London, Water Lane, London E15 4LZ.

Email: t.patel@uel.ac.uk

Thank you again for taking part in this study.

Organisation	Contact Details & Information
Black Mind's Matter https://www.Blackmindsmatteruk.com/	Information and resources available on website.
MANUP? https://www.manup.how/	Information and resources available on website.
Men Who Talk https://menwhotalk.org/	Information and resources available on website.
Samaritan's https://www.samaritans.org/	Call 116 123 (free, 24/7 telephone support service) Email jo@samaritans.org (may take several days to get an email response)
Shout https://giveusashout.org/	Text 'SHOUT' to 85258 (free, confidential, 24/7 text messaging support service)
Mind https://www.mind.org.uk/	Call 0300 123 3393 (Monday-Friday, 9am-6pm, call for non-urgent mental health information)

Poster

do you rap and identify as a Black male?

I'M INVITING YOU TO TAKE PART IN MY RESEARCH!

I'M INTERESTED IN WHETHER RAP MUSIC HELPS BLACK MEN TO TALK ABOUT EXPERIENCES OF MENTAL HEALTH, TRAUMA AND ADVERSITY.

TO UNDERSTAND THIS BETTER, I'LL BE CARRYING OUT 1-1 VIRTUAL INTERVIEWS LASTING AROUND 45-60 MINUTES.

YOU COULD PARTICIPATE IF YOU:

- ARE AGED 18 AND ABOVE,
- IDENTIFY AS MALE,
- ARE BLACK OR MIXED HERITAGE BLACK
- CREATE RAP MUSIC IN ANY CAPACITY (E.G. WRITING, PERFORMING)

YOU WILL BE REIMBURSED WITH A £10 AMAZON VOUCHER.

I'M LYNETTE, THE TRAINEE CLINICAL PSYCHOLOGIST CARRYING OUT THIS DOCTORAL RESEARCH AT UEL.

PLEASE CONTACT ME ON U2388775@UEL.AC.UK IF YOU WOULD LIKE TO TAKE PART OR FIND OUT MORE.

**University of
East London**

THIS STUDY HAS RECEIVED A FAVOURABLE ETHICAL OPINION FROM THE UEL SCHOOL OF PSYCHOLOGY RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE (SREC)

Emails

The below email was sent out to 15 organisations and individuals. This included music studios, youth community organisations, mental health organisations offering rap, hip-hop or music therapy and individuals working with young offenders or at risk of offending.

“Dear [organisation/individual]

I hope this email finds you well.

My name’s Lynette and I’m a second-year trainee on the Clinical Psychology Doctorate at the University of East London.

I’m reaching out to you in relation to my thesis project, which will be looking at whether rap music helps Black men to talk about experiences of mental health, adversity and trauma. This is currently missing in the literature and feels important to research, given that a lot of traditional interventions offered within the NHS aren’t culturally relevant and can feel inaccessible. I will be conducting 1-1 online interviews lasting between 45-60 minutes and my target demographic is: aged 18+, identify as male, Black or mixed heritage Black, and create rap music in any capacity.

I’m looking for organisations to support me with circulating my research poster to potential participants once my project starts this summer (please see the draft poster attached, for reference). I’m also currently looking for help in identifying a few people from my target demographic who would like to give feedback on my thesis materials (e.g. consent form, information sheet) and thesis title.

Please let me know if you might be able to support me with my project. I’d be happy to answer any questions or arrange a meeting to discuss anything further.

Best wishes,

Lynette”

A follow up email was also sent out to organisations who did not initially respond, below.

“Dear [organisation/individual]

I hope this email finds you well.

I’m emailing to follow up on the below email, to see if it would be possible to link up with you for my doctoral thesis project?

Specifically, I’m looking for organisations to support me with circulating my research poster to potential participants (please see the draft poster attached, for reference).

I’m also looking for help in identifying a few people from my target demographic who would like to give feedback on my thesis materials (e.g. consent form, information sheet) and thesis title. The target demographic is - aged 18+, identify as male, Black or mixed heritage Black, and create rap music.

Please let me know if you have any questions or would like to arrange a time to talk.

Kind regards,

Lynette”

An X account was made for the purpose of circulating the research poster. An example of post is demonstrated below.

“Looking for participants to take part in my clinical psychology doctoral thesis, exploring whether rap music helps Black men to talk about experiences of mental health, trauma and adversity. Get in touch if interested in taking part/finding out more. Retweets are appreciated!”

Appendix I: Voucher Reimbursement Form

UNIVERSITY OF EAST LONDON
SCHOOL OF PSYCHOLOGY

PARTICIPANT VOUCHER CLAIM FORM 2023-24

Recipient Name: _____

Recipient Title: _____

Home Address: _____

Term-time Address: _____

(if applicable)

National Insurance No: _ _ _ _ _

UEL Student No: _____ Date of Birth: _____ / _____ / _____

(if applicable)

Amount Received: £ 10 . 00 p

Voucher Serial No(s): _____

Date received: _____

I declare that this is the first such claim I have made in the current tax year. I receive no other earnings from the University of East London.

N.B. – If either of the above statements does not apply, please let the University Project Manager know as you will not be entitled to this one-off cash payment

Recipient Signature: _____

Issuer Name: _____

Issuer Signature: _____

Issue Date: _____

Project Manager
Authorisation: _____

Project Code: _____

UNIVERSITY OF EAST LONDON
School of Psychology

**APPLICATION FOR RESEARCH ETHICS APPROVAL
 FOR RESEARCH INVOLVING HUMAN PARTICIPANTS
 (Updated October 2021)**

**FOR BSc RESEARCH;
 MSc/MA RESEARCH;
 PROFESSIONAL DOCTORATE RESEARCH IN CLINICAL, COUNSELLING & EDUCATIONAL
 PSYCHOLOGY**

7. Section 1 – Guidance on Completing the Application Form

8. (please read carefully)

1.1	Before completing this application, please familiarise yourself with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ British Psychological Society’s Code of Ethics and Conduct ▪ UEL’s Code of Practice for Research Ethics ▪ UEL’s Research Data Management Policy ▪ UEL’s Data Backup Policy
1.2	Email your supervisor the completed application and all attachments as ONE WORD DOCUMENT. Your supervisor will look over your application and provide feedback.
1.3	When your application demonstrates a sound ethical protocol, your supervisor will submit it for review.
1.4	Your supervisor will let you know the outcome of your application. Recruitment and data collection must NOT commence until your ethics application has been approved, along with other approvals that may be necessary (see section 7).
1.5	Research in the NHS: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ If your research involves patients or service users of the NHS, their relatives or carers, as well as those in receipt of services provided under contract to the NHS, you

	<p>will need to apply for HRA approval/NHS permission (through IRAS). You DO NOT need to apply to the School of Psychology for ethical clearance.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Useful websites: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.myresearchproject.org.uk/Signin.aspx https://www.hra.nhs.uk/approvals-amendments/what-approvals-do-i-need/hra-approval/ ▪ If recruitment involves NHS staff via the NHS, an application will need to be submitted to the HRA in order to obtain R&D approval. This is in addition to separate approval via the R&D department of the NHS Trust involved in the research. UEL ethical approval will also be required. ▪ HRA/R&D approval is not required for research when NHS employees are not recruited directly through NHS lines of communication (UEL ethical approval is required). This means that NHS staff can participate in research without HRA approval when a student recruits via their own social/professional networks or through a professional body such as the BPS, for example. ▪ The School strongly discourages BSc and MSc/MA students from designing research that requires HRA approval for research involving the NHS, as this can be a very demanding and lengthy process.
1.6	<p>If you require Disclosure Barring Service (DBS) clearance (see section 6), please request a DBS clearance form from the Hub, complete it fully, and return it to applicantchecks@uel.ac.uk. Once the form has been approved, you will be registered with GBG Online Disclosures and a registration email will be sent to you. Guidance for completing the online form is provided on the GBG website:</p> <p>https://fadv.onlinedisclosures.co.uk/Authentication/Login</p> <p>You may also find the following website to be a useful resource:</p> <p>https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/disclosure-and-barring-service</p>
1.7	<p>Checklist, the following attachments should be included if appropriate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Study advertisement ▪ Participant Information Sheet (PIS) ▪ Participant Consent Form ▪ Participant Debrief Sheet ▪ Risk Assessment Form/Country-Specific Risk Assessment Form (see section 5) ▪ Permission from an external organisation (see section 7) ▪ Original and/or pre-existing questionnaire(s) and test(s) you intend to use ▪ Interview guide for qualitative studies ▪ Visual material(s) you intend showing participants

9. Section 2 – Your Details

2.1	Your name:	Lynette Meredith
2.2	Your supervisor's name:	Dr Lorna Farquharson

2.3	Name(s) of additional UEL supervisors:	Dr Vicki Collin 3rd supervisor (if applicable)
2.4	Title of your programme:	Professional Doctorate in Clinical Psychology
2.5	UEL assignment submission date:	15/02/2025 Re-sit date (if applicable)

10. Section 3 – Project Details

Please give as much detail as necessary for a reviewer to be able to fully understand the nature and purpose of your research.

3.1	Study title: <u>Please note</u> - If your study requires registration, the title inserted here must be <u>the same</u> as that on PhD Manager	Crafting Lyrics, Breaking Barriers: Exploring the Role of Rap Music in Facilitating Mental Health Expression among Black Men in the UK
3.2	Summary of study background and aims (using lay language):	<p>Despite being over-represented in rates of mental health difficulties, secure mental health services and the criminal justice system, Black men are under-represented in how often they access psychological therapy (McKeown, Robertson, Habte-Mariam, Newbigging & Stockwell-Smith, 2008; McManus, Bebbington, Jenkins & Brugha, 2016; Bignall, Jeraj, Helsby & Butt, 2019).</p> <p>The lack of engagement in mental health services may relate to a reluctance to seek help and talk about psychological distress. For example, research has found that some Black men view mental health services and professionals as stigmatising, discriminative and failing to address cultural barriers (Meechan, 2021, Watkins & Neighbors, 2007). The inter-section between race and gender has also been explored as a factor influencing help-seeking and mental health discourse (e.g. Black masculinity and emotional expression being viewed as ‘weak’, Coleman-Kirumba, Cornish, Horton & Alvarez, 2022).</p> <p>Culturally adaptive interventions have been developed to address these barriers; for example, rap and hip-hop music interventions have shown positive outcomes in contexts such as prisons (e.g.</p>

		<p>Elligan’s Rap Therapy, 2000).</p> <p>Given the worldwide popularity and cultural significance of rap music within the Black community, and the increasing lyrical reference to mental health amongst artists (Kresovich, Collins, Riffe & Carpentier, 2021), it could be used creatively to address lack of engagement with services. Yet, little is known about whether, or how rap music enables Black men to talk about mental health and adversity.</p> <p>Missing in the current literature is how rap music impacts men’s willingness to disclose emotion and hardship (Levy & Keum, 2014). Therefore, this study aims to explore whether and how rap music helps Black men to talk about experiences of mental health and adversity.</p>
3.3	Research question(s):	<p>The proposed research questions are as follows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Does creating rap music impact Black men’s willingness to talk about mental health and adversity? 2. If so, what is it about rap music that impacts disclosure?
3.4	Research design:	<p>This research project adopts qualitative approach, using semi-structured interviews with participants. The 1-1 interviews will be conducted online via MS Teams, lasting between 45-60 minutes. The study is cross-sectional as data will only be collected at one time point (during the interview).</p> <p>A critical realist position will be drawn upon for this research. This position assumes that data reflects what is occurring in the “real world”, however, instead of directly reflecting reality, it reflects an individual’s perspectives and how they relate to others within a historical, social, and cultural context (Willig, 2012; Tuli, 2010). Rather than searching for an objective truth or reality, the individual and collective experiences of Black</p>

		men will be explored within a broader cultural, historical, and social context.
3.5	Participants: Include all relevant information including inclusion and exclusion criteria	<p>I aim to recruit between 10-12 participants.</p> <p>The following inclusion criteria will be used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aged 18 and above - Identify as male - Black or mixed heritage Black - Create rap music in any capacity - Live in the UK
3.6	Recruitment strategy: Provide as much detail as possible and include a backup plan if relevant	<p>I aim to recruit via three methods with the use of a research advertisement poster (see Appendix A).</p> <p>The first will be through the support of community-based organisations who have agreed to share my poster to potential participants and via social media (see Appendix F for evidence of permission sought from organisations who have been approached so far).</p> <p>The second will be through social media; I will be sharing my research poster to personal and professional networks through an X account created for this project (@RapMentalHealth).</p> <p>The third will be by sharing the poster to personal and professional networks using WhatsApp.</p>
3.7	Measures, materials or equipment: Provide detailed information, e.g., for measures, include scoring instructions, psychometric properties, if freely available, permissions required, etc.	<p>An interview schedule will be followed (see Appendix D). The interview will ask questions relating to participant's experiences of creating rap music, whether they have used rap music to talk about personal difficulties and whether doing so makes it easier/harder for disclosure.</p> <p>A laptop with access to the internet, Microsoft Teams, Microsoft Office (Word, Excel), UEL email and UEL OneDrive will be used. The research advertisement poster was designed using the online graphic design tool, Canva (www.canva.com).</p>

3.8	<p>Data collection: Provide information on how data will be collected from the point of consent to debrief</p>	<p>The participant information sheet (see Appendix B) will be shared with those who express interest in taking part in the study. The names and contact details of those who express interest will be stored in a secure excel document on UEL OneDrive for the purpose of recruitment organisation.</p> <p>Informed consent will be collected via a consent form (see Appendix C), which can be electronically signed or printed, signed, electronically scanned and sent to me as the researcher. Consent forms will be stored securely my UEL OneDrive.</p> <p>1-1 interviews will be conducted virtually via Microsoft Teams and will last between 45-60 minutes. Interviews will only take place if participants have given consent. The interviews will follow a semi-structured interview guide (see Appendix D). At the end of the interview, I will revisit consent to use the interview data, debrief the participants verbally and give them the debrief sheet (see Appendix E).</p> <p>Audio transcription of the interviews will be downloaded from Microsoft Teams and checked through for accuracy. Manual amendments will be made to the transcriptions where necessary. All identifiable information will be removed, and the transcription file will be securely saved under the assigned pseudonym on UEL OneDrive. The Microsoft Teams recording will then be deleted.</p>	
3.9	<p>Will you be engaging in deception?</p>	<p>YES <input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>NO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
	<p>If yes, what will participants be told about the nature of the research, and how/when will you inform them about its real nature?</p>	<p>N/A</p>	
3.10	<p>Will participants be reimbursed?</p>	<p>YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>NO <input type="checkbox"/></p>
	<p>If yes, please detail why it is necessary.</p>	<p>Participants will be reimbursed for their contributions to this research project, which will</p>	

		involve meeting with me for an interview lasting 45-60 minutes. I feel that it is necessary to compensate participants for their time, as the interview may bring up sensitive topics relating to how rap music has influenced personal disclosure about mental health, trauma, and adversity. Furthermore, speaking to a stranger about personal difficulties may be challenging.
	How much will you offer? <u>Please note</u> - This must be in the form of vouchers, <u>not cash</u> .	£10 Amazon voucher per participant
3.11	Data analysis:	<p>Reflexive thematic analysis will be used to analyse the interview data, which involves ‘developing, analyzing and interpreting patterns across a qualitative dataset’ (p.4, Braun & Clarke, 2021). My position as researcher is also considered within this approach, in relation to how my experiences, knowledge and identity may influence interpretation of the data.</p> <p>To analyse the data, the interviews will first be transcribed, then I will follow Braun and Clarke’s (2006) 6 steps to conducting thematic analysis:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Familiarising myself with the data 2. Generating initial codes 3. Searching for themes 4. Reviewing steps 5. Defining themes 6. Writing up <p>My position as a researcher will be reflected upon by keeping a reflexive journal.</p>

11. Section 4 – Confidentiality, Security and Data Retention

It is vital that data are handled carefully, particularly the details about participants. For information in this area, please see the UEL guidance on data protection, and also the UK government guide to data protection regulations.

If a Research Data Management Plan (RDMP) has been completed and reviewed, information from this document can be inserted here.

4.1	Will the participants be anonymised at source?	YES <input type="checkbox"/>	NO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	If yes, please provide details of how the data will be anonymised.		
4.2	Are participants' responses anonymised or are an anonymised sample?	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>
	If yes, please provide details of how data will be anonymised (e.g., all identifying information will be removed during transcription, pseudonyms used, etc.).	During transcription, each participant's name will be replaced by a pseudonym. All identifying information will be removed or replaced to ensure anonymity.	
4.3	How will you ensure participant details will be kept confidential?	<p>Any personal data that is collected will be held securely and processed in accordance with the UK GDPR and the Data Protection Act 2018. Participants will not be identified by the data collected, on any material resulting from the data collected, or in any write-up of the research.</p> <p>Transcription will only be undertaken by myself to protect the confidentiality of participants. Recordings of the interviews will be destroyed as soon as they have been transcribed to minimise the amount of data being stored.</p> <p>Participants will be given a unique pseudonym and all identifying information will be removed during transcription.</p> <p>A list of participant names and pseudonyms will be kept in a separate document and folder to the transcription data, both stored securely on UEL OneDrive.</p> <p>Consent forms and interview transcripts will be stored in different folders on UEL OneDrive.</p> <p>Participants can request to delete their data after the interview within a 3 week opt-out period.</p>	
4.4	How will data be securely stored and backed up during the research?	The data will be stored on my UEL's password protected OneDrive account in a folder that is not synchronised on any devices. Data will be sent to	

	Please include details of how you will manage access, sharing and security	my supervisor as a backup during the study and stored on their OneDrive account. Consent forms will be stored as password-protected files in a separate folder to other research data on UEL OneDrive.	
4.5	Who will have access to the data and in what form? (e.g., raw data, anonymised data)	I will have access to the raw data. My supervisor will have access to the anonymised data.	
4.6	Which data are of long-term value and will be retained? (e.g., anonymised interview transcripts, anonymised databases)	The anonymised transcripts are of long-term value. It is expected that some of the anonymised research data (e.g. quotes from the interviews) will be used for wider dissemination purposes.	
4.7	What is the long-term retention plan for this data?	Anonymised research data will be securely stored on my supervisor's UEL's password-protected OneDrive account for a maximum of 3 years, following which all data will be deleted. All identifiable information will be destroyed as soon as the allowed withdrawal period is over and transcripts have been created unless there has been an agreement with the participants to receive an update from the researcher on the outcomes of the study.	
4.8	Will anonymised data be made available for use in future research by other researchers?	YES <input type="checkbox"/>	NO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	If yes, have participants been informed of this?	YES <input type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>
4.9	Will personal contact details be retained to contact participants in the future for other research studies?	YES <input type="checkbox"/>	NO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	If yes, have participants been informed of this?	YES <input type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>

12. Section 5 – Risk Assessment

If you have serious concerns about the safety of a participant, or others, during the course of your research please speak with your supervisor as soon as possible. If there is any unexpected occurrence while you are collecting your data (e.g., a participant or the researcher injures themselves), please report this to your supervisor as soon as possible.

5.1	Are there any potential physical or psychological risks to	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>
-----	---	---	---------------------------------------

	<p>participants related to taking part? (e.g., potential adverse effects, pain, discomfort, emotional distress, intrusion, etc.)</p>		
	<p>If yes, what are these, and how will they be minimised?</p>	<p>There may be a risk of emotional distress caused by interview discussions with participants around rap music being used in the context of mental health, trauma and adversity. The information sheet will be provided to participants before taking part in the study, which highlights this risk (see Appendix B). A debrief sheet will also be provided after taking part in the study, signposting to different services and organisations participants can access for support (see Appendix E).</p> <p>During the interview, participants will be reminded that they do not have to answer all questions, can take a break if needed, and can withdraw from the study at any point without giving an explanation.</p> <p>Support will be provided by the researcher and Director of Studies, if required. Supervision will be sought by the researcher throughout the project and if any issues arise.</p>	
5.2	<p>Are there any potential physical or psychological risks to you as a researcher?</p>	<p>YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>NO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
	<p>If yes, what are these, and how will they be minimised?</p>	<p>There is a minor risk of emotional distress to myself as the researcher caused by hearing potentially difficult experiences disclosed by the participants. Supervision will be provided by my Director of Studies and will be sought out if any issues arise.</p>	
5.3	<p>If you answered yes to either 5.1 and/or 5.2, you will need to complete and include a General Risk Assessment (GRA) form (signed by your supervisor). Please confirm that you have attached a GRA form as an appendix:</p>	<p>YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	

5.4	If necessary, have appropriate support services been identified in material provided to participants?	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
5.5	Does the research take place outside the UEL campus?	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		NO <input type="checkbox"/>
	If yes, where?	Interviews will take place online via Microsoft Teams. I will be conducting the interviews from home – ensuring that the space is quiet and confidential.		
5.6	Does the research take place outside the UK?	YES <input type="checkbox"/>	NO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	If yes, where?	Please state the country and other relevant details		
	If yes, in addition to the General Risk Assessment form, a Country-Specific Risk Assessment form must also be completed and included (available in the Ethics folder in the Psychology Noticeboard). Please confirm a Country-Specific Risk Assessment form has been attached as an appendix. <u>Please note</u> - A Country-Specific Risk Assessment form is not needed if the research is online only (e.g., Qualtrics survey), regardless of the location of the researcher or the participants.	YES <input type="checkbox"/>		
5.7	Additional guidance: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ For assistance in completing the risk assessment, please use the AIG Travel Guard website to ascertain risk levels. Click on 'sign in' and then 'register here' using policy # 0015865161. Please also consult the Foreign Office travel advice website for further guidance. ▪ For on campus students, once the ethics application has been approved by a reviewer, all risk assessments for research abroad must then be signed by the Director of Impact and Innovation, Professor Ian Tucker (who may escalate it up to the Vice Chancellor). ▪ For distance learning students conducting research abroad in the country where they currently reside, a risk assessment must also be carried out. To minimise risk, it is recommended that such students only conduct data collection online. If the project is deemed low risk, then it is not necessary for the risk assessment to be 			

	<p>signed by the Director of Impact and Innovation. However, if not deemed low risk, it must be signed by the Director of Impact and Innovation (or potentially the Vice Chancellor).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Undergraduate and M-level students are not explicitly prohibited from conducting research abroad. However, it is discouraged because of the inexperience of the students and the time constraints they have to complete their degree.
--	---

13. Section 6 – Disclosure and Barring Service (DBS) Clearance

6.1	<p>Does your research involve working with children (aged 16 or under) or vulnerable adults (*see below for definition)?</p> <p>If yes, you will require Disclosure Barring Service (DBS) or equivalent (for those residing in countries outside of the UK) clearance to conduct the research project</p>	<p>YES</p> <input type="checkbox"/>	<p>NO</p> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<p>* You are required to have DBS or equivalent clearance if your participant group involves:</p> <p>(1) Children and young people who are 16 years of age or under, or</p> <p>(2) ‘Vulnerable’ people aged 16 and over with particular psychiatric diagnoses, cognitive difficulties, receiving domestic care, in nursing homes, in palliative care, living in institutions or sheltered accommodation, or involved in the criminal justice system, for example. Vulnerable people are understood to be persons who are not necessarily able to freely consent to participating in your research, or who may find it difficult to withhold consent. If in doubt about the extent of the vulnerability of your intended participant group, speak with your supervisor. Methods that maximise the understanding and ability of vulnerable people to give consent should be used whenever possible.</p>			
6.2	<p>Do you have DBS or equivalent (for those residing in countries outside of the UK) clearance to conduct the research project?</p>	<p>YES</p> <input type="checkbox"/>	<p>NO</p> <input type="checkbox"/>
6.3	<p>Is your DBS or equivalent (for those residing in countries outside of the UK) clearance valid for the duration of the research project?</p>	<p>YES</p> <input type="checkbox"/>	<p>NO</p> <input type="checkbox"/>
6.4	<p>If you have current DBS clearance, please provide your DBS certificate number:</p>	<p>Please enter your DBS certificate number</p>	

	If residing outside of the UK, please detail the type of clearance and/or provide certificate number.	Please provide details of the type of clearance, including any identification information such as a certificate number
6.5	<p>Additional guidance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ If participants are aged 16 or under, you will need two separate information sheets, consent forms, and debrief forms (one for the participant, and one for their parent/guardian). ▪ For younger participants, their information sheets, consent form, and debrief form need to be written in age-appropriate language. 	

14. Section 7 – Other Permissions

7.1	<p>Does the research involve other organisations (e.g., a school, charity, workplace, local authority, care home, etc.)?</p>	<p>YES</p> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>NO</p> <input type="checkbox"/>
	<p>If yes, please provide their details.</p>	<p>Third sector organisations have been approached to ask for permission to support this project with recruitment by sharing the advertisement poster within their networks. These organisations work with/deliver music interventions to the following demographics: men with mental health difficulties, men at risk of offending, and disadvantaged and vulnerable young people.</p> <p>The organisations that have already given permission include:</p> <p>Hip-hop HEALS Raw Material Music & Media Changing the Game Everybody Loves Music CIC Unique Talent CIC</p> <p>Please see Appendix F for evidence of permission from these organisations.</p>	
	<p>If yes, written permission is needed from such organisations (i.e., if they are helping you with recruitment and/or data collection, if you are collecting</p>	<p>YES</p> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

	<p>data on their premises, or if you are using any material owned by the institution/organisation). Please confirm that you have attached written permission as an appendix.</p>	
7.2	<p><u>Additional guidance:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Before the research commences, once your ethics application has been approved, please ensure that you provide the organisation with a copy of the final, approved ethics application or approval letter. Please then prepare a version of the consent form for the organisation themselves to sign. You can adapt it by replacing words such as 'my' or 'I' with 'our organisation' or with the title of the organisation. This organisational consent form must be signed before the research can commence. ▪ If the organisation has their own ethics committee and review process, a SREC application and approval is still required. Ethics approval from SREC can be gained before approval from another research ethics committee is obtained. However, recruitment and data collection are NOT to commence until your research has been approved by the School and other ethics committee/s. 	

15. Section 8 – Declarations		
8.1	<p>Declaration by student. I confirm that I have discussed the ethics and feasibility of this research proposal with my supervisor:</p>	<p>YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
8.2	<p>Student's name: (Typed name acts as a signature)</p>	<p>Lynette Meredith</p>
8.3	<p>Student's number:</p>	<p>2388775</p>
8.4	<p>Date:</p>	<p>03/05/2024</p>
<p><i>Supervisor's declaration of support is given upon their electronic submission of the application</i></p>		

School of Psychology Ethics Committee

NOTICE OF ETHICS REVIEW DECISION LETTER

For research involving human participants

BSc/MSc/MA/Professional Doctorates in Clinical, Counselling and Educational Psychology

Reviewer: Please complete sections in **blue** | **Student:** Please complete/read sections in **orange**

Details

Reviewer:	Please type your full name Lucy Poxon
Supervisor:	Please type supervisor's full name Lorna Farquharson
Student:	Please type student's full name Lynette Meredith
Course:	Please type course name Prof Doc in Clinical Psychology
Title of proposed study:	Crafting Lyrics, Breaking Barriers: Exploring the Role of Rap Music in Facilitating Mental Health Expression among Black Men in the UK

Checklist

(Optional)

	YES	NO	N/A
Concerns regarding study aims (e.g., ethically/morally questionable, unsuitable topic area for level of study, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Detailed account of participants, including inclusion and exclusion criteria	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Concerns regarding participants/target sample	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Detailed account of recruitment strategy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Concerns regarding recruitment strategy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
All relevant study materials attached (e.g., freely available questionnaires, interview schedules, tests, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Study materials (e.g., questionnaires, tests, etc.) are appropriate for target sample	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Clear and detailed outline of data collection	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Data collection appropriate for target sample	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
If deception being used, rationale provided, and appropriate steps followed to communicate study aims at a later point	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
If data collection is not anonymous, appropriate steps taken at later stages to ensure participant anonymity (e.g., data analysis, dissemination, etc.) – anonymisation, pseudonymisation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Concerns regarding data storage (e.g., location, type of data, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Concerns regarding data sharing (e.g., who will have access and how)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Concerns regarding data retention (e.g., unspecified length of time, unclear why data will be retained/who will have access/where stored)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
If required, General Risk Assessment form attached	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Any physical/psychological risks/burdens to participants have been sufficiently considered and appropriate attempts will be made to minimise	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Any physical/psychological risks to the researcher have been sufficiently considered and appropriate attempts will be made to minimise	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
If required, Country-Specific Risk Assessment form attached	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
If required, a DBS or equivalent certificate number/information provided	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
If required, permissions from recruiting organisations attached (e.g., school, charity organisation, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
All relevant information included in the participant information sheet (PIS)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Information in the PIS is study specific	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Language used in the PIS is appropriate for the target audience	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
All issues specific to the study are covered in the consent form	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Language used in the consent form is appropriate for the target audience	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
All necessary information included in the participant debrief sheet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Language used in the debrief sheet is appropriate for the target audience	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Study advertisement included	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Content of study advertisement is appropriate (e.g., researcher’s personal contact details are not shared, appropriate language/visual material used, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Decision options

APPROVED	Ethics approval for the above-named research study has been granted from the date of approval (see end of this notice), to the date it is submitted for assessment.
APPROVED - BUT MINOR AMENDMENTS ARE REQUIRED BEFORE THE RESEARCH COMMENCES	<p>In this circumstance, the student must confirm with their supervisor that all minor amendments have been made before the research commences. Students are to do this by filling in the confirmation box at the end of this form once all amendments have been attended to and emailing a copy of this decision notice to the supervisor. The supervisor will then forward the student’s confirmation to the School for its records.</p> <p>Minor amendments guidance: typically involve clarifying/amending information presented to participants (e.g., in the PIS, instructions), further</p>

	detailing of how data will be securely handled/stored, and/or ensuring consistency in information presented across materials.
NOT APPROVED - MAJOR AMENDMENTS AND RE-SUBMISSION REQUIRED	<p>In this circumstance, a revised ethics application must be submitted and approved before any research takes place. The revised application will be reviewed by the same reviewer. If in doubt, students should ask their supervisor for support in revising their ethics application.</p> <p>Major amendments guidance: typically insufficient information has been provided, insufficient consideration given to several key aspects, there are serious concerns regarding any aspect of the project, and/or serious concerns in the candidate’s ability to ethically, safely and sensitively execute the study.</p>

Decision on the above-named proposed research study

Please indicate the decision:	APPROVED - MINOR AMENDMENTS ARE REQUIRED BEFORE THE RESEARCH COMMENCES
--------------------------------------	---

Minor amendments

Please clearly detail the amendments the student is required to make

3.6 You state: “The third will be by sharing the poster to personal and professional networks using WhatsApp”. Interviewing friends and acquaintances may introduce the potential for bias in the data you collect – eg participants saying what they think you want to hear, or *not* saying things they know you don’t want to hear. To avoid this potential ethical issue, stipulate recruitment outside of friends and family network.

Major amendments

Please clearly detail the amendments the student is required to make

Assessment of risk to researcher

Has an adequate risk assessment been offered in the application form?	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>
If no, please request resubmission with an <u>adequate risk assessment</u> .		
If the proposed research could expose the <u>researcher</u> to any kind of emotional, physical or health and safety hazard, please rate the degree of risk:		
HIGH	Please do not approve a high-risk application. Travel to countries/provinces/areas deemed to be high risk should not be permitted and an application not be approved on this basis. If unsure, please refer to the Chair of Ethics.	<input type="checkbox"/>
MEDIUM	Approve but include appropriate recommendations in the below box.	<input type="checkbox"/>
LOW	Approve and if necessary, include any recommendations in the below box.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Reviewer recommendations in relation to risk (if any):	Please insert any recommendations	

Reviewer's signature

Reviewer: (Typed name to act as signature)	Dr Lucy Poxon
Date:	08/05/2024
<i>This reviewer has assessed the ethics application for the named research study on behalf of the School of Psychology Ethics Committee</i>	
RESEARCHER PLEASE NOTE	
For the researcher and participants involved in the above-named study to be covered by UEL's Insurance, prior ethics approval from the School of Psychology (acting on behalf of the UEL Ethics Committee), and	

confirmation from students where minor amendments were required, must be obtained before any research takes place.

For a copy of UEL's Personal Accident & Travel Insurance Policy, please see the Ethics Folder in the Psychology Noticeboard.

Confirmation of minor amendments

(Student to complete)

I have noted and made all the required minor amendments, as stated above, before starting my research and collecting data

Student name:

(Typed name to act as signature)

Lynette Meredith

Student number:

2388775

Date:

23/05/2024

Please submit a copy of this decision letter to your supervisor with this box completed if minor amendments to your ethics application are required

UNIVERSITY OF EAST LONDON
School of Psychology

APPLICATION FOR RESEARCH ETHICS APPROVAL
FOR RESEARCH INVOLVING HUMAN PARTICIPANTS
(Updated October 2021)

FOR BSc RESEARCH;
MSc/MA RESEARCH;
PROFESSIONAL DOCTORATE RESEARCH IN CLINICAL, COUNSELLING & EDUCATIONAL
PSYCHOLOGY

16. Section 1 – Guidance on Completing the Application Form

17. (please read carefully)

1.1	Before completing this application, please familiarise yourself with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ British Psychological Society’s Code of Ethics and Conduct ▪ UEL’s Code of Practice for Research Ethics ▪ UEL’s Research Data Management Policy ▪ UEL’s Data Backup Policy
1.2	Email your supervisor the completed application and all attachments as ONE WORD DOCUMENT. Your supervisor will look over your application and provide feedback.
1.3	When your application demonstrates a sound ethical protocol, your supervisor will submit it for review.
1.4	Your supervisor will let you know the outcome of your application. Recruitment and data collection must NOT commence until your ethics application has been approved, along with other approvals that may be necessary (see section 7).
1.5	Research in the NHS: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ If your research involves patients or service users of the NHS, their relatives or carers, as well as those in receipt of services provided under contract to the NHS, you will need to apply for HRA approval/NHS permission (through IRAS). You DO NOT need to apply to the School of Psychology for ethical clearance. ▪ Useful websites: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.myresearchproject.org.uk/Signin.aspx https://www.hra.nhs.uk/approvals-amendments/what-approvals-do-i-need/hra-approval/

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ If recruitment involves NHS staff via the NHS, an application will need to be submitted to the HRA in order to obtain R&D approval. This is in addition to separate approval via the R&D department of the NHS Trust involved in the research. UEL ethical approval will also be required. ▪ HRA/R&D approval is not required for research when NHS employees are not recruited directly through NHS lines of communication (UEL ethical approval is required). This means that NHS staff can participate in research without HRA approval when a student recruits via their own social/professional networks or through a professional body such as the BPS, for example. ▪ The School strongly discourages BSc and MSc/MA students from designing research that requires HRA approval for research involving the NHS, as this can be a very demanding and lengthy process.
1.6	<p>If you require Disclosure Barring Service (DBS) clearance (see section 6), please request a DBS clearance form from the Hub, complete it fully, and return it to applicantchecks@uel.ac.uk. Once the form has been approved, you will be registered with GBG Online Disclosures and a registration email will be sent to you. Guidance for completing the online form is provided on the GBG website: https://fadv.onlinedisclosures.co.uk/Authentication/Login You may also find the following website to be a useful resource: https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/disclosure-and-barring-service</p>
1.7	<p>Checklist, the following attachments should be included if appropriate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Study advertisement ▪ Participant Information Sheet (PIS) ▪ Participant Consent Form ▪ Participant Debrief Sheet ▪ Risk Assessment Form/Country-Specific Risk Assessment Form (see section 5) ▪ Permission from an external organisation (see section 7) ▪ Original and/or pre-existing questionnaire(s) and test(s) you intend to use ▪ Interview guide for qualitative studies ▪ Visual material(s) you intend showing participants

18. Section 2 – Your Details

2.1	Your name:	Lynette Meredith
2.2	Your supervisor's name:	Dr Lorna Farquharson
2.3	Name(s) of additional UEL supervisors:	Dr Vicki Collin
		3rd supervisor (if applicable)
2.4	Title of your programme:	Professional Doctorate in Clinical Psychology
2.5	UEL assignment submission date:	01/05/2025
		Re-sit date (if applicable)

19. Section 3 – Project Details

Please give as much detail as necessary for a reviewer to be able to fully understand the nature and purpose of your research.

3.1	<p>Study title: <u>Please note</u> - If your study requires registration, the title inserted here must be <u>the same</u> as that on PhD Manager</p>	<p>Crafting Lyrics, Breaking Barriers: Exploring the Role of Rap Music in Facilitating Mental Health Expression among Black Men in the UK</p>
3.2	<p>Summary of study background and aims (using lay language):</p>	<p>Despite being over-represented in rates of mental health difficulties, secure mental health services and the criminal justice system, Black men are under-represented in how often they access psychological therapy (McKeown, Robertson, Habte-Mariam, Newbigging & Stockwell-Smith, 2008; McManus, Bebbington, Jenkins & Brugha, 2016; Bignall, Jeraj, Helsby & Butt, 2019).</p> <p>The lack of engagement in mental health services may relate to a reluctance to seek help and talk about psychological distress. For example, research has found that some Black men view mental health services and professionals as stigmatising, discriminative and failing to address cultural barriers (Meechan, 2021, Watkins & Neighbors, 2007). The inter-section between race and gender has also been explored as a factor influencing help-seeking and mental health discourse (e.g. Black masculinity and emotional expression being viewed as ‘weak’, Coleman-Kirumba, Cornish, Horton & Alvarez, 2022).</p> <p>Culturally adaptive interventions have been developed to address these barriers; for example, rap and hip-hop music interventions have shown positive outcomes in contexts such as prisons (e.g. Elligan’s Rap Therapy, 2000).</p> <p>Given the worldwide popularity and cultural significance of rap music within the Black community, and the increasing lyrical reference to mental health amongst artists (Kresovich, Collins,</p>

		<p>Riffe & Carpentier, 2021), it could be used creatively to address lack of engagement with services. Yet, little is known about whether, or how rap music enables Black men to talk about mental health and adversity.</p> <p>Missing in the current literature is how rap music impacts men’s willingness to disclose emotion and hardship (Levy & Keum, 2014). Therefore, this study aims to explore whether and how rap music helps Black men to talk about experiences of mental health and adversity.</p>
3.3	Research question(s):	<p>The proposed research questions are as follows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Does creating rap music impact Black men’s willingness to talk about mental health and adversity? 2. If so, what is it about rap music that impacts disclosure?
3.4	Research design:	<p>This research project adopts qualitative approach, using semi-structured interviews with participants. The 1-1 interviews will be conducted online via MS Teams, lasting between 45-60 minutes. The study is cross-sectional as data will only be collected at one time point (during the interview).</p> <p>A critical realist position will be drawn upon for this research. This position assumes that data reflects what is occurring in the “real world”, however, instead of directly reflecting reality, it reflects an individual’s perspectives and how they relate to others within a historical, social, and cultural context (Willig, 2012; Tuli, 2010). Rather than searching for an objective truth or reality, the individual and collective experiences of Black men will be explored within a broader cultural, historical, and social context.</p>
3.5	<p>Participants: Include all relevant information including inclusion and exclusion criteria</p>	<p>I aim to recruit between 10-12 participants.</p> <p>The following inclusion criteria will be used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aged 18 and above - Identify as male

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Black or mixed heritage Black - Create rap music in any capacity - Live in the UK
3.6	<p>Recruitment strategy: Provide as much detail as possible and include a backup plan if relevant</p>	<p>I aim to recruit via two methods with the use of a research advertisement poster (see Appendix A).</p> <p>The first will be through the support of community-based organisations who have agreed to share my poster to potential participants and via social media (see Appendix F for evidence of permission sought from organisations who have been approached so far).</p> <p>The second will be through social media; I will be sharing my research poster to personal and professional networks through an X account created for this project (@RapMentalHealth).</p>
3.7	<p>Measures, materials or equipment: Provide detailed information, e.g., for measures, include scoring instructions, psychometric properties, if freely available, permissions required, etc.</p>	<p>An interview schedule will be followed (see Appendix D). The interview will ask questions relating to participant’s experiences of creating rap music, whether they have used rap music to talk about personal difficulties and whether doing so makes it easier/harder for disclosure.</p> <p>A laptop with access to the internet, Microsoft Teams, Microsoft Office (Word, Excel), UEL email and UEL OneDrive will be used. The research advertisement poster was designed using the online graphic design tool, Canva (www.canva.com).</p>
3.8	<p>Data collection: Provide information on how data will be collected from the point of consent to debrief</p>	<p>The participant information sheet (see Appendix B) will be shared with those who express interest in taking part in the study. The names and contact details of those who express interest will be stored in a secure excel document on UEL OneDrive for the purpose of recruitment organisation.</p> <p>Informed consent will be collected via a consent form (see Appendix C), which can be electronically signed or printed, signed,</p>

		<p>electronically scanned and sent to me as the researcher. Consent forms will be stored securely my UEL OneDrive.</p> <p>1-1 interviews will be conducted virtually via Microsoft Teams and will last between 45-60 minutes. Interviews will only take place if participants have given consent. The interviews will follow a semi-structured interview guide (see Appendix D). At the end of the interview, I will revisit consent to use the interview data, debrief the participants verbally and give them the debrief sheet (see Appendix E).</p> <p>Audio transcription of the interviews will be downloaded from Microsoft Teams and checked through for accuracy. Manual amendments will be made to the transcriptions where necessary. All identifiable information will be removed, and the transcription file will be securely saved under the assigned pseudonym on UEL OneDrive. The Microsoft Teams recording will then be deleted.</p>	
3.9	Will you be engaging in deception?	YES <input type="checkbox"/>	NO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	If yes, what will participants be told about the nature of the research, and how/when will you inform them about its real nature?	N/A	
3.10	Will participants be reimbursed?	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>
	If yes, please detail why it is necessary.	<p>Participants will be reimbursed for their contributions to this research project, which will involve meeting with me for an interview lasting 45-60 minutes. I feel that it is necessary to compensate participants for their time, as the interview may bring up sensitive topics relating to how rap music has influenced personal disclosure about mental health, trauma, and adversity. Furthermore, speaking to a stranger about personal difficulties may be challenging.</p>	
	How much will you offer?	£10 Amazon voucher per participant	

	Please note - This must be in the form of vouchers, <u>not cash</u> .	
3.11	Data analysis:	<p>Reflexive thematic analysis will be used to analyse the interview data, which involves ‘developing, analyzing and interpreting patterns across a qualitative dataset’ (p.4, Braun & Clarke, 2021). My position as researcher is also considered within this approach, in relation to how my experiences, knowledge and identity may influence interpretation of the data.</p> <p>To analyse the data, the interviews will first be transcribed, then I will follow Braun and Clarke’s (2006) 6 steps to conducting thematic analysis:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Familiarising myself with the data 2. Generating initial codes 3. Searching for themes 4. Reviewing steps 5. Defining themes 6. Writing up <p>My position as a researcher will be reflected upon by keeping a reflexive journal.</p>

20. Section 4 – Confidentiality, Security and Data Retention

It is vital that data are handled carefully, particularly the details about participants. For information in this area, please see the UEL guidance on data protection, and also the UK government guide to data protection regulations.

If a Research Data Management Plan (RDMP) has been completed and reviewed, information from this document can be inserted here.

4.1	Will the participants be anonymised at source?	YES <input type="checkbox"/>	NO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	If yes, please provide details of how the data will be anonymised.		
4.2	Are participants' responses anonymised or are an anonymised sample?	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>
	If yes, please provide details of how data will be anonymised (e.g., all identifying information will be	During transcription, each participant’s name will be replaced by a pseudonym. All identifying	

	removed during transcription, pseudonyms used, etc.).	information will be removed or replaced to ensure anonymity.
4.3	How will you ensure participant details will be kept confidential?	<p>Any personal data that is collected will be held securely and processed in accordance with the UK GDPR and the Data Protection Act 2018. Participants will not be identified by the data collected, on any material resulting from the data collected, or in any write-up of the research.</p> <p>Transcription will only be undertaken by myself to protect the confidentiality of participants. Recordings of the interviews will be destroyed as soon as they have been transcribed to minimise the amount of data being stored.</p> <p>Participants will be given a unique pseudonym and all identifying information will be removed during transcription.</p> <p>A list of participant names and pseudonyms will be kept in a separate document and folder to the transcription data, both stored securely on UEL OneDrive.</p> <p>Consent forms and interview transcripts will be stored in different folders on UEL OneDrive.</p> <p>Participants can request to delete their data after the interview within a 3 week opt-out period.</p>
4.4	<p>How will data be securely stored and backed up during the research?</p> <p>Please include details of how you will manage access, sharing and security</p>	<p>The data will be stored on my UEL's password protected OneDrive account in a folder that is not synchronised on any devices. Data will be sent to my supervisor as a backup during the study and stored on their OneDrive account. Consent forms will be stored as password-protected files in a separate folder to other research data on UEL OneDrive.</p>
4.5	<p>Who will have access to the data and in what form?</p> <p>(e.g., raw data, anonymised data)</p>	<p>I will have access to the raw data. My supervisor will have access to the anonymised data.</p>
4.6	Which data are of long-term value and will be retained?	<p>The anonymised transcripts are of long-term value. It is expected that some of the anonymised</p>

	(e.g., anonymised interview transcripts, anonymised databases)	research data (e.g. quotes from the interviews) will be used for wider dissemination purposes.	
4.7	What is the long-term retention plan for this data?	Anonymised research data will be securely stored on my supervisor's UEL's password-protected OneDrive account for a maximum of 3 years, following which all data will be deleted. All identifiable information will be destroyed as soon as the allowed withdrawal period is over and transcripts have been created unless there has been an agreement with the participants to receive an update from the researcher on the outcomes of the study.	
4.8	Will anonymised data be made available for use in future research by other researchers?	YES <input type="checkbox"/>	NO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	If yes, have participants been informed of this?	YES <input type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>
4.9	Will personal contact details be retained to contact participants in the future for other research studies?	YES <input type="checkbox"/>	NO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	If yes, have participants been informed of this?	YES <input type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>

21. Section 5 – Risk Assessment

If you have serious concerns about the safety of a participant, or others, during the course of your research please speak with your supervisor as soon as possible. If there is any unexpected occurrence while you are collecting your data (e.g., a participant or the researcher injures themselves), please report this to your supervisor as soon as possible.

5.1	Are there any potential physical or psychological risks to participants related to taking part? (e.g., potential adverse effects, pain, discomfort, emotional distress, intrusion, etc.)	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>
	If yes, what are these, and how will they be minimised?	There may be a risk of emotional distress caused by interview discussions with participants around rap music being used in the context of mental health, trauma and adversity. The information sheet will be provided to participants before taking part in the	

		<p>study, which highlights this risk (see Appendix B). A debrief sheet will also be provided after taking part in the study, signposting to different services and organisations participants can access for support (see Appendix E).</p> <p>During the interview, participants will be reminded that they do not have to answer all questions, can take a break if needed, and can withdraw from the study at any point without giving an explanation.</p> <p>Support will be provided by the researcher and Director of Studies, if required. Supervision will be sought by the researcher throughout the project and if any issues arise.</p>		
5.2	<p>Are there any potential physical or psychological risks to you as a researcher?</p> <p>If yes, what are these, and how will they be minimised?</p>	<p>YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>NO</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>There is a minor risk of emotional distress to myself as the researcher caused by hearing potentially difficult experiences disclosed by the participants. Supervision will be provided by my Director of Studies and will be sought out if any issues arise.</p>
5.3	<p>If you answered yes to either 5.1 and/or 5.2, you will need to complete and include a General Risk Assessment (GRA) form (signed by your supervisor). Please confirm that you have attached a GRA form as an appendix:</p>	<p>YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>		
5.4	<p>If necessary, have appropriate support services been identified in material provided to participants?</p>	<p>YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>NO</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>N/A</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/></p>
5.5	<p>Does the research take place outside the UEL campus?</p> <p>If yes, where?</p>	<p>YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>NO</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>Interviews will take place online via Microsoft Teams. I will be conducting the interviews from home – ensuring that the space is quiet and confidential.</p>

5.6	Does the research take place outside the UK?	YES <input type="checkbox"/>	NO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	If yes, where?	Please state the country and other relevant details	
	<p>If yes, in addition to the General Risk Assessment form, a Country-Specific Risk Assessment form must also be completed and included (available in the Ethics folder in the Psychology Noticeboard).</p> <p>Please confirm a Country-Specific Risk Assessment form has been attached as an appendix.</p> <p><u>Please note</u> - A Country-Specific Risk Assessment form is not needed if the research is online only (e.g., Qualtrics survey), regardless of the location of the researcher or the participants.</p>	YES <input type="checkbox"/>	
5.7	<p>Additional guidance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ For assistance in completing the risk assessment, please use the AIG Travel Guard website to ascertain risk levels. Click on 'sign in' and then 'register here' using policy # 0015865161. Please also consult the Foreign Office travel advice website for further guidance. ▪ For on campus students, once the ethics application has been approved by a reviewer, all risk assessments for research abroad must then be signed by the Director of Impact and Innovation, Professor Ian Tucker (who may escalate it up to the Vice Chancellor). ▪ For distance learning students conducting research abroad in the country where they currently reside, a risk assessment must also be carried out. To minimise risk, it is recommended that such students only conduct data collection online. If the project is deemed low risk, then it is not necessary for the risk assessment to be signed by the Director of Impact and Innovation. However, if not deemed low risk, it must be signed by the Director of Impact and Innovation (or potentially the Vice Chancellor). ▪ Undergraduate and M-level students are not explicitly prohibited from conducting research abroad. However, it is discouraged because of the inexperience of the students and the time constraints they have to complete their degree. 		

22. Section 6 – Disclosure and Barring Service (DBS) Clearance

6.1	<p>Does your research involve working with children (aged 16 or under) or vulnerable adults (*see below for definition)?</p> <p>If yes, you will require Disclosure Barring Service (DBS) or equivalent (for those residing in countries outside of the UK) clearance to conduct the research project</p>	<p>YES</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>NO</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>* You are required to have DBS or equivalent clearance if your participant group involves:</p> <p>(1) Children and young people who are 16 years of age or under, or</p> <p>(2) ‘Vulnerable’ people aged 16 and over with particular psychiatric diagnoses, cognitive difficulties, receiving domestic care, in nursing homes, in palliative care, living in institutions or sheltered accommodation, or involved in the criminal justice system, for example. Vulnerable people are understood to be persons who are not necessarily able to freely consent to participating in your research, or who may find it difficult to withhold consent. If in doubt about the extent of the vulnerability of your intended participant group, speak with your supervisor. Methods that maximise the understanding and ability of vulnerable people to give consent should be used whenever possible.</p>			
6.2	<p>Do you have DBS or equivalent (for those residing in countries outside of the UK) clearance to conduct the research project?</p>	<p>YES</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>NO</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/></p>
6.3	<p>Is your DBS or equivalent (for those residing in countries outside of the UK) clearance valid for the duration of the research project?</p>	<p>YES</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>NO</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/></p>
6.4	<p>If you have current DBS clearance, please provide your DBS certificate number:</p>	<p>Please enter your DBS certificate number</p>	
	<p>If residing outside of the UK, please detail the type of clearance and/or provide certificate number.</p>	<p>Please provide details of the type of clearance, including any identification information such as a certificate number</p>	
6.5	<p>Additional guidance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ If participants are aged 16 or under, you will need two separate information sheets, consent forms, and debrief forms (one for the participant, and one for their parent/guardian). ▪ For younger participants, their information sheets, consent form, and debrief form need to be written in age-appropriate language. 		

23. Section 7 – Other Permissions

7.1	<p>Does the research involve other organisations (e.g., a school, charity, workplace, local authority, care home, etc.)?</p>	<p>YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>NO <input type="checkbox"/></p>
	<p>If yes, please provide their details.</p>	<p>Third sector organisations have been approached to ask for permission to support this project with recruitment by sharing the advertisement poster within their networks. These organisations work with/deliver music interventions to the following demographics: men with mental health difficulties, men at risk of offending, and disadvantaged and vulnerable young people.</p> <p>The organisations that have already given permission include:</p> <p>Hip-hop HEALS Raw Material Music & Media Changing the Game Everybody Loves Music CIC Unique Talent CIC</p> <p>Please see Appendix F for evidence of permission from these organisations.</p>	
	<p>If yes, written permission is needed from such organisations (i.e., if they are helping you with recruitment and/or data collection, if you are collecting data on their premises, or if you are using any material owned by the institution/organisation). Please confirm that you have attached written permission as an appendix.</p>	<p>YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	
7.2	<p><u>Additional guidance:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Before the research commences, once your ethics application has been approved, please ensure that you provide the organisation with a copy of the final, approved ethics application or approval letter. Please then prepare a version of the consent 		

	<p>form for the organisation themselves to sign. You can adapt it by replacing words such as 'my' or 'I' with 'our organisation' or with the title of the organisation. This organisational consent form must be signed before the research can commence.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ If the organisation has their own ethics committee and review process, a SREC application and approval is still required. Ethics approval from SREC can be gained before approval from another research ethics committee is obtained. However, recruitment and data collection are NOT to commence until your research has been approved by the School and other ethics committee/s.
--	--

24. Section 8 – Declarations		
8.1	Declaration by student. I confirm that I have discussed the ethics and feasibility of this research proposal with my supervisor:	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
8.2	Student's name: (Typed name acts as a signature)	Lynette Meredith
8.3	Student's number:	2388775
8.4	Date:	03/05/2024
<i>Supervisor's declaration of support is given upon their electronic submission of the application</i>		

Appendix K: Excerpt of Coded Transcript

Codes	Transcript
<p>Rap as a source of happiness</p> <p>Passion for rap</p> <p>Contributing to the world through rap</p> <p>Rap to self-express about lived experiences</p> <p>Rap as a tool for teaching and learning</p> <p>Rap as a source of happiness</p>	<p>MICHAEL: It makes me feel excited. OK, despite the fact that I studied economics. Yeah, I studied economics, but I have come to develop this passion and love for rap music. And anytime I have the opportunity to sit down and write and put some things together, I feel actually kind of like I'm adding something to the world generally, even from my own little corner because you know, I said I write about love, I write about things that happen around and I feel when people listen to it, they will be able to take something out from it, like learn something that so I feel excited about rap music.</p> <p>LYNETTE: Mm hmm. Yeah, it does. The excitement come from being able to share your stories with other people, or where do you think that the excitement comes from?</p>
<p>Impacting lives through rap</p> <p>Sharing a story with others</p>	<p>MICHAEL: Yeah, the excitement actually starts from me being able to think and put those together and also being able to share to people and the most exciting part of the whole thing is me knowing that I am able to impact some lives or pass a message to some set of people. And yeah, so that's the most exciting part of it, yeah.</p>

Appendix L: Excerpt from Reflexive Journal

My thesis poster was circulated on Facebook by [name of individual from community organisation, redacted] to help me with recruitment. They shared with me some feedback that she received under the post relating to the language I had used in my poster, specifically, the phrase “identify as male/Black or mixed heritage Black.” Several individuals expressed discomfort with this wording, arguing that you can’t “identify” as something like male or Black, you either are or you aren’t. One person suggested the wording implied a hidden agenda, thinking that the study might be targeting trans men without stating this explicitly, which led them to say they wouldn’t participate.

This prompted me to reflect carefully on my word choices. I had intentionally used the phrase “identify as” to be inclusive of how individuals self-report both gender and ethnic identity, particularly within a context where rigid, imposed categories have historically excluded or misrepresented people’s lived experiences. My aim was to offer space for participants to define themselves. However, this reaction made me aware that this language can be misinterpreted or perceived differently.

This experience highlighted the complexities of language, and different definitions can lead to differing opinions and responses depending on audience and context. It made me think about how the way language is perceived can shape not only who feels welcome in a study, but also the perceived integrity or transparency of the research itself.

While I continue to feel that self-identification is an important principle in my work, I’m also considering how I might clarify my intentions more explicitly in future work, particularly in spaces where I am not directly present to contextualise or explain. This feedback, although initially uncomfortable, reminded me that the language of research is always open to interpretation and amendment.